

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

D.1.4.2

**Report modellazioni
analitiche e numeriche**

NOVEMBRE 2025

D.1.4.2

**Poročilo o analitičnem in
Numeričnem modeliranju**

NOVEMBER 2025

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Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

D.1.4.2

Report on analytical and numerical modeling

NOVEMBER 2025

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The report collects all the results of the activities of WP1 of the PRO-SIS project, titled “Development and calibration of analytical and numerical algorithms”.

- In “REPORT 1.1: Analytic model for dimensioning”, the “CONSTRAIN” experimental results are gathered, analysed in depth, compared and critically reviewed and a first approach to the definition and calibration of analytical-mechanical models capable to describe the experimental behaviour is presented.
- In “REPORT 1.2: Numerical models for simulating the behaviour of reinforced elements/buildings”, advanced numerical models are developed by using two different finite element software (Abaqus and OOFEM) to simulate the behaviour of the CONSTRAIN experimental samples (masonry piers and spandrels) strengthened with Composite Reinforced Mortar (CRM).
- In “REPORT 1.3: Results of case studies analysis of structural elements and entire buildings”, the advanced numerical models are used for the simulation of case studies of increasing complexity, ranging from single structural elements to entire buildings. Both unreinforced and CRM strengthened masonry configurations are analysed and compared.
- In “REPORT 1.4: Definition of parameters for simplified automatic calculation programs”, the procedures to be used in commercial software for analysing the seismic behaviour of masonry buildings, taking into account the effects of reinforcement interventions using the CONSTRAIN techniques, are analysed.

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.1 Modelli analitici di dimensionamento

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Poročilo 1.1 Analitični modeli za dimenzioniranje

NOVEMBER 2025

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PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.1 Analytic model for dimensioning

NOVEMBER 2025

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Report 1.1

Analytic model for dimensioning

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1. Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 1.1 of the “PRO-SIS” project, aimed at the “Development of analytical models to quantify the performances of structures reinforced with the innovative “CONSTRAIN” techniques and validation with experimental results”.

The CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>) was aimed at developing intervention strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry buildings and assess their effectiveness by means of an extended experimental campaign. The proposed strategies, based on the use of fiber-based composite materials, allow for substantial reductions in seismic vulnerability through interventions executed from the exterior of the buildings, without requiring the relocation of people and belongings inside the buildings.

The aim of the “PRO-SIS” project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for designing and applying these strategies. To this end, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated against the experimental results of “CONSTRAIN”. The results provide designers with robust strategies for designing the proposed systems, as well as instructions for design in commonly used commercial structural design programmes.

This document reports the first approach to the definition and calibration of analytical-mechanical models capable of describing the behaviour of the different structural elements subjected to seismic loads (masonry piers and spandrels, walls subjected to out-of-plane bending, roof and floor ring beams). The report is divided into different sections, for each type of “CONSTRAIN” tests performed. For each section, the first part resumes the previously obtained experimental results, providing also a critical review and an interpretation of the resisting mechanisms. In the second part, the proposed analytical model for estimating the behaviour is described; in the third, the analytic method is applied to the experimental samples and compared with the experimental results.

2. Summary of the “CONSTRAIN” experimental program

The list and main characteristics of the experimental tests carried out within the “CONSTRAIN” project are reported in Table 2.1 (each specimen is identified with an alphanumeric string). The main characteristics of the materials are resumed in Appendix A.

Table 2.1: Summary of the experimental program carried out within the CONSTRAIN project

Type of test	Masonry type	Sample ID	Strengthening
In-plane tests on masonry piers	Stone R2	P-R2U	/
	Stone R2	P-R2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Stone R2	P-R2R-2	CRM on two-sides
	Solid brick B2	P-B2U	/
	Solid brick B2	P-B2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Solid brick B2	P-B2R-2	CRM on two-sides
	Solid brick B1	P-B1U	/
	Solid brick B1	P-B1R	CRM on one-side
In-plane tests on masonry spandrels	Stone R2	S-R2U-1	/
	Stone R2	S-R2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Stone R2	S-R2U-2	/
	Stone R2	S-R2R -2	CRM on two-sides
	Solid brick B2	S-B2U-1	/
	Solid brick B2	S-B2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Solid brick B1	S-B1U-1	/
	Solid brick B1	S-B1R-1	CRM on one-side
Out-of-plane tests on piers	Stone R2	B-R2	CRM on one-side
	Solid brick B2	B-B2	CRM on one-side
	Solid brick B1	B-B1	CRM on one-side
Pushover tests on a pilot building	Stone R2	PB-U	/
	Stone R2	PB-R	CRM on one-side
Out-of-plane tests on roof ring beams	Stone R2	T-R2	GFRP mesh in bed joints
	Solid brick B1	T-B1	GFRP mesh in bed joints
Out-of-plane tests on floor ring beams	Stone R2	C-R2	CFRP eccentric strips
	Solid brick B1	C-B1	CFRP eccentric strips

3. Strengthening with CRM

3.1. Technique characteristics

The Composite Reinforced Mortar - CRM technique (Fig. 3.1.1) can be generally adopted to improve the resistance, displacement and dissipative capacities of existing masonry elements in both in-plane and out-of-plane directions. The technique consists in the application, on the masonry surface (one or both sides), of a mortar coating with preformed Fiber-Reinforced Polymer - FRP composite meshes embedded, in combination with the introduction of transversal connectors. In particular, Glass fibres meshes (GFRP) are considered, with a minimum coating thickness of 30 mm.

In addition, FRP "L"-shaped connectors are inserted into holes drilled in the masonry and injected with resin; in front of each connector, a FRP mesh sheet is positioned to distribute stresses within the coating.

In case of application of CRM at both sides of the masonry (Fig. 3.1.2a), the holes passed side-by-side throughout the masonry; one connector for each side is inserted in the hole, so that the two connectors overlapped within the masonry thickness.

In case of application of CRM only on one side of the masonry (Fig. 3.1.2b), a single connector is inserted. However, in case of double or multiple leaves masonry, additional transversal connectors (called "artificial diaton") are also introduced, involving almost the whole masonry thickness, to create the connection between leaves and prevent leaves separation and delamination phenomena (Fig. 3.1.2c). The artificial diaton is composed of a threaded steel bar centred in a cement-based mortar core injected in a transversal hole drilled in the masonry (typically by using a water-cooled core drilling machine) and with a thick steel washer screwed at the head. The term "artificial diaton" recognises a transversal tying element not originally present in the masonry and introduced during the strengthening intervention. In contrast, "non-artificial diaton" or, simply, "diaton", commonly refers as a large stone element arranged as header during the wall construction, connecting the leaves.

The main characteristics for the CRM component materials adopted in the "CONSTRAIN" tests are resumed in Appendix A.

Fig. 3.1.1 Application of the CRM strengthening technique on a masonry wall.

GFRP element connection (both sides strengthening)

Transversal section

Front view

(a)

GFRP element connection (one side strengthening)

Transversal section

Front view

(b)

Artificial diaton connection

Transversal section

Front view

(c)

Fig. 3.1.2 Main features of the transversal connectors for the CRM strengthening technique: FRP connection for double-sides (a) and single-side (b) application, and additional "artificial diaton" connection for multiple leaves masonry (c).

3.2. In-plane behaviour of piers

3.2.1. Summary and analysis of the experimental results

The pier samples were rectangular masonry panels having a width of 1500 mm and a height of 1960 mm (Fig. 3.2.1). Each specimen was built between a bottom and a top reinforced concrete (RC) beam 300 mm height, 1500 mm long and with a thickness equal to that of the plain masonry. Three different masonry types were considered: R2, B2 and B1 (Appendix A.). A total of eight panels were built and tested (Table 3.1): three in rubble stone masonry (R2), three in double leaf solid brick masonry (B2), and two in single leaf solid brick (B1) masonry. In the strengthened samples, the CRM layer was extended over the upper and lower RC beams to reproduce the continuity of the strengthening system at the piers' extremities in actual structures. The positioning of the GFRP connectors and of GFRP connectors combined with artificial diatones is schematized in Fig. 3.2.2.

Fig. 3.2.1 Main geometric characteristics of the pier samples.

Table 3.1: Summary of the CONSTRAIN experimental tests on piers

Sample ID	Masonry type	Strengthening system	Connectors
P-R2U	R2	/	/
P-R2R-1	R2	CRM on one-side	GFRP + diatons, 1 side
P-R2R-2	R2	CRM on two-sides	GFRP, passing-through
P-B2U	B2	/	/
P-B2R-1	B2	CRM on one-side	GFRP + diatons, 1 side
P-B2R-2	B2	CRM on two-sides	GFRP, passing-through
P-B1U	B1	/	/
P-B1R-1	B1	CRM on one-side	GFRP, 1 side

Fig. 3.2.2 Positioning of the connectors in CRM strengthened pier samples.

The test setup is schematized in Fig. 3.2.3: the lower RC beam was bolted to a stiff steel beam fixed to the laboratory floor. The RC beam at the top of the sample was bolted to the upper stiff steel beam of the testing apparatus. At the lateral extremities of the upper steel beam, two electro-mechanical actuators, connected to the floor, were installed to control the amount of vertical axial load and the rotation at the top. During testing, they were governed so as the applied axial load was maintained constant during the tests (axial stress level was 0.5 MPa) and the rotations of the upper steel beam were constrained. A third actuator, positioned at the side of the upper steel beam (left side), at its mid-height, applied the lateral loading, which was applied by cycles with increasing displacement amplitude. Each load amplitude was repeated only once before it was increased.

Fig. 3.2.3 Schematization of the test setup for piers.

The behaviour of each sample is described in the following, reporting also monitored loads and displacements and evolution of the crack pattern, which was surveyed at the back side by means of a Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system. The main results are then summarized and compared.

The global behaviour of the pier is described in terms of capacity curves, which show the applied horizontal load V_p (shear force) as a function of the horizontal displacement of the top RC beam d_p . The pier drift γ_p was determined by dividing d_p by the pier's height.

According to the typical in-plane failure mechanisms of historic masonry elements, two groups of cracks were generally expected: mainly horizontal cracks at the corners of the pier, related to in-plane bending failure, and diagonal cracks in the center of the pier, indicative of an in-plane shear mechanism. For monitoring such occurrences, the relative displacements along the diagonals (d_1 and d_2) and throughout the piers height (d_{vL} and d_{vR} , at left and right side) were monitored at both sides of the pier samples. The diagonal displacements were measured on a base length of about 2365 mm centred in the pier area; the vertical on a base length of about 1960 mm.

In addition, the global vertical displacements between the upper steel beam and the laboratory floor were also measured (d_{vtot}) to monitor possible additional movements external to the deformations of the masonry sample. Positive displacements conventionally refer to elongations.

- Test P-R2U (Fig. 3.2.4)

The first damage was observed almost in the middle of the wall, where a sub-vertical crack formed. Then, the crack grew in length with increasing load and other cracks formed from the centre of the panel, with an inclined trend. The diagonal cracks grew and eventually connected the corners of the wall. At the end, the unreinforced stone masonry pier responded in shear, characterised by diagonal cracks: the cracks ran almost exclusively through joints and involved the whole masonry thickness. The progressive opening of diagonal cracks was detected by the diagonal transducers (positive values that alternatively occurred at the opposite diagonals); the vertical transducers evidenced a gradual shortening of the sample during the test.

Fig. 3.2.4 Main results of test P-R2U.

- Test P-R2R-1 (Fig. 3.2.5)

It is observed that, before the beginning of the test, the sample had minor cracks in the first mortar bedding and at the base of the coating. This may have likely led to a lower-than-expected initial stiffness, which resulted quite similar to that of the unstrengthened sample. During the test, damage developed differently on the strengthened and unstrengthened sides: the response and damage on the unstrengthened (front) side were again in shear, which was clear from the diagonal cracks. On the strengthened (back) side, the cracks in the coating were almost vertical initially, at the centre of the sample, only starting to incline when approaching to the maximum resistance; horizontal cracks in the coating also appeared near the corners, indicating the activation of bending. Despite these horizontal cracks, the governing mechanism was shear, as evidently from the alternating elongations detected by the diagonal transducers, whereas the global vertical displacements almost remained negative. (d_{Vtot}) The vertical transducers applied at the two sides of the sample (d_V) behaved differently: those on the unstrengthened side mainly measured a gradual compression, while those applied on the mortar coating detected elongations, likely related to the activation of the bending mechanism. The cracking in the unstrengthened side was concentrated in a few large cracks, whereas the cracking in the coating was widely spread out in much more cracks. Finally, almost at the end of the test, a vertical crack was observed at the sides of the sample and the coating diffusely lost bond with the masonry, except where transversal connectors were present, and the also the coating near some of the steel connectors crumbled and the GFRP mesh fractured.

Fig. 3.2.5 Main results of test P-R2R-1

- Test P-R2R-2 (Fig. 3.2.6)

The first cracks were horizontal at the bottom and top corners, indicating the activation of bending damage; however, also some sub-vertical cracks formed at the centre of the sample. When approaching to the maximum resistance, other horizontal, parallel cracks occurred at the corners and several inclined cracks propagated diagonally from the centre of the panel. Horizontal and inclined cracks, widely spread over a large area, indicated the combined activation of bending and shear mechanisms. This was evident also from the consistent elongations monitored by both diagonal and vertical transducers installed on the sample. Close to the end of the test, the coating diffusely lost the bond with masonry, by connectors. Also, a vertical crack between the wythes developed and gradually widened until the end of the test.

Fig. 3.2.6 Main results of test P-R2R-2.

- Test P-B2U (Fig. 3.2.7)

The pier responded in shear, characterised by diagonal cracks: the first cracks were scattered in bricks and head joints, starting from the centre of the panel and then developing along the diagonal trajectories throughout the whole thickness. The diagonal cracks were monitored by the diagonal transducers (positive values occurring alternatively at the opposite diagonals). The progressive shortening of the sample was surveyed by the vertical transducers (negative values). During the test, also significant cracking at the sides of the sample, due to separation of the leaves, was observed.

Fig. 3.2.7 Main results of test P-B2U.

- Test P-B2R-1 (Fig. 3.2.8)

The initial damage in the wall manifested as horizontal cracks at the top and bottom corners. With increasing load, the horizontal cracks propagated until peak resistance, when suddenly an inclined crack formed in the coating and also on the unstrengthened side. In the post-peak response, diagonal cracks in both the coating and the masonry were active and gradually propagated and the separation of the leaves was also observed. At the end of the test, the leaf with the coating diffusely separated and heavily leaned out. However, the transversal connectors prevented the overturning. The combination of several horizontal and inclined cracks in the coating reflected the combined activation of bending and shear mechanisms, as detected also by positive values achieved by both diagonal and vertical transducers.

Fig. 3.2.8 Main results of test P-B2R-1.

- Test P-B2R-2 (Fig. 3.2.9)

The first damage was horizontal cracking at the base and top corners of the wall. This type of damage gradually propagated until peak resistance was reached. In post peak stage, the bending response remained dominant, but inclined cracks also appeared. The GFRP mesh fracture at the top of the wall was observed at collapse. No evident leaves separation of coating debonding were observed.

Fig. 3.2.9 Main results of test P-B2R-2.

- Test P-B1U (Fig. 3.2.10)

The first damage was horizontal cracks at the opposite corners, due to bending mechanism. Shortly after, a vertical crack at the centre of the wall opened. Approaching to the peak resistance, the vertical crack elongated at an angle towards the corners of the wall. Inclined cracking indicates shear response took over (as also detected by diagonal transducers) and continued until collapse was achieved.

Fig. 3.2.10 Main results of test P-B1U.

- Test P-B1R-1 (Fig. 3.2.11)

The sample initially developed horizontal cracks on both the coating and the unstrengthened side. With increasing load, the horizontal cracks in the coating extended and propagated, but on the unstrengthened side some inclined cracks appeared in addition to the horizontal cracks, intersecting in the upper half of the wall. Shortly before peak resistance was reached, inclined cracks appeared also in the coating. After peak resistance, the inclined cracks were active and horizontal cracks barely activated. This continued until the end of the test. Although the inclined cracks were not exactly diagonal (from corner to corner), response was predominantly in shear.

Fig. 3.2.11 Main results of test P-B1R-1.

The capacity curves comparison of unstrengthened and CRM strengthened pier samples is reported in Fig. 3.2.12. The values of V_p and d_p obtained from the eight experimental tests are summarized in Table 3.2 and in Fig. 3.2.13 for first cracking, peak load and end of the test (Cr , Pk , End).

Fig. 3.2.12 Comparison of capacity curves of unstrengthened and CRM strengthened pier samples.

Table 3.2 Values of the lateral load (V_P) and horizontal displacement (d_P) measured in positive and negative loading directions, for the first cracking, peak load and end of the test.

ID	First cracking (Cr)		Peak load (Pk)		End of test (End)	
	V_P [kN]	d_P [mm]	V_P [kN]	d_P [mm]	V_P [kN]	d_P [mm]
P-R2U	83.2	2.0	106.8	4.9	74.7	13.0
	-84.8	-2.0	-108.8	-3.9	-76.2	-13.1
P-R2R-1	91.7	2.3	164.0	12.9	114.8	35.1
	-97.6	-2.5	-155.0	-16.2	-108.5	-32.2
P-R2R-2	157.2	3.7	234.3	19.8	164.0	68.0
	-157.6	-4.7	-224.5	-19.9	-157.1	-50.7
P-B2U	64.2	2.0	78.0	3.1	54.6	12.1
	-62.1	-2.0	-78.6	-4.0	-55.0	-15.0
P-B2R-1	98.0	3.2	157.0	20.1	109.9	38.1
	-95.0	-3.3	-164.0	-20.0	-114.8	-38.0
P-B2R-2	88.2	2.8	200.7	24.1	140.5	69.7
	-84.5	-2.6	-201.4	-25.1	-141.0	-70.4
P-B1U	55.7	1.3	98.5	4.8	68.9	18.1
	-63.4	-1.8	-105.3	-7.9	-73.7	-18.0
P-B1R-1	109.5	3.6	172.2	13.0	120.6	30.8
	-98.4	-3.0	-160.5	-16.1	-112.4	-31.6

Fig. 3.2.13 Main test results of "P" samples: first cracking, peak and near collapse forces (a) and top horizontal displacements (b).

In all the unstrengthened masonry piers, the failure was governed by a pure diagonal cracking mechanism; the cracks had a stair-stepped trend and involved mainly the mortar joints (both head and bed joints). The stone masonry P-R2U attained to a mean peak load of 107.8 kN, quite similar to that of the single leaf brick masonry P-B1U (101.9 kN); a lower resistance was attained by the double leaf brick masonry P-B2U (78.3 kN). The ultimate displacement was quite high for P-B1U (18.1 mm), while lower for P-R2U and P-B2U (about 13.1-13.6 mm), due to the weak wythes connection. An evident leaf separation actually occurred in P-B2U, just after the peak load.

In the samples strengthened at one side only, the diagonal cracking mechanism was evidently detectable on the plain masonry side; diagonal cracks also occurred in the coating on the strengthened side, but in combination with horizontal and inclined cracks originating from the corners at the bottom and top of the pier, indicating also the activation of the in-plane bending mechanism. After reaching the peak load and approaching to collapse, leaf separation and coating debonding started to occur in P-R2R-1 and P-B2R-1 masonry and the coating debonding also activated in P-R2R-1. However, the presence of the transversal anchors contrasted the layer separation and overturning.

A very largely diffused crack pattern occurred in the two-sides strengthened samples, for the combined activation of diagonal cracking and bending mechanisms. The coating debonding (and the leaf separation in P-R2R-2) also activated when the collapse was incipient.

In the stone rubble masonry, the one-side CRM strengthening intervention led to an increase of the pier resistance of 1.48 times and determined an ultimate displacement 2.58 times higher in respect to the plain masonry. In case of strengthening at both sides, such increments resulted, respectively, 2.13 and 4.55 times. Actually, the one-side application provided values of strength and ultimate displacement almost in-between the plain and the two-sides strengthened configurations.

In the double leaf brick masonry, the peak resistance and the ultimate displacement of the one-side reinforced configuration were, respectively, 2.05 and 2.81 times those of the plain masonry. In case of strengthening at both sides, the increments were of 2.57 and 5.17 times. The one-side reinforcement applied on the single leaf brick masonry determined a pier resistance and ultimate displacement of 1.63 and 1.73 times those of the plain masonry.

The cyclic tests allow also to draw the trends of the piers cycle stiffness, K_P (evaluated as the slope of the peak-to-peak line within each loop of the V_P-d_P curve) by varying d_P (Fig. 3.2.14a). The stiffness degradation with increasing distortion shows an approximately power-law trend, with a softer degradation in the strengthened samples, in respect to the unstrengthened ones. At the end of the tests, the cycle stiffness degraded by about 90–95% of the initial value.

The cumulative input energy (E_{in}) and the dissipated hysteretic energy (E_{hys}) were quantified (Fig. 3.2.14b-c), as well as the E_{hys}/E_{in} ratios (Fig. 3.2.14d). E_{in} is the cumulative work to deform the sample from the beginning of the test to a specific target value of displacement d_P . For each loading cycle, it corresponds to the area under the positive and negative branches of the

hysteretic loop of the F_p-d_p graph. Similarly, the cumulative dissipated hysteretic energy E_{hys} is the sum of all the areas included in the hysteretic loops.

Finally, an estimation of the equivalent hysteretic damping with varying target displacement was performed (Fig. 3.2.14e), accordingly to the procedure reported in FEMA 440 [1].

In general, significantly higher input and dissipated cumulative energies resulted from the strengthened samples, in respect to the plain masonry (Table 3.3). The cumulative dissipated hysteretic energy for rubble stone, at the end of the tests, increased by 3.39 and 7.18 times compared to unstrengthened state, for piers P-R2R-1 and P-R2R-2, respectively. In case of two leaf brick masonry, the cumulative dissipated hysteretic energy was increased 5.46 and 8.73 times for piers P-B2R-1 and P-B2R-2, respectively. In case of single leaf brick masonry, the single sided application of coating increased the amount of hysteretic cumulative dissipated hysteretic energy by a factor of 4.45.

Initially, the equivalent hysteretic damping, ξ_{hys} , ranged within 0.1-0.2, then experienced a rapid drop (more substantial in the strengthened samples) before increase again and reaching higher values (generally, up to 0.25-0.30).

Table 3.3 Cumulative input energy E_{in} and dissipated hysteresis E_{hys} at peak load (P_k) and at the end of the test (End), mean dissipated energy ratio in the cycles (E_{hys}/E_{in}). The ratios between strengthened and unstrengthened samples, for both E_{in} and E_{hys} are also calculated.

	Peak load (P_k)					End of the test (End)				
	E_{in} [J]	$E_{in,R}/E_{in,U}$ [-]	E_{hys} [J]	$E_{hys,R}/E_{hys,U}$ [-]	E_{hys}/E_{in} [-]	E_{in} [J]	$E_{in,R}/E_{in,U}$ [-]	E_{hys} [J]	$E_{hys,R}/E_{hys,U}$ [-]	E_{hys}/E_{in} [-]
P-R2U	2.84	1.00	2.02	1.00	0.71	11.95	1.00	9.62	1.00	0.81
P-R2R-1	16.33	5.74	12.21	6.06	0.75	44.65	3.74	32.59	3.39	0.73
P-R2R-2	27.06	9.52	14.44	7.16	0.53	101.13	8.46	69.10	7.18	0.68
P-B2U-1	2.02	1.00	1.14	1.00	0.56	8.04	1.00	6.11	1.00	0.76
P-B2R-1	18.92	9.39	9.51	8.31	0.50	52.41	6.52	33.36	5.46	0.64
P-B2R-2	27.01	13.40	11.42	9.98	0.42	87.72	10.91	53.32	8.73	0.61
P-B1U-1	4.85	1.00	2.43	1.00	0.50	13.59	1.00	7.04	1.00	0.52
P-B1R-1	14.79	3.05	7.05	2.91	0.48	47.58	3.50	31.33	4.45	0.66

Fig. 3.2.14. Piers stiffness and energy characteristics, varying the cycle target displacement d_p .

3.2.2. Analytic model

Symbols:

t	masonry pier thickness	β	pier slenderness factor ($1.0 \leq \beta = l/b \leq 1.5$)
b	masonry pier width	χ	effectiveness reduction factor (=1 for CRM at both-sides, ≤ 1 at one side)
l	masonry pier height (i.e. "effective length")	γ	model coefficient (=2)
E_m	masonry Young's modulus	A_G	net cross section of a GFRP wire
G_m	masonry shear modulus ($\sim 1/3E_m$)	T_G	mean tensile resistance of a GFRP wire
i	number of CRM-strengthened sides (1-2)	s	GFRP mesh grid pitch
t_c	plaster nominal thickness	l_f	CRM effective length ($=l$, but $\leq b$)
E_c	plaster Young's modulus	$\varepsilon_{lim,G}$	limit tensile strain of GFRP
G_c	plaster shear modulus ($\sim 0.4E_c$)	E_G	GFRP Young's modulus
η	coefficient related to the pier static scheme (e.g. 3 for cantilever, 12 for shear type)	f_m	masonry compressive strength
I	second bending moment of the uncracked pier cross section ($tb^3/12$)	α	coefficient of bending moment distribution (e.g. 1 for cantilever, 2 for shear type)
σ_0	mean vertical compressive stress on the pier	x	depth of the neutral axis of the cracked cross-section
τ_0	equivalent masonry shear strength for $\sigma_0 = 0$ (for "Turnšek and Čačovič" formula)		

To schematize analytically, in a simplified way, the in-plane lateral performances of masonry piers, an elastic-plastic behaviour can be considered (Fig. 3.2.15). To estimate the stiffness, resistance and ultimate displacement capacities, well-known correlations available in the literature can be considered for the unstrengthened masonry. For CRM strengthened masonry, the correlations need to be adjusted to account for the CRM contribution.

Fig. 3.2.15 Generic, simplified elastic-plastic schematization of the in-plane lateral performances of masonry piers (red line), in comparison with actual performances (black line).

To evaluate the pier stiffness, K_e , both the flexural and shear deformability shall be accounted, as indicated in Eq.(3.1). In case of CRM strengthened masonry, equivalent Young and shear moduli shall be considered, evaluating the average values between masonry and mortar coating, weighted on the respective thickness.

$$K_e = \frac{1}{\frac{l^3}{\eta IE} + \frac{1.2l}{Gbt}} \quad (3.1)$$

For the evaluation of the pier's in-plane lateral resistance, V_p , the weakest mechanism between shear failure (due to diagonal cracking), $V_{p,d}$, and bending, $V_{p,f}$, is considered:

$$V_p = \min(V_{p,d}; V_{p,f}) \quad (3.2)$$

The typical crack patterns that occur during seismic events are illustrated in Fig. 3.2.16. For these mechanisms to activate, the diagonal masonry strut should not prematurely fail in compression:

$$V_p \leq 0.25 \cdot b \cdot t \cdot f_m \quad (3.3)$$

Fig. 3.2.16 Typical in-plane failure mechanism of masonry piers: diagonal cracking (a) and bending (b).

For the unstrengthened masonry piers (suffix URM), different resistant models can be found in the literature to estimate $V_{p,d(URM)}$. For example, the well-known "Turnšek and Čačovič" correlation, suitable for both regular and irregular masonry, can be applied (according to C8.7.1.16 in MIT 2019 [2]):

$$V_{p,d(URM)} = \frac{1.5\tau_0}{\beta} b \cdot t \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_o}{1.5\tau_0}} \quad (3.4)$$

The in-plane bending resistance of the unreinforced masonry piers is mainly due to the masonry compressive resistance and the stabilizing effect of the vertical loads ([7.8.2] in MIT 2018 [3]):

$$V_{p,f(URM)} = \frac{\alpha M_{P(URM)}}{l} = \frac{\alpha}{l} \frac{\sigma_o b^2 t}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_o}{0.85 f_m} \right) \quad (3.5)$$

Both mechanisms benefit from the contribution of the CRM system, as the fiber-based composite material (the mesh wires), crossing both the diagonal and the horizontal cracks,

limits their opening, fostering a wider stress diffusion. However, to be effective against the bending failure, the CRM system has to be sufficiently extended beyond the pier end sections. Due to the lack of specific correlations for the evaluation of the resistance of CRM strengthened masonry pier (suffix CRM), reference is herein made to CNR-DT 215/2018 [4], an Italian guideline available for FRCM strengthening systems, that have several similarities with CRM ones. According to [4], the contribution given by the wires along the loading direction crossing the diagonal crack shall be added to that of the unstrengthened masonry:

$$V_{P,d(CRM)} = V_{P,d(URM)} + \chi \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot i \cdot \frac{A_G}{s} \cdot l_f \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G \quad (3.6)$$

Note that, if the tensile failure of the fibers is attained, the factor $A_G \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G$ corresponds to the tensile resistance of a single wire, T_G .

For the bending failure mechanism of the CRM strengthened masonry pier, the tensile-resistant contribution of the vertical wires crossing the horizontal cracks at the end sections shall be accounted:

$$V_{P,f(CRM)} = \frac{\alpha M_{P(CRM)}}{l} = \frac{\alpha}{l} \left[0.8x \cdot f_m \cdot t \left(\frac{b}{2} - 0.4x \right) + \chi \frac{i \cdot A_G \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G}{s} \cdot \frac{(b-x)}{2} \left(\frac{b}{6} + \frac{x}{3} \right) \right] \quad (3.7)$$

$$\text{with } x = b \cdot t \left(\sigma_0 + \chi \frac{i A_G \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G}{2s \cdot t} \right) / \left(0.8 \cdot f_m \cdot t + \chi \frac{i \cdot A_G \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G}{2s} \right).$$

Basically, $M_{P(CRM)}$ shall be evaluated by analysing a reinforced section subjected to combined compression and bending in cracked conditions, assuming conservation of plane sections, perfect bond among materials, masonry cracked in tension and plastic in compression, fibre mesh with linear-elastic behaviour in tension until the limit strain.

It is observed that the plaster contribution is neglected in both mechanisms. It is also worth noting that the introduction of effective transversal connectors in multiple-leaves masonry could be grossly considered by increasing the masonry shear strength, τ_0 . Appropriate coefficients (range 1.2-1.5, depending on masonry type) are provided in C8.5.II of MIT 2019 [2].

The ultimate displacement capacity of the masonry pier, d_{Pu} , is evaluated on the basis of the chord rotation limits at the pier extremities, θ_{Pu} . For unstrengthened masonry, the values provided in C8.7.1.3.1.1 of MIT 2019 [2] can be applied – Eq. (3.8).

$$\theta_{Pu(URM)} = \begin{cases} 0.005 & \text{if } V_{P,d(URM)} < V_{P,f(URM)} \\ 0.010 & \text{if } V_{P,d(URM)} \geq V_{P,f(URM)} \end{cases} \quad (3.8)$$

For CRM masonry, in the lack of any guidance, doubled values could be considered, based on experimental evidences – Eq. (3.9).

$$\theta_{Pu(CRM)} = \begin{cases} 0.010 & \text{if } V_{P,d(CRM)} < V_{P,f(CRM)} \\ 0.020 & \text{if } V_{P,d(CRM)} \geq V_{P,f(CRM)} \end{cases} \quad (3.9)$$

3.2.3. Application and validation

The analytical model described in §3.2.2 is adopted to evaluate the lateral performances of the CONSTRAIN experimental tests on the pier samples resumed in §3.2.1.

The values of the unstrengthened masonry shear strength (τ_0) considered in the formulations are calculated from the CONSTRAIN experimental tests obtained for the unstrengthened pier samples (P-R2U, P-B2U and P-B2U in §3.2.1). In particular, since the diagonal cracking failure was attained in all the unstrengthened samples, Eq. (3.4) is solved for τ_0 . For the resistance $V_{P,d(URM)}$, a bi-linearization of the backbone capacity curves is performed (according to C7.3.4.2 of MIT 2018 [3]) and the mean plastic value between positive and negative loading directions is considered.

For the Young's modulus, E_m , and the compressive strength, f_m , a preliminary estimation was done on the basis of Tab.C8.5.I of MIT 2019 [2], by performing a linear interpolation within the provided ranges for the different masonry types, starting from the values of shear strength τ_0 . Actually, for the rubble stone sample, the values estimated by this procedure resulted slightly higher than the results of the monotonic compressive tests on masonry wallets (Appendix A.). Therefore, those experimental outcomes were assumed as consistent and representative and were thus prudentially set as input parameters for masonry R2. Conversely, for the solid brick masonry (both B2 and B1), the results of the monotonic compressive tests on masonry wallets (Appendix A.) provided values of both E_m and f_m significantly higher than Tab.C8.5.I. In this case, this latter calculated values were set as input parameters, since prudentially believed to be more representative for a masonry that is subjected to cyclic loading and whose orientation of principal compressive stresses may from the vertical.

The main results are summarized in Fig. 3.2.17 and compared graphically with the experimental capacity curves. It is worth to note that the elastic deformability of the apparatus ($1/K_{add,P}$, experimentally measured as 1/56000 mm/N) is added to that of the samples, as it is not negligible.

Main data								
b	[mm]	1500	σ_0	[MPa]	0.5	η	[-]	12
l	[mm]	1960	A_G	[mm ²]	3.8	α	[-]	2
t_c	[mm]	30	T_G	[kN]	5.11			
E_c	[GPa]	10	s	[mm]	66			
G_c	[GPa]	4	l_f	[mm]	1500			

		P-R2U	P-R2R-1	P-R2R-2
t	[mm]	350	350	350
f_m	[MPa]	2.48	2.48	2.48
τ_o	[MPa]	0.071	0.071	0.071
i	[-]	-	1	2
χ	[-]	-	1.0	1.0
E	[MPa]	1074.2	1931.3	2788.5
G	[MPa]	358.1	700.9	1043.8
K_e	[N/mm]	54214	103178	152022
$K_{add,P}$	[N/mm]	56000	56000	56000
x	[mm]	-	437.3	490.6
M_p	[kNm]	150.2	190.9	221.0
$V_{p,f}$	[kN]	153.2	194.8	225.5
$V_{p,d}$	[kN]	102.2	160.2	218.3
V_p	[kN]	102.2	160.2	218.3
Mode	[-]	Shear	Shear	Shear*
$d_{p,e}$	[mm]	3.71	4.41	5.33
$d_{p,u}$	[mm]	11.6	21.4	21.4 (41.0)

		P-B2U	P-B2R-1	P-B2R-2
t	[mm]	250	250	250
f_m	[MPa]	2.98	2.98	2.98
τ_o	[MPa] (*)	0.068	0.068x1.3	0.068x1.3
i	[-]	-	1	2
χ	[-]	-	1.0	1.0
E	[MPa]	1335.7	2535.7	3735.7
G	[MPa]	445.2	925.2	1405.2
K_e	[N/mm]	48150	97104	145939
$K_{add,P}$	[N/mm]	56000	56000	56000
x	[mm]	-	386.4	450.3
M_p	[kNm]	112.9	153.6	185.7
$V_{p,f}$	[kN]	115.2	156.8	189.5
$V_{p,d}$	[kN]	71.2	141.3	199.3
V_p	[kN]	71.2	141.3	199.3
Mode	[kN]	71.2	141.3	189.5
$d_{p,e}$	[-]	Shear	Shear**	Bending
$d_{p,u}$	[mm]	2.75	3.98	4.68
M_p	[mm]	11.1	21.1	40.7 (40.7)

(*) since $V_{p,f}$ and $V_{p,d}$ are very close, a combined shear/bending failure is expected, thus $d_{p,u}$ could likely reach values related to flexure.

(*) 1.3 is the amplification factor of the shear strength in multiple-leaves solid brick masonry, to account for the benefits of effective transversal connectors (since leaves separation actually occurred in P-B2U, but not in P-B2R-1 and P-B2R-2).

(**) since $V_{p,f}$ and $V_{p,d}$ are very close, a combined shear/bending failure is expected, thus $d_{p,u}$ could likely reach values related to flexure.

		P-B1U	P-B1R-1
t	[mm]	250	250
f_m	[MPa]	3.84	3.84
τ_o	[MPa]	0.108	0.108
i	[-]	-	1
χ	[-]	-	1.0
E	[MPa]	1638.6	2838.6
G	[MPa]	546.2	1026.2
K_e	[N/mm]	59069	108041
$K_{add,P}$	[N/mm]	56000	56000
x	[mm]	-	304.2
$M_{P(CRM)}$	[kNm]	119.1	163.2
$V_{P,f(CRM)}$	[kN]	121.5	166.5
$V_{P,d(URM)}$	[kN]	94.2	94.2
$V_{P,d(CRM)}$	[kN]	-	152.3
$V_{P(CRM)}$	[kN]	94.2	152.3
Mode	[-]	Shear	Shear
$d_{P,e(CRM)}$	[mm]	3.28	4.13
$d_{P,u(CRM)}$	[mm]	11.5	21.3

Fig. 3.2.17 Analytic results concerning the masonry pier samples and comparison with the experimental behaviour

3.3. In-plane behaviour of spandrels

3.3.1. Summary and analysis of the experimental results

The samples consisted of “H”-shape masonry panels (Fig. 3.3.1) aimed at recreating the spandrel area. To facilitate a uniform load distribution in testing, r.c. beams were created at the base and at the top of each masonry column.

Three different masonry types were considered: R2, B2 and B1 (Appendix A.). In the rubble stone samples, a timber lintel (2 beams, cross section 170x170 mm²), indenting in each lateral column for 150 mm, was introduced under the spandrel, to reproduce the typical arrangements in historical stone buildings. Differently, in the solid brick samples, a masonry jack arch was created at the spandrel intrados, with couples of bricks arranged alternatively as headers or stretchers (height 250 mm).

Fig. 3.3.1 Main geometric characteristics of the spandrel samples.

Four “H”-shape panels were built and tested firstly unstrengthened, up to a damage level close to the ultimate. Then they were repaired, retrofitted and tested again, up to a near-collapse condition (Table 3.4). The positioning of the GFRP connectors and of GFRP connectors combined with artificial diatones is schematized in Fig. 3.3.2.

Table 3.4: Summary of the CONSTRAIN experimental tests on spandrels.

Sample ID	Masonry type	Strengthening system	Connectors
S-R2U-1	R2	/	/
S-R2R-1	R2	CRM on one-side	GFRP + diatons, 1 side
S-R2U2	R2	/	/
S-R2R-2	R2	CRM on two-sides	GFRP, passing-through
S-B2U	B2	/	/
S-B2R	B2	CRM on one-side	GFRP + diatons, 1 side
S-B1U	B1	/	/
S-B1R	B1	CRM on one-side	GFRP, 1 side

Fig. 3.3.2 Positioning of the connectors in CRM strengthened spandrel samples.

The test apparatus consisted of two independent horizontal steel beams, placed on support knuckle joints (equipped with load cells). The joints allowed the possibility of carrying loads in both compression and tension. Both joints were rotational; in addition, the right joint, allowed horizontal translations. Each external wall column of the H-shape masonry sample was positioned on one of the steel beams, vertically centered with the knuckle joint. Two servo-hydraulic actuators oriented vertically were attached to the free, external ends of the steel beams and locked on independent steel frames. Four hydraulic pistons were installed on the columns to apply an axial compressive load. Each pistons was contrasted at the top by steel elements connected to the steel beams at the base by means of threaded rods. The four pistons were connected in parallel and introduced a constant force (correspondent to an axial stress level of about 0.33 MPa on the masonry columns). During the tests, the two external actuators moved at the same speed in opposite directions, which means that the two masonry piers rotated with the same direction and intensity. This caused shear and bending in the spandrel. The load was applied cyclically in the positive (clockwise rotation of the beams) and negative directions (anti-clockwise rotation), gradually increasing the target amplitude and performing three repetitions for each.

Fig. 3.3.3 Schematization of the test setup for spandrels.

The behaviour of each sample is described in the following, reporting also monitored loads and displacements and evolution of the crack pattern (surveyed at the front side by means of a Digital Image Correlation system). The main results are then summarized and compared.

The global behaviour of the spandrels is described in terms of capacity curves, representing the shear load, V_S , varying the vertical distortion d_S . The shear load V_S was obtained from the vertical translation equilibrium of the external vertical forces acting on the left half (as well as right half) of the sample, i.e. load applied by the outer actuator and the reaction at the support. The distortion d_S was calculated by using the following equation:

$$d_S = (\delta_{V,r} - \delta_{V,l}) \cdot \left(\frac{b_S}{2} + \frac{b_P}{2} \right) / \left(\frac{b_P}{2} \right), \quad (3.10)$$

where b_S and b_P are the spandrel and the pier widths, respectively and δ_V the vertical displacements in correspondance on the inner corners of the two masonry columns (right - r , and left - l). The spandrel drift γ_S was determined by dividing d_S by the spandrel's length.

In addition to the distortion, the horizontal sliding of the right support (d_H) was monitored during the tests.

According to the typical in-plane failure mechanisms of historic masonry elements, two groups of cracks were generally expected: mainly vertical cracks at the spandrels ends, related to in-plane bending failure, and diagonal cracks within the spandrels, indicative of an in-plane diagonal shear mechanism. For monitoring such occurrences, the DIC system was employed to evaluate the trends of the equivalent horizontal strains at the top and the bottom of the spandrels (ε_{top} and ε_{bot} , respectively) and of the equivalent strains across the spandrels diagonals (ε_{d1} and ε_{d2} , respectively). Strains ε_{top} and ε_{bot} were calculated on a base length of about 1780 mm; ε_{d1} and ε_{d2} were calculated on a base length of about 700 mm centred in the spandrel area. In general, the monitored strains were positive (tensile strains), regardless of the loading direction, consistently with the formation of the cracks. Not-negligible residual strains were expected, as long as damage progressed.

- Test S-R2U-1 (Fig. 3.3.4)

The first cracking appeared at the spandrels opposite corners. The cracks gradually expanded, following the mortar joints in an almost vertical pattern until they spanned the entire height. Similar cracks emerged on both sides of the sample, spanning the full thickness of the wall. A significant drop in stiffness then occurred, and the cracking evolved asymmetrically. When loaded in the positive direction, damage was concentrated in the two vertical cracks at the spandrel ends. In contrast, a diagonal crack appeared when loaded in the negative direction, originating from the top-right corner, where the damage was primarily focused. Despite these differences, the load decrease was gradual in both cases. A mixed failure mode, involving both bending and shear, was observed. The horizontal displacements at the right support noticed the right pier pulled away from the left one; residual slip significantly increased with the number of load cycles. The horizontal strains at top and bottom resulted almost comparable, while diagonal strains were not, due to the activation of the inclined crack along one diagonal only.

Fig. 3.3.4 Main results of test S-R2U-1.

- Test S-R2R-1 (Fig. 3.3.5)

The first cracks occurred at the opposite corners of the spandrel and initially involved only the mortar of the coating; then the cracks extended almost vertically, also new parallel cracks formed nearby. Inclined and diagonal cracks developed, spreading over the entire coating surface till the progressive failure of the GFRP wires, leading to a rapid load decrease. Mainly the horizontal wires at the spandrel corners fractured, indicating that final failure was due to bending, despite numerous diagonal cracks. During the test, the bond of the coating with the masonry was gradually lost over a large area of the cracked spandrel; no separation between the wall leaves was observed. On the unstrengthened back side, the masonry cracks were fewer than on the strengthened front side and reproduced the crack pattern of a plain wall, S-R2U-1. The right support began sliding quite early, as the first cracks occurred; the residual sliding progressed with the cycles. The horizontal strains progressed almost symmetrically, and so did the diagonal strains.

Fig. 3.3.5 Main results of test S-R2R-1.

- Test S-R2U-2 (Fig. 3.3.6)

The first cracks appeared at the opposite corners and the damage concentrated in two main, almost vertical cracks at the spandrel extremities, indicating failure governed by the bending mechanism (diagonal strains were quite negligible). Similar cracks emerged on both sides of the sample, spanning the full thickness of the wall. After the peak load, a gradual drop or resistance was surveyed, also with the progressive gradual residual slip between the piers. The horizontal strains at top and bottom were almost comparable.

Fig. 3.3.6 Main results of test S-R2U-2.

- Test S-R2R-2

The first cracks formed in the coating, at opposite corners of the spandrel, displaying a vertical pattern. These cracks progressively extended and, due to load reversal, spanned the entire height of the spandrel. Additional vertical cracks appeared near the previous ones, followed also by inclined cracks in the coating within the spandrel area, so that the entire coating surface was covered by cracks once the peak resistance was reached. The collapse mode was flexural: the vertical crack at the right end of the spandrel widened, leading to the failure of the GFRP wires crossing the crack, on both the front and back sides. At the end of the test, some debonding of the coating from the masonry was observed around the wider cracks. Additionally, initial separation of the wall leaves was detected in the pier portions below the lintel. The horizontal sliding at the right support was quite limited until peak load; after that, increasing values were recorded, along with significant residual slip.

Actually, during the data post-processing, it emerged that a malfunction determined an unexpected, progressive reduction of the axial pre-stress level after the first cracking. With the reduced vertical load, N_s , horizontal cracks formed at the base of both piers, at the interface between the masonry and the RC beams: a crack opened from the inner corner of the left pier when loading in the positive direction, and from the inner corner of the right one for the opposite loading. The alternated opening of these cracks limited the actual rotation of the cracked pier in respect to that imposed by the apparatus, affecting the net spandrel distortion. The bottom horizontal strains resulted significantly higher than the top ones; diagonal strains were comparable.

Fig. 3.3.7 Main results of test S-R2R-2.

- Test S-B2U (Fig. 3.3.10)

The first significant cracking occurred almost at the attainment of the peak load: the cracks were inclined, running mostly through the mortar joints (diagonal shear failure mechanism) and determined an abrupt resistance decay and a large horizontal sliding at the base right support. This triggered the lower portion of the masonry spandrel (mainly, the jack arch), fully surrounded by cracks, to detach from the upper portion at the end of the test. The crack pattern was identical on both sides of the sample, spanning the full thickness of the wall. The horizontal strains at top and bottom resulted almost comparable, as well as the diagonal strains (which clearly detected the occurrence of symmetric diagonal cracking).

Fig. 3.3.8 Main results of test S-B2U.

- Test S-B2R (Fig. 3.3.11)

The first cracks formed in the coating, at diagonally opposite corners of the spandrel, then the cracks progressively spread: they were initially almost vertical, but then also diagonal cracks appeared in the centre. When peak load was reached, the cracks covered the entire spandrel surface. On the reverse side (unstrengthened masonry), the cracks also gradually diffused, but the trend was that of stepped cracking that mainly followed previously repaired cracks. The lower masonry portion of the spandrel (the jack arch) tended to detach (similar to what occurred in the unstrengthened configuration). The final collapse was due to failure of some vertical GFRP wires around the left end of the spandrel, reminiscent of vertical shear sliding. No layer separation emerged between the wall leaves but some debonding of the coating around the cracked areas; however the composite action was maintained until the end. The horizontal strains progressed almost symmetrically, and so did the diagonal strains.

Fig. 3.3.9 Main results of test S-B2R.

- Test S-B1U (Fig. 3.3.10)

The first cracks occurred at the ends of the jack arch, first at the left corner of the spandrel (when loading in the positive direction) and then suddenly also in the right corner (when loading in the negative one). When reaching peak load, cracks also formed around the top corners of the spandrel, leading to activation of the bending failure mechanism. The upper cracks then opened with an inclined pattern, while the lower cracks opened almost vertically, causing a rapid load drop. A horizontal crack also appeared at the top of the jack arch. After the peak load, the right pier moved horizontally, regardless of the loading direction. By the end, the arch was completely surrounded by cracks and on the verge of collapse. The damage pattern on the back of the wall mirrored that on the front, with cracks running almost exclusively through the mortar joints. The horizontal strains at top and bottom were almost comparable; the diagonal strains resulted almost negligible

Fig. 3.3.10 Main results of test S-B1U.

- Test S-B1R (Fig. 3.3.11)

Cracks in the coating firstly activated in the spandrel's lower corners and then, at the top corners. Such cracks progressed almost vertically, meanwhile other inclined cracks gradually occurred in the vicinity. At the reaching of the peak load, the entire coating was diffusely covered by cracks, and the cracks at the centre of the spandrel were diagonal. Then, the horizontal GFRP wires at the right end of the spandrel progressively failed in tension, starting from the bottom corner. The coating debonded in the cracked areas, but the anchors and the diatones maintained composite action. The unstrengthened side experienced inclined cracks very similar to those observed in the test of the unstrengthened wall, S-B1-U. The crack above the jack arch opened again, but the arch fallin was prevented. The sliding of the right support was significant and also in the residual sliding. Both the horizontal strains and the diagonal ones progressed almost symmetrically.

Fig. 3.3.11 Main results of test S-B1R.

The capacity curves of unstrengthened and CRM strengthened spandrel samples are compared in Fig. 3.3.12. The values of shear force V_s and distortion d_s obtained from the eight experimental tests are summarized in Table 3.4 and in Fig. 3.3.13 for the three limit state, namely, first cracking, peak load and near collapse (Cr , Pk , Nc). The latter was identified at the occurrence of a 30% load decrease after the peak load.

Fig. 3.3.12 Comparison of capacity curves of unstrengthened and CRM strengthened spandrel samples.

Table 3.5 Values of the shear force (V_s) and distortion (d_s) measured in positive and negative loading directions, for the first cracking, peak load and near collapse limit states.

ID	First cracking (Cr)		Peak load (Pk)		Near collapse (Nc)	
	V_s [kN]	d_s [mm]	V_s [kN]	d_s [mm]	V_s [kN]	d_s [mm]
S-R2U-1	23.3	0.28	28.9	0.49	20.2	4.27
	-24.0	-0.33	-25.3	-0.55	-17.7	-4.23
S-R2R-1	29.7	0.26	75.5	18	52.8	24.7
	-26.7	-0.29	-67.5	-17.6	-47.2	-24.6
S-R2U-2	22.1	0.19	23.9	0.26	16.7	3.22
	-22.4	-0.12	-23.5	-0.19	-16.4	-3.15
S-R2R-2	48.6	0.63	88.1	17.8	61.7	31.69
	-53.0	-0.71	-84.8	-17.6	-59.4	-32.15
S-B2U-1	+23.6	+0.44	+23.6	+0.44	+16.5	+0.85
	-15.7	-0.30	-15.7	-0.30	-11.0	-0.55
S-B2R-1	+21.6	+0.26	+45.5	+8.4	+31.9	+18.05
	-23.8	-0.29	-42.7	-8.4	-29.9	-18.50
S-B1U-1	+22.9	+0.29	+26.6	+0.59	+18.6	+1.09
	-26.8	-0.26	-30.6	-0.54	-20.1	-1.17
S-B1R-1	+19.6	+0.33	+38.9	+8.7	+27.2	+18.4
	-23.2	-0.14	-37.4	-7.5	-26.2	-18.4

Fig. 3.3.13. Main test results of "S" samples: first cracking, peak and near collapse forces (a) and distortion (b)

The failure of the two unstrengthened rubble stone spandrels and of the single-leaf solid brick masonry was dominated by the bending mechanism, as evidenced from the typical crack

pattern with sub-vertical cracks at the spandrel extremities (with cracks running mostly through the mortar joints). Very similar peak resistance values were attained: 27.1 kN for S-R2U-1, 23.7 kN for S-R2U-2 and 28.6 kN for S-B1U. In contrast, the unreinforced masonry spandrel made of double-leaves solid brick failed by shear (diagonal cracks, mean peak load 19.7 kN). The capacity curves showed a quite ductile response for the stone samples with the timber lintel (ultimate displacements 4.25 mm and 3.19 mm, for S-R2U-1 and -2), while the response was brittle in case of masonry arch (0.7 mm for S-B2U and 0.3 mm for S-B1): at the end of the tests, the arch was completely surrounded by cracks and was about to fall.

In the strengthened spandrels, the first nearly vertical cracks formed in the coating, at the extremities of the spandrel (activation of bending mechanism), but then progressively spread, and diagonal cracks also appeared (activation of diagonal cracking mechanism), covering the entire spandrel. At the end of the tests, the bond between the coating and the spandrel was lost in the cracked areas, but the anchors assured the composite action until the end, when the GFRP wires progressively failed in tension at the extremities. It resulted mean peak loads of 71.5 kN for S-R2R-1, 44.1 kN for S-B2R-1 and S-B1R-1; the mean ultimate displacements were 24.7 mm, 18.3 mm and 18.4 mm, respectively. For the sample S-R2R-2, the mean peak resistance and ultimate displacement values were 86.5 kN and 31.9 mm. However, as already noted, the accidental malfunction of the vertical pressure control system limited the pier rotation, affecting the net spandrel distortion.

In the rubble stone masonry, the one-side retrofitting intervention increased the spandrel resistance to 2.8 times of original and the ultimate distortion by 6.6 times with respect to the plain masonry. In case of retrofitting at both sides, the improvement was 3.4 and 8.6 times for the same quantities (lower than expected due to the anomaly in the vertical loading system). In the single-leaf solid brick masonry, the peak force of the one-side retrofitted configuration was 2.24 times that of the unstrengthened one and the distortion more than 26.1 times higher. In the double-leaves solid brick masonry, increment ratios were, respectively, 1.33 and 16.3 times.

The cyclic tests allow also to draw the trends of the spandrels cycle stiffness, K_S (evaluated as the slope of the peak-to-peak line within each loop of the V_S-d_S curve) by varying the distortion d_S (Fig. 3.3.13a). The stiffness degradation with increasing distortion shows an approximately power-law trend, with a softer degradation in the strengthened samples, in respect to the unstrengthened ones. The stiffness gap within the three loops of a single target displacement was quite low. At the end of the tests, the cycle stiffness degraded by about 90–95% of the initial value.

The cumulative input energy (E_{in}) and the dissipated hysteretic energy (E_{hys}) were quantified (Fig. 3.3.13b-c), as well as the E_{hys}/E_{in} ratios (Fig. 3.3.13d). E_{in} is the cumulative work to deform the sample from the beginning of the test to a specific target value of distortion. For each loading cycle, it corresponds to the area under the positive and negative branches of the hysteretic loop of the F_S-d_S graph. Similarly, the cumulative dissipated hysteretic energy E_{hys} is the sum of all the areas included in the hysteretic loops. Three points for each target displacement are reported because of the three iterations cyclic.

For the strengthened samples, an approximate estimation of the equivalent hysteretic damping with varying target displacement was performed (accordingly to the procedure reported in FEMA 440 - [1]), by distinguishing the values of each of the three load iterations (Fig. 3.3.13e). In general, significantly higher input and dissipated cumulative energies resulted from the strengthened samples, in respect to the plain masonry (Table 3.6). The cumulative dissipated energy at near collapse increased by 21-22 times for R2, by 66 times for B2 and by 26 times for B1. At a given target drift, the reduction in ξ_{hys} result greater between the second and third cycles than between the first and second. Approaching the peak load ξ_{hys} was about 0.11 in S-R2R-1 and 0.08 in S-R2R-2; at the near-collapse limit, ξ_{hys} 0.14 and 0.09, respectively. The values of ξ_{hys} at peak load (0.10–0.11) and near collapse (0.13) almost coincided in S-B1R-1 and S-B2R-1.

Table 3.6 Cumulative input energy E_{in} and dissipated hysteresis E_{hys} at peak load (Pk) and at near collapse (Nc), and mean energy ratio in the cycles (E_{hys}/E_{in})

ID	Peak load (Pk)			Near collapse (Nc)		
	E_{in} [J]	E_{hys} [J]	E_{in}/E_{hys} [-]	E_{in} [J]	E_{hys} [J]	E_{in}/E_{hys} [-]
S-R2U-1	119.8	78.6	0.66	1233.0	807.8	0.66
S-R2R-1	18496.4	9462.8	0.51	30045.2	16591.2	0.55
S-R2U-2	34.9	23.5	0.67	831.1	641.1	0.77
S-R2R-2	16100.1	5941.8	0.35	35706.6	14362.3	0.40
S-B2U-1	83.8	48.2	0.58	125.2	77.9	0.62
S-B2R-1	4069.1	1883.4	0.46	9560.2	5109.7	0.53
S-B1U-1	152.3	66.8	0.44	334.6	174.0	0.52
S-B1R-1	3333.4	1757.2	0.53	8006.4	4463.2	0.56

Fig. 3.3.14. Spandrels stiffness and energy characteristics, varying the cycle target distortion d_s .

3.3.2. Analytic model

Symbols:

t	masonry spandrel thickness	σ_{0P}	vertical compressive stress on the piers adjacent to the spandrel
b	masonry spandrel width	f_m	masonry compressive strength (vertical direction)
l	masonry spandrel height (i.e. "effective length")	$f_{m,h}$	masonry compressive strength (horizontal direction)
b_h	average height of a masonry row	τ_0	equivalent masonry shear strength for $\sigma_0 = 0$ (for "Turnšek and Čačovič" formula)
b'	net masonry spandrel height (typically, lintel is not considered)	f_{v0}	masonry shear strength for $\sigma_0 = 0$ (shove test)
ρ	coefficient = $b'/4b_h$	β	spandrel slenderness factor ($1.0 \leq \beta = l/b \leq 1.5$)
d_{eff}	effective overlap length of blocks	χ	effectiveness reduction factor (=1 for CRM at both-sides, ≤ 1 at one side)
E_m	masonry Young's modulus	γ	model coefficient (=2)
G_m	masonry shear modulus ($\sim 1/3E_m$)	A_G	net cross section of a GFRP wire
i	number of CRM-strengthened sides (1-2)	T_G	mean tensile resistance of a GFRP wire
t_c	plaster nominal thickness	s	GFRP mesh grid pitch
E_c	plaster Young's modulus	l_f	CRM effective length ($=l$, but $\leq b$)
G_c	plaster shear modulus ($\sim 0.4E_c$)	$\epsilon_{lim,G}$	limit tensile strain of GFRP
η	coefficient related to the spandrel static scheme (e.g. 3 for cantilever, 12 for shear type)	E_G	GFRP Young's modulus
I	second bending moment of the uncracked spandrel cross section ($tb^3/12$)	α	coefficient of bending moment distribution (e.g. 1 for cantilever, 2 for shear type)
σ_0	mean compressive stress on the spandrel. Max. between horizontal compressive stress (if known) and vertical one (evaluated on the basis of the floor load and the diffusion of vertical stresses in adjacent piers). However, it is typically assumed = 0.	x	depth of the neutral axis of the cracked cross-section

The empirical evidence has shown that the in-plane behavior of unreinforced masonry spandrels without horizontal ties can be schematized analytically, in a simplified way, as an elastic-brittle behaviour with some residual resistance (Fig. 3.2.15a). Differently, when a horizontal tensile-resistant element is provided (e.g. a steel rod, a r.c. ring beam, a metallic profile, the CRM reinforcement, a fiber-based composite strip...) an elastic-plastic behaviour it is more appropriate (Fig. 3.2.15b).

To estimate the stiffness, resistance and ultimate displacement capacities, well-known correlations available in the literature can be considered for the unstrengthened masonry. For CRM strengthened masonry, the correlations need to be adjusted to account for the CRM contribution.

Fig. 3.3.15 Generic, simplified elastic-brittle (a) or elastic-plastic (b) schematization of the in-plane lateral performances of masonry spandrels (red line), in comparison with actual performances (black line).

To evaluate the spandrel stiffness, K_e , both the flexural and shear deformability should be accounted for, as indicated in Eq.(3.11). In case of CRM strengthened masonry, equivalent Young and shear moduli shall be considered, evaluating the average values between masonry and mortar coating, weighted on the respective thickness.

$$K_e = \frac{1}{\frac{l^3}{\eta I E} + \frac{1.2l}{G b t}} \quad (3.11)$$

For the evaluation of the spandrel's in-plane lateral resistance, V_s , the weakest mechanism between shear failure, $V_{s,d}$, and bending, $V_{s,f}$, is considered:

$$V_s = \min(V_{s,d}; V_{s,f}). \quad (3.12)$$

The typical crack patterns that occur during seismic events are illustrated in Fig. 3.3.16. For these mechanisms to activate, the diagonal masonry strut should not prematurely fail in compression:

$$V_s \leq 0.25 \cdot b \cdot t \cdot f_m \quad (3.13)$$

Fig. 3.3.16 Typical in-plane failure mechanism of masonry spandrels: diagonal cracking (a) and bending (b).

For the unstrengthened masonry spandrels (suffix URM), different resistant models can be found in the literature to estimate $V_{S,d(URM)}$. For example, the well-known “Turnšek and Čačovič” correlation, suitable for both regular and irregular masonry, can be applied (according to C8.7.1.16 in MIT 2019 [2]):

$$V_{S,d(URM)} = \frac{1.5\tau_0}{\beta} b' \cdot t \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_0}{1.5\tau_0}} \quad (3.14)$$

Conservatively, the net masonry spandrel height (without lintel) is considered. When failure is dominated by the shear mechanism, a residual resistance, $V'_{S,d(URM)}$, shall be considered. $V'_{S,d(URM)}$ can be estimated proportionally to $V_{S,d(URM)}$ (0.6 for r.c. or steel lintel, 0.4 for timber lintel, 0.1 for masonry arch - [2]).

To estimate the in-plane bending resistance of unreinforced masonry spandrels without an effective horizontal tie (suffix $t0$), Eq. (3.15) can be used with the additional expression for $f_{t,eq}$ (7.3.4 in FEMA 306 [5]), which considers the contribution of block-to-block interaction (cohesion and friction) at the spandrel's ends:

$$V_{S,f(URM,t0)} = \frac{\alpha M_{S(URM,t0)}}{l} = \frac{\alpha}{l} \frac{2}{3} f_{t,eq} \cdot t \cdot b_h \cdot b' \cdot \rho \quad \text{with} \quad (3.15)$$

$$f_{t,eq} = \frac{d^{eff}}{b_h} (f_{V0} + 0.65 \cdot \sigma_{0\rho})$$

When failure is dominated by the bending mechanism, a residual resistance, $V'_{S,f(URM)}$, shall be considered. $V'_{S,f(URM)}$ can be estimated by neglecting the cohesion contribution (i.e. assuming $f_{v0} = 0$ in Eq. (3.15)).

Both mechanisms benefit from the contribution of the CRM system, as the fiber-based composite material (the mesh wires), crossing both the diagonal and the vertical cracks, limits their opening, fostering a wider stress diffusion. However, to be effective against the bending failure, the CRM system has to be sufficiently extended beyond the spandrel area.

In the lack of specific correlations for the evaluation of the resistance of CRM strengthened masonry spandrel (suffix CRM), reference is herein made to CNR-DT 215/2018 [4], an Italian guideline available for FRCM strengthening systems, that have several similarities with CRM ones.

According to [4], the contribution given by the wires along the loading direction crossing the diagonal crack shall be added to that of the unstrengthened masonry:

$$V_{S,d(CRM)} = V_{S,d(URM)} + \chi \frac{1}{\gamma} \cdot i \cdot \frac{A_G}{S} \cdot l_f \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G \cdot (3.16)$$

Note that, if the tensile failure of the fibers is attained, the factor $A_G \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G$ corresponds to the tensile resistance of a single wire, T_G . It is also observed that, coherently with the behavior of the unreinforced masonry spandrel (Fig. 3.3.15a), its residual resistance, $V'_{S,d(URM)}$, should prudentially be considered, instead of the peak one, $V_{S,d(URM)}$.

For the bending failure mechanism of the CRM strengthened masonry spandrel, the tensile-resistant contribution of the horizontal wires crossing the vertical cracks at the end sections shall be accounted:

$$V_{S,f(CRM)} = \frac{\alpha M_{S(CRM)}}{l} = \frac{\alpha}{l} \left[0.8x \cdot f_{m,h} \cdot t \left(\frac{b'}{2} - 0.4x \right) + \chi \frac{i \cdot A_G \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G}{s} \cdot \frac{(b'-x)}{2} \left(\frac{b'}{6} + \frac{x}{3} \right) \right] \quad (3.17)$$

$$\text{with } x = b' \cdot t \left(\sigma_0 + \chi \frac{i A_G \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G}{2s \cdot t} \right) / \left(0.8 \cdot f_{m,h} \cdot t + \chi \frac{i \cdot A_G \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G}{2s} \right).$$

Basically, $M_{S(CRM)}$ shall be evaluated by analysing a reinforced section subjected to combined compression and bending in cracked conditions, assuming conservation of plane sections, perfect bond among materials, masonry cracked in tension (no residual frictional contribution) and plastic in compression, fiber mesh with linear-elastic behaviour in tension until reaching the limit strain. Conservatively, the net masonry spandrel height, b' , is considered; however, in presence of a lintel that effectively indents at the extremities, the gross height, b , can be assumed instead of b' . Note that, for this correlation to provide reliable results, it is necessary to ensure that the masonry does not reach the ultimate compressive strain while the fiber wires are still in the elastic range.

It is observed that the plaster contribution is neglected in both mechanisms. It is also worth noting that the introduction of effective transversal connectors in multiple-leaves masonry could be grossly considered by increasing the masonry shear strength, τ_0 . Appropriate coefficients (range 1.2-1.5, depending on masonry type) are provided in C8.5.II of MIT 2019 [2].

The ultimate displacement capacity of the masonry spandrel, d_{Su} , is evaluated on the basis of the chord rotation limits at the spandrel extremities, θ_{Su} .

For unstrengthened masonry spandrels without effective horizontal tie, the residual resistance for both failure mechanisms, is maintained up to $\theta_{Su(URM,t0)} = 0.015$ (C8.7.1.3.1.1 of MIT 2019 [2]). For CRM masonry, in the lack of any guidance, doubled values could be considered, based on experimental evidence ($\theta_{Su(CRM)} = 0.030$).

3.3.3. Application and validation

The analytical model described in §3.3.2 is adopted to evaluate the lateral performances of the CONSTRAIN experimental tests on the spandrel samples resumed in §3.3.1.

The mechanical characteristics of the unstrengthened masonry (E_m , τ_0 , f_m) considered in the formulations are those already applied for the masonry piers in §3.2.3. The masonry horizontal compressive strength, $f_{m,h}$, is taken as $f_m/2$. The value of f_{v0} for R2 masonry is calculated from the CONSTRAIN experimental test S-R2U (§3.3.1), by solving Eq. (3.15) for f_{v0} (for the resistance $V_{P,d(URM)}$, the peak load is taken and the mean value between positive and negative loading directions is considered). Coherently to the approach already adopted for the piers, for the solid brick samples, the values were taken from Tab.C8.5.I of MIT 2019 [2] (linear interpolation within the provided range, starting from the values of shear strength τ_0).

The main results are summarized in Fig. 3.3.17 and compared graphically with the experimental capacity curves. It is worth to note that, regarding the displacements estimation, the elastic deformability of the lateral masonry piers ($1/K_{add,S}$, quantified analytically of the basis of a cantilever static scheme) is added to that of the spandrel, since the displacement transducers monitoring the spandrel distortion in the experimental tests were actually located at the inner corner of the metallic lever beams at the base.

Main data								
l	[mm]	1050	A_G	[mm ²]	3.8	η	[-]	12
t_c	[mm]	30	T_G	[kN]	5.11	α	[-]	2
E_c	[GPa]	10	s	[mm]	66	σ_{0P}	[MPa]	0.33
G_c	[GPa]	4	l_f	[mm]	1050			

		S-R2U	S-B2U	S-B1U
b	[mm]	1170	1095	1095
d_{eff}	[mm]	80	125	65
b_h	[mm]	111	65	65
b'	[GPa]	1000	845	845
f_{v0}	[MPa]	0.103	0.208	0.248

		S-R2U	S-R2R-1	S-R2R-2
t	[mm]	350	350	350
$f_{m,h}$	[MPa]	1.24	1.24	1.24
τ_o	[MPa]	0.071	0.071	0.071
i	[-]	-	1	2
χ	[-]	-	1.0	1.0
E	[MPa]	1074.2	1931.3	2788.5
G	[MPa]	358.1	700.9	1043.8
K_e	[N/mm]	95097	183181	271117
$K_{add,s}$	[N/mm]	32400	51000	69600
x	[mm]	-	117.4	213.3
M_S	[kNm]	13.3	31.5	56.7
$V_{S,f}$	[kN]	25.4	59.9	108.0 (81.0)*
$V_{S,d}$	[kN]	35.5	52.9	91.6
V_S	[kN]	25.4	52.9	91.6 (81.0)
Mode	[-]	Bending	Shear ^o	Sh. (Bend)
$d_{S,e}$	[mm]	1.05	1.33	1.65 (1.46)
$d_{S,u}$	[mm]	16.5	32.5	32.8 (32.7)

(*) calculated with $\alpha=1.5$, as "in between" the shear-type and the cantilever scheme, to account grossly for the anomaly in the vertical loading system, as evidenced in §3.3.1.

(^o) since $V_{S,f}$ and $V_{S,d}$ are vely close, a combined shear/bending failure is expected.

		S-B2U	S-B2R-1
t	[mm]	250	250
$f_{m,h}$	[MPa]	1.49	1.49
τ_o	[MPa]	0.068	0.068x1.3*
i	[-]	-	1
χ	[-]	-	1.0
E	[MPa]	1335.7	2535.7
G	[MPa]	445.2	925.2
K_e	[N/mm]	77051	157094
$K_{add,s}$	[N/mm]	20500	39100
x	[mm]	-	97.0
M_S	[kNm]	24.2	16.1
$V_{S,f}$	[kN]	46.0	30.7
$V_{S,d}$	[kN]	17.4	35.0
V_S	[kN]	17.4	30.7
Mode	[-]	Shear	Bending ^o
$d_{S,e}$	[mm]	1.07	0.98
$d_{S,u}$	[mm]	16.6	32.3

(*) 1.3 is the amplification factor of the shear strength in multiple-leaves roughly-cut stone solid brick masonry, to account for the benefits of effective transversal connectors.

(^o) since $V_{S,f}$ and $V_{S,d}$ are vely close, a combined shear/bending failure is expected.

		S-B1U	S-B1R-1
t	[mm]	250	250
$f_{m,h}$	[MPa]	1.92	1.92
τ_o	[MPa]	0.108	0.108
i	[-]	-	1
χ	[-]	-	1.0
E	[MPa]	1638.6	2838.6
G	[MPa]	546.2	1026.2
K_e	[N/mm]	94523	174588
$K_{add,S}$	[N/mm]	25400	43700
x	[mm]	-	77.3
M_s	[kNm]	13.8	16.6
$V_{s,f}$	[kN]	26.2	31.6
$V_{s,d}$	[kN]	27.7	35.5
V_s	[kN]	26.2	31.6
Mode	[-]	Bending°	Bending°
$d_{s,e}$	[mm]	1.31	0.90
$d_{s,u}$	[mm]	16.8	32.2

(°) since $V_{s,f}$ and $V_{s,d}$ are very close, a combined shear/bending failure is expected.

Fig. 3.3.17 Analytic results concerning the masonry spandrel samples and comparison with the experimental behaviour.

3.4. Out-of-plane behaviour

3.4.1. Summary and analysis of the experimental results

The samples of the out-of-plane tests consisted in rectangular masonry panels having a width of 1030 mm and a height of 2480 mm (Fig. 3.4.1). Each specimen was built between a bottom and a top reinforced concrete (RC) beam 250 mm height, 1030 mm long and with a thickness equal to that of the plain masonry. A total of three panels were built and tested (Table 3.7), one for each masonry type: R2, B2 and B1 (Appendix A.). The samples were strengthened with the CRM system applied at one side only. The positioning of the GFRP connectors and of GFRP connectors combined with artificial diatones is schematized in Fig. 3.4.2.

Fig. 3.4.1 Main geometric characteristics of the samples.

Table 3.7: Summary of the CONSTRAIN experimental out-of-plane tests

Sample ID	Masonry type	Strengthening system	Connectors
B-R2	R2	CRM on one-side	GFRP + diatons, 1 side
B-B2	B2	CRM on one-side	GFRP + diatons, 1 side
B-B1	B2	CRM on one-side	GFRP, 1 side

Fig. 3.4.2 Positioning of the connectors in CRM strengthened samples.

The test setup, schematized in Fig. 3.4.3, was a vertical three-point bending test with the samples hinged at the top and bottom. The apparatus was composed of a steel truss reaction frame, four restraining bars, a trolley for the load distribution system and a hydraulic actuator. A smooth horizontal steel bar running through each RC beam allowed to connect to the reaction frame to the wall, by means of the restraining bars provided with knuckle joints. All the samples were arranged so that the CRM-strengthened side was that on the front side. During testing, the actuator, positioned horizontally at the mid-height of the samples, at the rear side, moved a loading trolley to apply the out-of-plane loading cycles at increasing displacements, acting in the positive (pushing from the rear to the front side) and negative (pulling from the front to the rear side) directions and gradually increasing the target amplitude. Each load amplitude was repeated only once before it was increased. When a net deflection equal to 1/100 of the sample height was reached, the test was prosecuted by pushing monotonically.

When pushed, the coating was in tension, simulating the strengthened wall response; when pulled, the coating was in compression, which simulated the unreinforced wall response.

Each specimen was equipped with 13 displacement transducers and two load cells. The displacement transducers were used to measure out-of-plane displacements at the top, middle and bottom of the sample, and rotations of the top and bottom RC elements. Two transducers were placed at the sides of the walls to measure vertical deformations at the mid-height of the pier. The load cells measured the force acting on the wall.

Fig. 3.4.3 Schematization of the test setup for out-of-plane tests.

The behaviour of each sample is described in the following, reporting also monitored loads and displacements and evolution of the crack pattern (surveyed at the front side by means of a Digital Image Correlation system). The main results are then summarized and compared.

The global behaviour of the samples is described in terms of capacity curves, representing the applied horizontal load F_B varying the net horizontal deflection d_B , at the mid-height of the sample.

- Test B-R2 (Fig. 3.4.4)

The first crack occurred at first on the unreinforced side, when pulling, near the mid-height; then also on the strengthened side, when pushing. As the displacement amplitudes increased, the crack pattern on the unstrengthened side remained the same as the single crack opened increasingly more. On the other side, several new horizontal cracks opened on the strengthened side, involving an increasingly wider sample portion. The cracks in the coating multiplied and spread over almost 2/3 of the pier height. The final collapse was due to the tensile failure of the GFRP vertical wires crossing a crack around the mid-span.

Fig. 3.4.4 Main results of test B-R2.

- Test B-B2 (Fig. 3.4.5)

A single horizontal crack occurred on the unreinforced side, in the middle section, which then gradually opened during the pulling stages. On the coated side, the first crack appeared next to the mid-height and had a sub-vertical trend. As the pushing load increased, new cracks appeared in the coating. All cracks in the coating were primarily horizontal. The cracks originated from the midsection and gradually spread toward the top and bottom of the pier, involving more than 2/3 of the height. At collapse, the GFRP vertical wires in the coating fractured around the mid-span.

Fig. 3.4.5 Main results of test B-B2.

- Test B-B1 (Fig. 3.4.7)

The first crack appeared when pulling and was horizontal in the mid-height bed joint of the unreinforced side; a second horizontal crack formed slightly upper when the deflection was increased. On the coated side, the first horizontal crack appeared at mid-height. As the pushing load increased, new cracks appeared in the coating. All cracks in the coating were primarily horizontal. The cracks originated from the midsection and gradually spread toward the top and bottom of the pier, involving almost 2/3 of the height. At collapse, the GFRP vertical wires in the coating fractured at the mid-span.

Fig. 3.4.6 Main results of test B-B1.

The values of F_B and d_B obtained from the three experimental tests are summarized in Fig. 3.4.7 and Table 3.8, for first cracking and ultimate load (Cr , UI). When pushing, the ultimate load is taken in correspondance of the peak load; when pulling, the value correspondant to a net deflection equal to 1/150 the height is assumed.

It is observed that the comparison between the sample performances in pushing and pulling directions almost provided a comparison between CRM-strengthened and unstrengthened masonry. In fact, the contribution of CRM in compression is almost negligible (except for the small additional thickness, due to the mortar).

Table 3.8 Values of the out-of-plane horizontal load (F_B) and net deflection (d_B) measured in positive and negative loading directions, for the first cracking and ultimate load.

ID	Side in tension	First cracking (Cr)		Ultimate load (UI)	
		F_B [kN]	d_B [mm]	F_B [kN]	d_B [mm]
B-R2	URM	-6.49	-2.81	-5.15	-16.7
	CRM	20.4	3.28	52.0	59.6
B-B2	URM	-3.42	-3.15	-3.43	-16.7
	CRM	8.83	2.25	29.0	44.5
B-B1	URM	-3.37	-3.1	-3.32	-16.7
	CRM	9.80	1.90	35.1	58.6

Fig. 3.4.7. Main results of out-of-plane tests: first cracking, peak and near collapse forces (a) and net deflections (b).

In general, on the unstrengthened side, the failure mechanism was characterized by the opening of one or two nearly horizontal cracks in masonry bed joints. Differently, on the strengthened side, many cracks in the coating widely spread from the central section: the CRM and the masonry performed as a composite element.; when the collapse occurred, the vertical GFRP wires fractured due to tension, indicating it was exploited at its maximum.

Significant improvements were attained in terms of resistance (ratio between ultimate forces): 10.1 in B-R2, 8.5 in B-B2 and 10.6 in B-B1. The failure on the fibres occurred at 45.8 times the span in B-R2, 61.4 in B-B2 and 46.6 in B-B1.

3.4.2. Analytic model

Symbols:

t	masonry wall thickness	A_G	net cross section of a GFRP wire
b	masonry wall width	T_G	mean tensile resistance of a GFRP wire
l	masonry wall height	s	GFRP mesh grid pitch
E_m	masonry Young's modulus	$\varepsilon_{lim,G}$	limit tensile strain of GFRP
G_m	masonry shear modulus ($\sim 1/3E_m$)	E_G	GFRP Young's modulus
t_c	plaster nominal thickness	n_G	number of GFRP wires subjected to tension = $1+int(b/s)$
E_c	plaster Young's modulus	c	covering of GFRP mesh (typically, = $t_c/2$)
G_c	plaster shear modulus ($\sim 0.4E_c$)	f_m	masonry compressive strength
η	coefficient related to the wall static scheme (e.g. 48 for three-point bending)	$f_{c,f}$	plaster flexural strength
I	second bending moment of the uncracked cross section ($bt^3/12$)	α	coefficient of bending moment distribution (e.g. = 4 for three-point bending)
σ_0	mean vertical compressive stress on the wall	α_e	plaster/masonry modular ratio = E_c/E_m
f_{v0}	masonry shear strength for $\sigma_0 = 0$ (shove test)	x	depth of the neutral axis of the cracked cross-section

To schematize analytically, in a simplified way, the out-of-plane lateral performances of masonry piers:

- an elastic-plastic behaviour with linear softening can be considered when the unstrengthened masonry is on the tensed side (Fig. 3.4.8a);
- an elastic-plastic behaviour with linear hardening can be considered when the CRM layer is on the tensed e (Fig. 3.4.8b).

To estimate the stiffness, resistance and ultimate displacement capacities, well-known correlations available in the literature can be considered for the unstrengthened masonry side. For CRM strengthened masonry side, the correlations need to be adjusted, so to account for the CRM contribution.

Fig. 3.4.8 Generic, simplified elastic-brittle (a) or elastic-plastic (b) schematization of the out-of-plane performances of masonry walls (red line), in comparison with actual performances (black line).

To evaluate the pier stiffness, K_e , just the flexural deformability can be accounted, as indicated in Eq. (3.18), where a three point bending static scheme is considered. In case of CRM strengthened masonry, equivalent Young modulus shall be considered, evaluating the average values between masonry and mortar coating, weighted on the respective thickness.

$$K_e = \frac{\eta I E}{l^3}. \quad (3.18)$$

Typically, during seismic events, masonry panels subjected to out-of-plane seismic actions exhibit maximum bending moment at the centre of the panel and negligible stresses at the edges (Fig. 3.4.9). Such mechanism is likely to activate in masonry types not prone to disaggregation or leaves-separation phenomena.

Fig. 3.4.9 Typical out-of-plane failure mechanism of masonry walls.

The wall out-of-plane resistance related to bending, F_B , when the unstrengthened masonry is on the tensed side (suffix U) is mainly due to the masonry compressive resistance and the stabilizing effect of the vertical loads (7.8.2.2.3 in MIT 2018 [3]):

$$F_{B,f(U)} = \frac{\alpha M_{B(U)}}{l} = \frac{\alpha}{l} \frac{\sigma_o b t^2}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_o}{0.85 f_m} \right). \quad (3.19)$$

For this mechanism to activate, the masonry should not prematurely fail in shear in the cracked sections:

$$F_{B,f} \leq f_v \cdot b \cdot x. \quad \text{with } f_v = f_{v0} + 0.4 \cdot \sigma_0, \quad (3.20)$$

where f_{v0} shall be taken equal to zero, due to cyclic action.

When the CRM layer is on the tension side, the fibre-based composite material (the mesh wires) crossing the cracks, limits their opening, fostering a wider stress diffusion. In the lack of specific guidelines for the evaluation of the resistance of CRM strengthened masonry pier (suffix R), reference is herein made to CNR-DT 215/2018 [4], an Italian guideline available for FRCM strengthening systems, that have several similarities with CRM ones:

$$F_{B,u(R)} = \frac{\alpha M_{B,u(R)}}{l} = \frac{\alpha}{l} \left[0.8x \cdot f_m \cdot b \cdot (y_G - 0.4x) + n_G \cdot A_G \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G \cdot (t + t_c - c - y_G) \right], \quad (3.21)$$

$$\text{with } x = (\sigma_0 \cdot b \cdot t + n_G \cdot A_G \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G) / (0.8 \cdot f_m \cdot b)$$

$$\text{and } y_G = \left[\frac{b}{2} (t + t_c)^2 + n_G \cdot A_G \cdot (t + t_c - c) \right] / [b \cdot (t + t_c) + n_G \cdot A_G].$$

Basically, $M_{B,u(R)}$ shall be evaluated by analysing a reinforced section subjected to combined compression and bending in cracked conditions, assuming conservation of plane sections, perfect bond among materials, masonry and plaster cracked in tension and plastic in compression, fiber mesh with linear-elastic behaviour in tension until reaching the limit strain. Note that, if the tensile failure of the fibres is attained, the factor $A_G \cdot \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G$ corresponds to the tensile resistance of a single wire, T_G .

The conventional elastic limit force of the bi-linear curve (Fig. 3.4.8b), $F_{B,e(R)}$, can be calculated from the bending moment related to first cracking, $M_{B,e(R)}$:

$$F_{B,e(R)} = \frac{\alpha M_{B,e(R)}}{l} = \frac{\alpha}{l} \left[\frac{b \cdot (t + t_c)^2}{6} \cdot \left(\sigma_0 + \frac{f_{c,f}}{\alpha_e} \right) \right]. \quad (3.22)$$

According to C8.7.1.2.1.6 of MIT 2019 [2], the ultimate out-of-plane deflection of the unstrengthened wall, $d_{Bu(U)}$, corresponds to 60% the displacement for which $F_{B(U)} = 0$ ($d_{B0(U)}$), that is evaluated on the basis of equilibrium analysis of rigid blocks.

For CRM masonry, the ultimate deflection $d_{Bu(R)}$ corresponds to the attainment of the limit strain in tensed GFRP wires. As first attempt, based on experimental evidences, it is taken as $l/50$.

3.4.3. Application and validation

The analytical model described in §3.4.2 is adopted to evaluate the lateral performances of the CONSTRAIN experimental out-of-plane bending tests resumed in §3.4.1.

The mechanical characteristics of the unstrengthened masonry considered in the formulations are those already applied for the masonry piers and spandrels in §3.2.3 and §3.3.3.

To evaluate $d_{B0(U)}$, the contribution of the sample only was considered, as first attempt, thus $d_{B0(U)} = t/3$.

The main results are summarized in Fig. 3.4.10 and compared graphically with the experimental capacity curves.

Main data								
b	[mm]	1030	n_G	[-]	16	η	[-]	48
l	[mm]	2730	A_G	[mm ²]	3.8	α	[-]	4
t_c	[mm]	30	T_G	[kN]	5.11	α_e	[-]	8
E_c	[GPa]	10	s	[mm]	66	f_{cf}	[MPa]	3.0

		B-R2	B-B2	B-B1
t	[mm]	350	250	250
f_m	[MPa]	2.48	2.98	3.84
E_m	[MPa]	1074.2	1335.7	1638.6
E	[MPa]	1931.3	2535.7	2838.6
σ_0	[MPa]	0.034	0.032	0.032
K_e	[N/mm]	21459	11271	12618
y_G	[mm]	~190	~140	~140
$M_{B(U)}$	[kNm]	2.5	1.3	1.3
$M'_{B(U)}$	[kNm]*	3.5	2.3	2.3
$F_{B,f(U)}$	[kN]	5.2	3.3	3.3
$d_{B,e(U)}$	[mm]	0.24	0.30	0.26
$d_{B,e(U)}$	[mm]	70.0	50.0	50.0
$x_{(C)}$	[mm]	46.6	37.0	28.7
$M_{B(C)}$	[kN]	30.6	21.6	21.9
$M'_{B(C)}$	[kN]*	31.6	22.6	22.9
$F_{B,f(C)}$	[kN]	46.3	33.1	33.6
$M_{B,e(C)}$	[kN]	8.84	4.02	4.84
$M'_{B,e(C)}$	[kN]*	9.84	5.02	5.84
$F_{B,e(C)}$	[kN]	14.4	7.4	8.6
$d_{B,e(C)}$	[mm]	0.67	0.65	0.68
$d_{B,u(C)}$	[mm]	54.6	54.6	54.6

(*) evaluated by adding to M_B the additional contribution due to the friction of the testing apparatus (approximately 1 kNm)

Fig. 3.4.10 Analytic results concerning the out-of-plane tests and comparison with the experimental behaviour.

4. Roof ring beams with FRP meshes embedded in bed joints

4.1. Technique characteristics

The technique can be generally adopted for the reconstruction of the roof masonry ring beams by embedding FRP pre-formed meshes in the bed joints (Fig. 4.1.1), so to improve the out-of-plane response of the walls and foster the global, box-like behaviour of the masonry structure, contrasting overturning phenomena. It is observed that the intervention is also capable of improving the in-plane performances of the upper masonry spandrels.

In particular, Glass fibres meshes are herein considered (GFRP). The main characteristics for the components materials adopted in the "CONSTRAIN" tests are resumed in Appendix A.

Fig. 4.1.1 Reconstruction of the roof masonry ring beams FRP meshes embedded in bed joints

4.2. Out-of-plane behaviour

4.2.1. *Summary and analysis of the experimental results*

The masonry ring beam samples with GFRP meshes embedded in the bed joints ("T") were 3500 mm long. The first sample was made of 350 mm-thick double-leaf rubble stone masonry ("T-R2"), which was 660 mm tall and had four reinforced bed joints (Fig. 4.2.1a). The other sample was made of 250 mm-thick single-leaf solid clay brick masonry ("T-B1") that was 465 mm tall, with six reinforced bed joints (Fig. 4.2.1b).

Fig. 4.2.1 Main geometric characteristics of the roof ring beam masonry samples: (a) T-R2 and (b) T-B1.

The setup was composed of the horizontal sliding system (supporting the sample vertically), the horizontal restraining system, and the loading system. The sliding system consisted of a smooth, flat surface covered with two plastic sheets with grease in between. The restraining system comprised four stiff steel columns connected to the laboratory basement (two at each side), which was connected to the sample with hinged rods that provided support against out-of-plane horizontal sliding, but allowed rotations. The net span between the supports was 3000 mm. The loading system was a horizontal actuator located at the midspan of the sample and connected on one side to a concrete ballast and on the other to a steel frame on a trolley. The load was applied cyclically, alternatively pulling (negative loading) and pushing (positive loading), gradually increasing the amplitude of the deflection.

Fig. 4.2.2. Experimental setup for "T" samples.

The main results are summarized in the following, reporting also monitored loads and displacements and evolution of the crack pattern (visual surveyed during the test).

The global behaviour of the samples is described in terms of capacity curves, representing the out-of-plane horizontal load, F_T , varying the net horizontal deflection at the midspan, d_T .

- Test T-R2 (Fig. 4.2.3)

A first pair of central cracks opened on the rear face, when pulling, and just after of the front face, inversing the load direction. The cracks followed an almost vertical trend along the mortar joints. With increasing load, the deflection increased, and new sub-vertical cracks formed. The cracks progressively formed alternately at front and back, according to the loading direction. When the number of cracks stabilized, a gradual and significant widening of the central cracks emerged at increasing deflection. The collapse was due to the fracture of the GFRP longitudinal wires near the back side, when pulling, and then near the front side, when pushing. The behaviour was almost symmetric in the two directions.

Fig. 4.2.3 Main results of test T-R2.

- Test T-B1 (Fig. 4.2.4)

A first pair of cracks formed in the vicinity of the midspan, when pushing. The cracks were vertical but followed the joints at the front side. As the load direction was inverted, the cracks on the front side closed, and the cracks on the back side opened. With increasing load, the new sub-vertical cracks (following the joints) developed almost throughout the whole sample height, gradually covering an increasingly wider portion of the sample. Once the formation of most of the cracks was completed, the existing cracks widened with the deflection increase. Near the ultimate state, a continuous horizontal discontinuity at the upper bed joint caused a gradual separation of the last brick row from the lower part of the sample on the left side; thus, the last layer of reinforcement mesh lost part of its effectiveness. At the test prosecuted, some longitudinal GFRP wires on the rear face fractured at the mid-span; similarly, at the opposite loading direction, the GFRP wires on the front face fractured at the mid-span. The behaviour was quite asymmetric in the two loading directions (the hardening was stiffer in pulling).

Fig. 4.2.4 Main results of test T-B1.

Generally, the first cracks in the masonry formed on the tensed side, in the vicinity of the midspan. As the load direction was inversed, the cracks on one side closed, and the cracks on the other side opened. With increasing load, new sub-vertical cracks developed on the tensed side, almost throughout the whole sample height, gradually covering an increasingly wider portion of the sample (of a width of about 1800 mm). Moreover, as the deflection increased, the existing cracks widened. Both sample attained to peak load just before some longitudinal GFRP wires fractured on the tensed side, at the mid-span; then the load rapidly dropped down. The backbone of the load-deflection F_T-d_T curves assumed a roughly tri-linear trend: the first elastic part with an initial stiffness, a second plastic part with hardening, and a third part with near-zero stiffness.

The main results of the two tests in terms of load and deflection at first cracking (Cr) and at collapse (UI) are summarized in Table 4.1 and Fig. 4.2.5. For sample T-R2, the resistance of almost 18.3 kN at about 1/44 of the net span for both directions. Sample T-B1 reached 12.4 kN and 9.0 kN in pulling and pushing, respectively; the difference was likely influenced by the detachment of the upper rows mentioned before. However, the ultimate deflections were similar (about 1/29 the net span).

Table 4.1. Main results of tests on masonry ring beams with FRP meshes embedded in bed joints, in terms of load and deflection at first cracking (Cr) and at collapse (UI).

Sample	Load direction	First cracking (Cr)		Ultimate load (UI)	
		F_T [kN]	d_T [mm]	F_T [kN]	d_T [mm]
T-R2	Pull (-)	-2.3	-1.0	-18.0	-68.8
	Push (+)	+5.2	+0.8	+18.6	+69.0
T-B1	Pull (-)	-3.1	-2.7	-12.4	-105.1
	Push (+)	+2.6	+2.3	+9.0	+101.9

Fig. 4.2.5 Main test results of "T" samples: first cracking and ultimate force (a) and deflection (b) values

The cyclic tests allow also to draw the trends of the cycle stiffness, K_T (evaluated as the slope of the peak-to-peak line within each loop of the F_T-d_T curve) by varying the net deflection d_T (Fig. 4.2.6a). The stiffness degradation with increasing deflection shows an approximately power-law trend; at the end of the tests, the cycle stiffness was less than 10% the initial value.

The cumulative input energy (E_{in}) and the dissipated hysteretic energy (E_{hys}) were quantified (Fig. 4.2.6b), as well as the E_{hys}/E_{in} ratios (Fig. 4.2.6c). E_{in} is the cumulative work to deform the sample from the beginning of the test to a specific target value of deflection. For each loading cycle, it corresponds to the area under the positive and negative branches of the hysteretic loop of the F_T-d_T graph. Similarly, the cumulative dissipated hysteretic energy E_{hys} is the sum of all the areas included in the hysteretic loops. Moreover, an approximate estimation of the equivalent hysteretic damping with varying target displacement was performed (Fig. 4.2.6d).

In respect to the first cracking condition, the cumulative dissipated energy at collapse resulted more than 500 times greater in both cases. The damping ratio, ξ_{hys} , decreased as the deflection progressed and resulted about 11-12% at collapse.

Fig. 4.2.6. Roof ring beam stiffness and energy characteristics, varying the cycle target deflection d_T .

4.2.2. Analytic model

Symbols:

t	masonry beam thickness	E_G	GFRP Young's modulus
b	masonry beam height	n_G	total number of GFRP wire levels in a single bedjoint
l	Masonry beam span	n'_G	number of GFRP wire levels in tension in a single bedjoint
E_m	masonry Young's modulus	c	covering (distance between the outer GFRP wires and the tensed edge of the cross section)
η	coefficient related to the beam static scheme (e.g. =48 for 3 point bending)	$f_{m,f}$	masonry flexural strength (horizontal mending)
I	second bending moment of the uncracked beam cross section ($tb^3/12$)	α	coefficient of bending moment distribution (e.g.=4 for 3 point bending)
A_G	net cross section of a GFRP wire	α_G	GFRP/masonry modular ratio = E_G / E_m
n_B	number of bed joints with GFRP embedded		
T_G	mean tensile resistance of a GFRP wire		
s	GFRP grid pitch		
$\varepsilon_{lim,G}$	limit tensile strain of GFRP		

To schematize analytically, in a simplified way, the out-of-plane lateral performances of masonry beams with GFRP mesh embedded in the bed joints a tri-linear behaviour with final plastic stage can be considered (Fig. 3.4.8).

Fig. 4.2.7 Generic, simplified tri-linear schematization of the out-of-plane performances of masonry beams with GFRP meshes embedded in the bed joints (red line), in comparison with actual performances (black line).

To evaluate the beam stiffness, K_e , just the flexural deformability of the masonry can be accounted, as indicated in Eq. (4.1):

$$K_e = \frac{\eta I E_m}{l^3} \quad (4.1)$$

Typically, during seismic events, masonry roof ring beams subjected to out-of-plane seismic actions exhibit maximum bending moment at the centre of the span. Such mechanism is likely to activate in masonry types not prone to disaggregation or leaves-separation phenomena.

Fig. 4.2.8 Typical out-of-plane failure mechanism of masonry ring beams.

In masonry beams with GFRP meshes embedded in the bed joints, the out-of-plane resistance, $F_{T,u(R)}$, shall be evaluated by analysing a reinforced section subjected to bending in cracked conditions, assuming conservation of plane sections, perfect bond among materials, masonry cracked in tension and plastic in compression, fiber mesh with linear-elastic behaviour in tension until reaching the limit strain.

$$F_{T,u(R)} = \frac{\alpha M_{Tu(R)}}{l} = \frac{\alpha \varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G \cdot I_{id}}{l \alpha_G (t - c - x_{id})} \quad (4.2)$$

$$\text{with } x_{id} = \frac{\alpha_G \cdot n_B A_G \cdot n'_G}{b} \left(-1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{2b \cdot (t - c) - b s \cdot (n'_G - 1)}{\alpha_G \cdot n_B A_G \cdot n'_G}} \right) \text{ and}$$

$$I_{id} = \frac{b \cdot x_{id}^3}{3} + \alpha_G \cdot n_B A_G \cdot n'_G (t - c - x_{id})^2 - \alpha_G \cdot n_B A_G \cdot s (t - c - x_{id}) (n'_G - 1) n'_G + \alpha_G \cdot n_B A_G \cdot s^2 (2n'_G - 1)(n'_G - 1) n'_G / 6$$

Since n'_G is unknown, a first attempt value corresponding to the total number of wire levels n_G can be set, and equilibrium calculated. If the calculated neutral axis, x_{id} , is compatible with the assumption, the result is correct; otherwise, the procedure continues iteratively by reducing n'_G until a good solution is found.

Note that, if the tensile failure of the fibres is attained, the factor $\varepsilon_{lim,G} \cdot E_G$ corresponds to the tensile strength of the wires, T_G/A_G .

The conventional elastic limit force of the bi-linear curve (Fig. 3.4.8), $F_{T,e(R)}$, can be calculated from the bending moment related to the masonry first cracking, $M_{T,e(R)}$:

$$F_{T,e(R)} = \frac{\alpha M_{T,e(R)}}{l} = \frac{\alpha b \cdot t^2}{l \cdot 6} \cdot f_{m,f} \quad (4.3)$$

Note that the contribution of the reinforcement is neglected. This is likely the resistance of the unstrengthened masonry beam.

For GFRP reinforced masonry, the deflection d_y , based on the experimental evidences, it is taken as $5 \cdot l/t$, and $d_u = 1.5 \cdot d_y$.

Fig. 4.2.9 "T" samples: (a) static scheme assumed for the evaluation of the ultimate and first cracking load and (b) schematisation of the reinforced masonry cross-section.

4.2.3. Application and validation

The analytical model described in §4.2.2 is adopted to evaluate the lateral performances of the CONSTRAIN experimental out-of-plane bending tests of masonry ring beams resumed in §4.2.1. The mechanical characteristics of masonry and GFRP wire considered in the formulations are those already applied in §3.2.3, §3.3.3 and §3.4.3. The values of $f_{m,f}$ are calculated from the average first cracking load measured in the CONSTRAIN experimental tests on the ring beams, solving Eq. (4.3) for $f_{m,f}$.

The main results are summarized in Fig. 4.2.10 and compared graphically with the experimental capacity curves.

Main data				
l	[mm]	3000	E_G	[MPa] 72816
η	[-]	48	T_G	[kN] 5.11
α	[-]	4	A_G	[mm ²] 3.8
			s	[mm] 66

		T-R2	T-B1
t	[mm]	350	250
b	[mm]	660	465
E_m	[MPa]	1074.2	1638.6
$f_{m,f}$	[MPa]	0.235	0.442
n_b	[-]	4	6 (5*)
n_G	[-]	5	4
n'_G	[-]	4	3
c	[mm]	43	26
K_e	[N/mm]	4503	1764
$M_{T,e}$	[kNm]	3.17	2.14
I_{id}		1.52.E+8	4.5(3.84*) E+7
x_{id}	[mm]	45.1	33.7 (31.3*)
$M_{T,u(R)}$	[kN]	11.5	10.2 (8.6*)
$F_{T,e}$	[kN]	4.22	2.85
$F_{T,u(R)}$	[kN]	15.4	13.6 (11.5*)
$d_{T,e(R)}$	[mm]	0.94	1.62
$d_{T,y(R)}$	[mm]	42.9	60.0
$d_{T,u(R)}$	[mm]	64.3	90.0

* Assuming the ineffectiveness of the GFRP mesh in the upper bedjoint

Fig. 4.2.10 Analytic results concerning the out-of-plane tests and comparison with the experimental behaviour.

5. Ring beams with externally-bonded FRP strips

5.1. Technique characteristics

The technique can be generally adopted to improve the out-of-plane response of masonry walls and foster the global, box-like behaviour of the masonry structure. It consists of bonding Fibre-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) strips onto the outer surface of the masonry ring beams in a building (Fig. 5.1.1). Being an eccentric system (since FRP is on only one side), the continuity of the strip around the corner is crucial.

It is observed that the intervention is also capable of improving the in-plane performances of the masonry spandrels, since a horizontal tensile-resistant element is introduced.

In particular, unidirectional Carbon fibres strips are herein considered (CFRP). To apply the strips, the masonry surface was first levelled by applying a flat and smooth layer of a rapid-setting, thixotropic cementitious grout. Then, a first layer of epoxy resin was spread and the strip was applied; on top of the strip, a new layer of epoxy resin was spread. The main characteristics for the component materials adopted in the "CONSTRAIN" tests are resumed in Appendix A.

Fig. 5.1.1 CFRP strip externally bonded on a masonry ring beam.

5.2. Out-of-plane behaviour

5.2.1. Summary and analysis of the experimental results

The samples for testing the masonry ring beams with externally bonded FRP strips were C-shaped masonry samples ("C") and had nominal dimensions of $3650 \times 1035 \text{ mm}^2$ ($l \times b$ = central span \times side, measured along the axes) and height $h = 1000 \text{ mm}$. The first sample ("C-R2") was made of 350 mm-thick double-leaf rubble stone masonry and the other ("C-B1") of 250 mm-thick single-leaf solid clay brick masonry. A 200 mm-wide CFRP strip was bonded externally to each sample at mid-height around the outer perimeter, rounding the corners with a bend radius of 20 mm. In the double-leaf rubble stone sample, transversal connectors (i.e. "artificial diatones", as those described in section 3) were added to prevent leaves separation in the masonry.

Fig. 5.2.1 Main geometric characteristics of the C-shape masonry samples: (a) C-R2 and (b) C-B1.

The test setup for the "C" samples is schematized in Fig. 5.2.2. Each sample laid on six trolleys, which moved on the smooth horizontal surface with minimal friction. The out-of-plane horizontal cyclic loading was applied at the midspan using a hydraulic jack. The ends of the sample wings were clamped to a reaction wall (fixed concrete ballast) via supports capable to prevented rotation about vertical axis but to allow lateral movement. The CFRP strips were anchored into the supports (by clamping), thus fixing the axial movement of the sample (in the direction of the loading) when the actuator was pushing. In the case when the actuator was pulling the sample, the wings pressed against a vertical steel beam.

The load was applied cyclically, alternatively pushing (positive loading) and pulling (negative loading), gradually increasing the amplitude of the deflection. When the CFRP strip at the midspan failed during pushing, the test was stopped, and the reinforcement continuity was restored just to prevent the separation of the two wall portions (no other influence on negative loading). Then, the test was restarted by pulling monotonically to induce the failure of the CFRP strip at the corners.

Fig. 5.2.2 Experimental setup for "C" samples. The instrumentation is shown in the plan view.

The main results are summarized in the following. The global behaviour of the samples is described in terms of capacity curves, representing the out-of-plane horizontal load, F_C , varying the net horizontal deflection at the midspan, d_C .

Besides the deflection, the relative opening of the midspan crack (inner side, w_i , and external side, w_e) was monitored. Horizontal displacements at the wing extremities were also surveyed (left wing, h_L , and right one, h_R). In addition, pairs of displacement transducers were installed on the outer side of the wall, near the corners, enabling the survey of the corner rotations θ .

- Test C-R2 (Fig. 5.2.3)

The first sub-vertical cracks occurred at midspan and located at the outer side, when pushing, while at the inner side, when pulling, once the flexural tensile strength of the masonry parallel to the bed joint was attained. In the former case, the load did not drop, owing to the CFRP strip; conversely, in the latter, it dropped down and later increased again. The stiffness reduction was significant in both cases but more pronounced when pulling. The progressive deflection in the pushing direction led to the onset of CFRP debonding at the midspan and to the opening of other nearly vertical cracks on the outer masonry surface (about 500 mm from the midspan). Finally, the tensile fracture failure of the CFRP strip in the vicinity of the midspan occurred. Looking the fractured reinforcement, it is observed that some local delamination of occurred just around the crack: it involved both the GFRP-grout and the grout-masonry interfaces.

The test then proceeded monotonically in the pulling direction and induced the anticipated fracturing of impregnated fibers at the right clamp. This was likely caused by local stress concentration in the fibers due to rotation of the clamped supports, which might have aggravated the local weakening of the fibers. The fracturing caused a partial load decrease. Then, as the load was further increased, the cracking of the masonry close to the left corner and the tensile failure of the CFRP strip at the fold at the left corner, also accompanied by diffuse debonding, were attained. Actually the extensive debonding phenomena at the corner was observed concurrently with the failure of the strip; it involved mainly the masonry-levelling grout interface, while the grout-CFRP bond remained effective.

Consistently with the crack pattern, the crack opening at midspan resulted higher for pulling than pushing. The inward horizontal translations at supports when pushing were slightly higher at the left side in positive load direction, and the opposite was observed when pulling. However, the corner rotations were almost symmetric.

Fig. 5.2.3 Main results of test C-R2.

- Test C-B1 (Fig. 5.2.4)

The first crack, almost vertical, appeared in the masonry at the mid-span, on the outer side, for the attainment of the flexural tensile strength of the solid clay masonry parallel to the bed joint, when pushing. However, no significant load decrease occurred with the crack opening (just a slight stiffness degradation) because of the presence of the CFRP reinforcement. In contrast, the opening of a midspan vertical crack on the inner side, when pulling, induced a rapid load decrease. Afterwards, the load was gradually recovered in subsequent cycles but with a significant stiffness reduction. As the cyclic test progressed, the midspan crack alternatively opened on the outer side when pushing and on the inner side when pulling. As the deflection increased, a slight CFRP debonding was observed around the outer crack (masonry-grout interface), and new sub-vertical cracks opened at about 250–300 mm from the midspan section, as a consequence of the stress distribution effect of the CFRP strip). Because of this cracks, the stiffness reduced further. Some debonding also occurred near the right clamp, but the strip remained effective in carrying the tensile strength. The failure of the CFRP strip (tensile fracture of the fibres) occurred abruptly at the midspan with significant values of deflection. When loading monotonically in the opposite direction (pulling), the masonry began cracking in the vicinity of the corners and some diagonal and horizontal cracks appeared in the central part of the sample. The collapse occurred for the tensile failure of the CFRP strip at the left corner and, then, at the right side, near the corner bend. Some CFRP debonding was also observed in these sections, just before the failure.

The trend of the horizontal displacements at the wing extremities indicates quite comparable values of inward and outward lateral movement associated with a given deflection level. However, slightly higher translations occurred at the left side for both loading directions. The rotations at the corners almost coincided for both sides until achieving the positive peak value, after which a slightly asymmetrical behaviour occurred in the final loading cycle, with higher rotations at the right corner compared to the left. This was most likely due to the inhomogeneity of the masonry and imperfect symmetry of the damage. Consequently, the outward support translation was higher on the left than on the right side.

Fig. 5.2.4 Main results of test C-B1.

The main results of the two tests in terms of load and deflection at first cracking (Cr) and at collapse (UI) are summarised in Table 5.1 and Fig. 5.2.5. Since the eccentric reinforcement intervened differently, depending on the loading direction, the envelope of the load-deflection capacity curves had asymmetric trend: when pulling, the trend is elastic-plastic with hardening (end of the elastic phase at first cracking); when pushing, a sudden load decrease interrupts the elastic stage at first cracking, then a plastic stage with hardening is detected. When pushing, the CFRP strip fractures at the mid span; when pulling, the CFRP strip fractured around the corners. Sample C-R2 exhibited in pushing a peak resistance of +29.6 kN and a deflection 1/187 of the net span. The peak resistance and respective deflection in pulling were -20.3 kN, at 1/152 of the span and were lower than expected, since affected by the premature damage of fibres at the support and at the corner bend, as previously described.

Because of the smaller thickness, the resistances of C-B1 sample were lower (~22.6 kN for both loading directions). Because of different stiffness, the ultimate deflection for pulling (equal to 1/70 of the net span) resulted approximately twice that for pushing (1/140 of the net span).

Table 5.1. Main results of the tests on masonry ring beams with externally bonded FRP strips, in terms of load and deflection at first cracking (Cr) and at collapse (UI).

Sample	Load direction	First cracking (Cr)		Ultimate load (UI)	
		F_c [kN]	d_c [mm]	F_c [kN]	d_c [mm]
C-R2	Push (+)	+9.6	+1.2	+29.6	+19.5
	Pull (-)	-14.0	-1.2	-20.3*	-24.1*
C-B1	Push (+)	+10.4	+1.7	+22.9	+26.0
	Pull (-)	-14.8	-4.5	-22.2	-52.8

*premature damage of fibres

Fig. 5.2.5 Main test results of "C" samples: first cracking and collapse force (a) and deflection (b) values

5.2.2. Analytic model

Symbols:

- t thickness of the masonry cross section
- b width of the masonry cross section
- l beam span
- E_m masonry Young's modulus
- E_c CFRP Young's modulus
- α_c ratio of the CFRP and masonry Young's moduli (modular ratio) = E_c / E_m
- A_c CFRP cross section
- f_c maximum stress of the CFRP
- x_{id} idealised depth of the neutral axis of the cracked, homogenised cross-section
- I_{id} second moment of area of the cracked, homogenised cross-section

The static system of the “C” samples to evaluate the resistance is different for pulling (Fig. 5.2.6a) and pushing (Fig. 5.2.6b). For the positive loading (pushing), the system has free rotation at the extremities (vertical crack is free to occur at the inner side of the wings). In the opposite direction (pulling), the rotations are constrained at the extremities (assuming an effective continuity of the CFRP reinforcement), and a moment hinge is at the midspan (representing the vertical crack in masonry at the inner side).

However, according to the static systems, the resistance F_{Max} is the same for both cases - Eq. (5.1):

$$F_{Max} = 4 \frac{M_{RM}}{l} \quad (5.1)$$

being M_{RM} the resisting bending moment and F_{Max} the respective load.

The resisting bending moment M_{RM} of the CFRP reinforced cross section (Fig. 5.2.6c) can be estimated according to Eq. (5.2) assuming, for the sake of simplicity, plane cross-sections remain planar after deflection, perfect bond between the reinforcement and masonry, masonry has zero tensile strength and a linear-elastic response in compression, the CFRP reinforcement has a linear-elastic response in tension until reaching maximum stress f_f .

$$M_{RM} = \frac{f_c \cdot I_{id}}{\alpha_c (t - x_{id})} \quad (5.2)$$

$$x_{id} = \frac{\alpha_c \cdot A_c}{b} \left(-1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{2bt}{\alpha_c \cdot A_c}} \right) \quad (5.3)$$

$$I_{id} = \frac{b \cdot x_{id}^3}{3} + \alpha_c \cdot A_c (t - x_{id})^2 \quad (5.4)$$

Fig. 5.2.6 “C” samples: static scheme for the evaluation of the resistance in (a) positive and (b) negative directions and (c) reinforced masonry cross-section.

5.2.3. Application and validation

The analytical results are reported in Fig. 5.2.7, also in comparisons with the experimental outcomes.

Main data		
l	[mm]	3650
b	[mm]	1000
E_F	[MPa]	353000
A_F	[mm ²]	66.6
f_F	[MPa]	1314

		C-R2	C-B1
t	[mm]	350	250
E_m	[MPa]	1074.2	1638.6
α_F	[-]	329	215
x_{id}	[mm]	103.8	71.6
I_{id}	[mm ⁴]	1.7E+09	5.8E+08
M_{RM}	[kN·m]	27.6	19.8
F_{Max}	[kN]	30.3	21.7

Fig. 5.2.7 Analytic results concerning the out-of-plane tests and comparison with the experimental behaviour.

6. Conclusions

The detailed review and critical analysis of the “CONSTRAIN” experimental tests were achieved, with focus on masonry piers and spandrels strengthened with CRM and subjected to in plane loads, and masonry elements strengthened with CRM, CFRP strips and GFRP meshes embedded in the bed joints, subjected to out-of-plane bending. The mechanical response was described through appropriate, simple analytical-mechanical models, useful for preliminary design purposes. The ongoing parametric numerical analyses (under activities A1.2 and A1.3 of the PRO-SIS project) will allow for further refinement and validation of the proposed analytical models, to be adopted by professional designers.

Acknowledgments

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Appendix A.

Material characteristics

I. Masonry characteristics

Three different masonry types were considered in the “CONSTRAIN” experimental campaign (Fig. I.1): double leaf rubble stone masonry, 350 mm thick (R2), double leaf solid clay brick masonry, 250 mm thick (B2) and single leaf solid clay brick masonry, 250 mm thick (B1).

Fig. I.1 Masonry types (a) R2, (b) B2 and (c) B1.

The stone units were a mix of two Credaro stones: Berrettino (sandstone) and Medolo (limestone), with approximate compressive and flexural strengths of 160 MPa and 20 MPa, respectively. The units had approximate dimensions of 150x100x210 mm³ (width x height x length), laid in a two-leaves masonry configuration, although there was substantial size variability between the elements. The thickness of the joints was about 10 mm but varied significantly due to the irregular shape of the stones.

The solid clay bricks (120x55x250 mm³, width x height x length) had a surface roughness replicating the typical appearance of old masonry structures and had a nominal compressive strength of 18 MPa. The bricks in the samples were arranged in two different bond patterns (~10 mm thick joints). The former (for masonry B2) replicated a double-leaf masonry wall composed of two adjacent, independent wythes made up following the “stretcher bond”; headers were provided at the ends of alternating rows. The latter (for masonry B1) followed to the “English bond”, alternating courses of headers and stretchers, with headers laid centred over the stretchers in the course below.

All the masonry types were assembled with a natural lime mortar simulating the weak mortar typically found in historical buildings. It was a mixture of natural hydraulic lime and sand, in a lime-to-sand ratio of 1:7 by mass (i.e., 200 kg hydraulic lime and 1400 kg of sand per m³ of mortar). The mean values of flexural ($f_{b,f}$) and compressive strength ($f_{b,c}$) are reported in Table A.1.

Table A.1 Mechanical properties from tests on masonry prisms.

Ref. sample name	n° samples	Age [days]	Mechanical properties	
			$f_{b,f}$ [MPa] (CoV [%])	$f_{b,c}$ [MPa] (CoV [%])
S-R2-1, A3_1, A3_1	-	-	0,23 (18 %)	1,11 (17 %)
S-R2-2	21	36	0,36 (23%)	1,95 (12 %)
S-B1	/	/	/	/
S-B2	21	38	0,30 (15 %)	1,86 (6 %)
A2_1, A2_2	6	34	0,30(10 %)	1,50 (9 %)
A1_1, A1_1	6	97	0,29 (12 %)	1,63 (7 %)
T1	12	43	0,76 (10 %)	1,99 (11 %)
T2	6	43	0,59 (5 %)	1,62 (7 %)
P-R2U, P-R2R-1, P-R2R-2, B-R2	12	66	0.17 (16%)	0,93 (5 %)

For each of the three masonry types, monotonic compressive tests were carried out on two masonry wallets (500 mm width, 1000 mm height); the main test results are summarized in Table A.2 - Table A.4.

Table A.2 Mechanical properties of stone masonry (R2).

Sample ID	Peak force [kN]	Compressive strength [MPa]	Young modulus [MPa]	Ultimate strain [%]
A3_1	451.64	2.58	1162.0	1.2 %
A3_2	416.96	2.38	986.4	2.8 %
Average	434.30	2.48	1074.2	2 %

Table A.3 Mechanical properties of double-leaf brick masonry (B2).

Sample ID	Peak force [kN]	Compressive strength [MPa]	Young modulus [MPa]	Ultimate strain [%]
A2_1	875.60	6.86	2073.5	1.1
A2_2	750.68	6.00	2293.1	*
Average	813.14	6.43	2183.3	1.1

* Instruments were damaged after reaching a strain of 0.37%

Table A.4 Mechanical properties of single-leaf brick masonry (B1).

Sample ID	Peak force [kN]	Compressive strength [MPa]	Young modulus [MPa]	Ultimate strain [%]
A1_1*	490.3	3.8	1589.1	0.35
A1_2	852.4	6.7	2341.1	**
Average	852.4	6.7	2341.1	-

* Failure of the sample was eccentric. Values are not considered.

** Instruments were damaged after reaching a strain of 0.3%

II. Strengthening materials characteristics

For the CRM, a pre-mixed natural hydraulic lime mortar was used for the coating. The mean values of flexural ($f_{c,f}$) and compressive strengths ($f_{c,c}$) are reported in Table A.5.

Table A.5 Mechanical properties of mortar for strengthening.

Ref. sample name	n° samples	Age [days]	Mechanical properties	
			$f_{c,f}$ [MPa] (CoV [%])	$f_{c,c}$ [MPa] (CoV [%])
S-R2-1	3	40	4,2 (5 %)	22,9 (10 %)
S-R2-2	12	38	5,6 (4%)	24,6 (5 %)
S-B1	12	84	4,4 (7 %)	20,1 (8 %)
S-B2	15	39	3,9 (15 %)	15,0 (20 %)
P-R2R-1, P-R2R-2, B-R2	6	35	3,0 (10 %)	30,1 (4%)

The preformed FRP meshes (Fig. II.1) embedded within the coating were composed of long Alkali-Resistant glass fibres embedded in a thermosetting resin made of epoxy vinylester with benzoyl peroxide as catalyst (Glass FRP - GFRP). They had a 66x66 mm² grid dimension and were composed of twisted-fibre wires in the warp direction, weaved on parallel-fibre wires in the weft direction (dry fibre cross-sectional area in the wire of 3.8 mm²). The main mechanical properties are presented in Table A.6. The same type of meshes were used also for the masonry ring beams samples with meshes embedded in bed joints.

Fig. II.1 GFRP mesh for the CRM system: (a) general view of the mesh rolls and (b) detail.

Table A.6 Mechanical properties of the GFRP mesh: tensile resistance T_G , ultimate strain $\epsilon_{u,G}$ and axial stiffness EA_G .

Property	Twisted fibres wires		Parallel fibres wires	
	Mean	COV (%)	Mean	COV (%)
T_G (kN)	5.11	2.4	5.93	3.9
$\epsilon_{u,G}$ (%)	1.85	1.9	2.03	4.2
EA_G (kN)	276.7	2.6	291.2	1.6

The GFRP L-shaped connectors had a cross-section of 7 x 10 mm², with a dry fiber cross section of 32.4 mm² (nominal characteristic tensile strength of 17 kN and ultimate strain of 1.9 %.) - Fig.

II.2a. The holes drilled in the masonry had a diameter of 24 mm for double-side application (with connectors overlapping length of at least 200 mm), and of 16 mm for single-sided. The holes were injected with bi-component vinylester chemical anchor. The GFRP mesh sheets were 165x165 mm², with a 33x33 mm² mesh grid dimension (Fig. II.2b).

Fig. II.2 GFRP transversal connections: (a) the "L"-shape connector and (b) the mesh sheets.

The artificial diatons (Fig. II.3) were made with a 16 mm diameter threaded stainless steel bar (AISI 316) embedded in a 50 mm diameter core of high resistance thixotropic cement-based mortar and were provided at the head with a perforated stainless steel washers (4 mm thick, 150 mm diameter), with a nut welded at the centre, screwed on the head of the threaded bar.

Fig. II.3 Artificial diaton: (a) assembling of the steel connector and (b) detail of the perforated head washer.

Generally, the number, position and diameter of connectors are crucial for the transversal tying and depend on the masonry texture, thickness and mechanical characteristic. In lack of a specific design procedure, reference was made to the literature. In particular, the GFRP injected connectors were distributed by considering the range 4–6/m² suggested by Tomazevic [6] for traditional reinforced-cement coating. For dimensioning the artificial diatons, reference was made to the ranges suggested by Castori et al. [7] for historic hard-stone masonry (barely cut stones and pebbles assembled with lime-based mortars): connector diameter: 16–20 mm; hole diameter to connector diameter ratio: 3–4; connectors distance to hole diameter ratio: 9–11.

The unidirectional CFRP strips for the masonry ring beams with the externally bonded strengthening system (Fig. II.4) had a width of 200 mm and a dry fibre cross-section of 66.6 mm² (fibre mass per unit area 600 g/m²). Epoxy-impregnated CFRP coupons provided mean values

of tensile strength and Young modulus of 1314.3 MPa (CoV = 8.7%) and 353 GPa (CoV = 13.6%), respectively.

Fig. II.4 CFRP strips: (a) dry fibres roll and (b) detail of application

PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.2
**Modelli numerici per la
simulazione del
comportamento di
elementi /edifici rinforzati**

NOVEMBRE 2025

Poročilo 1.2
**Numerični modeli za
simulacijo obnašanja utrjenih
konstrukcijskih elementov
in stavb**

NOVEMBER 2025

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PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.2

Numerical models for the simulation of the behavior of reinforced elements/buildings

NOVEMBER 2025

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Report 1.2

Numerical models for the simulation of the behavior of reinforced elements/buildings

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1. Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 1.2 of the PRO-SIS project, aimed at the Development of numerical models capable of simulating the actual behaviour of experimental samples tested in the CONSTRAIN project.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extended experimental campaign. The developed strengthening method is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced by fiber-based composite materials. The main advantage of the developed system is that it can be applied only on one side of the wall, which makes it much more convenient for residents and businesses. Due to construction works only on the outside of the building, people and their belongings don't have to be relocated, and business activity doesn't have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the inside (or outside, when the inside side application is preferred). The developed strengthening method stands out because of its proven effectiveness by tests on structural components and on full scale pilot building.

The aim of the "PRO-SIS" project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for the design and application of these strategies. For this purpose, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated on the experimental results of "CONSTRAIN". The results provide the designers with robust strategies for the design of the proposed systems, and instructions for design in commonly used commercial programs for design of structures.

In the previous report "REPORT 1.1: Analytic model for dimensioning" [1] the CONSTRAIN experimental results are gathered, analysed in depth, compared and critically reviewed and a first approach to the definition and calibration of analytical-mechanical models capable to describe the experimental behaviour is presented.

This REPORT 1.2 presents the main features of the advanced numerical models developed to accurately simulate the behaviour of masonry elements strengthened with Composite Reinforced Mortar. The purpose of developing the detailed numerical models is to use them instead of expensive and time-consuming experimental tests on configurations that were not tested within CONSTRAIN. Moreover, these models will allow also a broader validation of more simplified predictive models for the seismic behaviour masonry structures strengthened with CRM (such as the equivalent frame method with lumped plasticity).

Two different finite element software were considered (ABAQUS and OOFEM) and this report provides a detailed description of the two simulation approaches applied for analysing the CONSTRAIN samples.

The ABAQUS models were developed primarily by the University of Ljubljana (UL FGG), while the OOFEM models were developed by the University of Trieste (DIA – UNITS). In this process,

the two partners began by sharing the same available experimental data, then worked independently, each autonomously defining its own procedures and analysis parameters. Once the simulations were completed, they combined and compared the results. Intentionally, some assumptions were not strictly enforced to be identical, in order to identify the impact of the uncertainty inherent in the two different approaches.

The report starts with a summary of the experimental evidences. Then, there are the two main sections of the report, one for each type modelling developed. For each section, the first part resumes the modelling approach, and the latter the numeric results, which include a comparison with the experimental CONSTRAIN tests. At the end, a final section provides a direct comparison and analyses of the results.

2. List of the experimental samples

The full-scale tests performed within CONSTRAIN project, that are modelled by the detailed numerical models are presented in Table 2.1. They consist of shear-compression tests on piers and shear-bending tests on spandrels. Rubble stone and solid brick masonry were considered, and different configurations of strengthening (unstrengthened, strengthened on one side and strengthened on both sides).

The labelling of samples presented in Table 2.1 and used throughout the report is as follows:

- P/S = Pier or Spandrel
- R2/B1/B2 = two leaf rubble/one leaf brick/two leaf brick
- U/R1/R2 = unstrengthened/strengthened on one side/strengthened on two sides

The main geometric characteristics of masonry pier and spandrel samples are illustrated in Fig. 2.1 and Fig. 2.2, respectively. All relevant dimensions are included, to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the configurations.

Detailed description of the experimental tests features and results can be found in [1].

Table 2.1: List of tests that are modelled by detailed numerical models

Type of test	Masonry type	Wall wythes	Label	Strengthening
In-plane tests on masonry piers	Stone	2	P-R2U	/
	Stone	2	P-R2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Stone	2	P-R2R-2	CRM on two-sides
	Solid brick	2	P-B2U	/
	Solid brick	2	P-B2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Solid brick	2	P-B2R-2	CRM on two-sides
	Solid brick	1	P-B1U	/
	Solid brick	1	P-B1R	CRM on one-side
In-plane tests on masonry spandrels	Stone	2	S-R2U-1	/
	Stone	2	S-R2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Stone	2	S-R2U-2	/
	Stone	2	S-R2R -2	CRM on two-sides
	Solid brick	2	S-B2U-1	/
	Solid brick	1	S-B2R-1	CRM on one-side
	Solid brick	1	S-B1U-1	/
	Solid brick	2	S-B1R-1	CRM on one-side

Fig. 2.1 Main geometric characteristics of the pier samples.

Fig. 2.2 Main geometric characteristics of the spandrel samples.

3. Numerical modelling with ABAQUS (by UL FGG)

ABAQUS Simulia [2] is a commercial software for modelling of structures using the finite element method. The program is suitable for modelling response of brittle or ductile materials, for static and dynamic analysis and is particularly known for its ability to model various contacts.

3.1. Modelling approach

The numerical models were developed to accurately capture the actual geometry and boundary conditions of the tested specimens, with certain separate considerations for piers and spandrels, as elaborated later. There are separate meshes for masonry, mortar coating and glass fibre mesh, and each material has its own nonlinear material model (see §3.2).

Both the masonry and the mortar coating were modelled as a continuum using 3D solid linear brick elements (C3D8R) with eight nodes and reduced integration, ensuring computational efficiency and stability in explicit dynamic simulations [2]. The glass fibre mesh, on the other hand, was represented using T3D2 elements, 2-node linear 3D truss elements, which was incorporated into the models as a separate component with lengths and positions taken from the tested pier and spandrels.

The masonry and mortar materials were characterized using the well-established Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model, widely used for brittle materials such as masonry and concrete. The material parameters were carefully determined based on experimental tests on materials and further refined through calibration with experimental test results from piers and spandrels. The stress-strain relationships (shape of the curve) followed the modelling approach proposed by Stavridis and Shing [3].

Different material properties were assigned for each of the three masonry types in the study: two-leaf rubble stone, single-leaf brick, and double-leaf brick. Extensive numerical analyses confirmed that the material properties in tension played a crucial role in obtaining accurate wall response predictions. Consequently, the material model in tension was modified and adjusted to account for additional effects which were not explicitly considered, such as friction in cracks, interlocking of stones, coating debonding, and the influence of anchoring.

A similar approach was adopted for the mortar used in the strengthening method. The tensile material law was adjusted in parallel with the masonry parameters to ensure a consistent response. Particular attention was given to calibrating the composite interaction of the GFRP mesh and mortar, to adequately reproduce the behaviour observed in experimental tests.

The material model for GFRP mesh was modelled as a perfectly brittle elastic material using the Plastic model in ABAQUS. The rupture stress values were determined based on the experimentally observed rupture forces of each fibre type (weft of warped).

Explicit dynamic analyses were employed for the numerical simulations, given their well-known advantages in modelling brittle response, such as improved numerical stability and fewer convergence issues. The time increment varied depending on the type of simulation, with

minimum and maximum values set at 0.000001s and 0.001s, respectively. A dedicated parametric analysis was conducted to determine the optimal balance between computational efficiency and accuracy.

To further enhance computational speed, mass scaling was applied. The scaling factor was selected to achieve a target time increment of 0.001 s for pilot building analyses and between 0.0001 s and 0.00008 s for other simulations. Additional analyses confirmed that mass scaling had a negligible influence on accuracy of the results. Simulations performed with and without mass scaling produced nearly identical results, as illustrated in Fig. 3.1.

Fig. 3.1 Comparison of typical pushover curves for models with and without mass scaling.

3.2. Material models

- Stone masonry

Material properties of stone masonry in compression were based on two compression tests on stone masonry and tests on masonry piers and spandrels (see CONSTRAIN report for details [4]). The pre-peak stress strain constitutive model was taken as the average of two compression tests, as shown in Fig. 3.2a. Elastic modulus amounted to 4500 MPa and peak compressive strength to $f_c = 2.5$ MPa.

The post-peak part of the constitutive model for compression is characterized by a gradual reduction towards the residual strength, which is 20% of the compressive strength ($r_c = 0.2 f_c$). The complete constitutive law for stone masonry in compression is shown in Fig. 3.2b.

The constitutive model for tension was defined as a stress-strain curve according to the recommendations of Stavridis and Shing [3]. As mentioned in the previous Section, this part of the material response had the greatest influence on the results and was modified to account for phenomena not explicitly included in the model. Therefore, a high residual tensile strength ($r_t = 0.4 f_t$) was assumed, with a large deformation of 2.5 % at final failure in tension in order to match the ductility of spandrel samples. Tensile strength was 0.21 MPa (about 8 % of

compressive strength of stone masonry). The stress-strain relationship under tension for the stone masonry is shown in Fig. 3.3.

Fig. 3.2 Stress-strain curve for stone masonry in compression: (a) pre-peak response and comparison with experiment and (b) post-peak response.

Fig. 3.3 Stress-strain curve for stone masonry in tension: (a) the initial response and (b) complete response.

- Single leaf brick masonry

Material properties of single-leaf brick masonry in compression were based on two compression tests, and tests on masonry piers and spandrels (see CONSTRAIN report [3] for details). The pre-peak stress strain constitutive model was assumed based on a compression test, as shown in Fig. 3.4. Elastic modulus amounted to 2341 MPa and peak compressive strength to $f_c = 6.7$ MPa.

The post-peak part of the constitutive model for compression is characterized by a gradual reduction towards the residual strength, which is 20% of the compressive strength ($r_c = 0.2 f_c$). The complete constitutive law for single-leaf brick masonry in compression is shown in Fig. 3.4.

The constitutive model for tension was defined as a stress-strain curve, similar to that for stone masonry, based on the work of Stavridis and Shing [3]. This part of the material curve had the greatest influence on the results, as stated in the previous Section. The newly adjusted model incorporates phenomena that were not explicitly modelled in the original version. Therefore, a

high residual tensile strength ($r_t = 0.66 f_t$) was assumed, with a large deformation of 2.5 % at final failure in tension, again for accounting spandrel's ductility. Tensile strength of single-leaf brick masonry was set to 0.23 MPa. The stress-strain relationship under tension for the single-leaf brick masonry is shown in Fig. 3.5.

Fig. 3.4 Stress-strain curve for single-leaf brick masonry in compression.

Fig. 3.5 Stress-strain curve for single-leaf brick masonry in tension: (a) initial response and (b) complete response.

- Double leaf brick masonry

Material properties of double-leaf brick masonry in compression were based on two compression tests on masonry and tests on masonry piers and spandrels (see CONSTRAIN report [4] for details). The pre-peak stress strain constitutive model was determined based on a compression test, and is shown in Fig. 3.6. Elastic modulus amounted to 2200 MPa and peak compressive strength to $f_c = 6.4$ MPa.

The post-peak part of the constitutive model for compression was characterised by gradual reduction towards the residual strength, which amounted to 20% of compressive strength ($r_c = 0.2 f_c$). The complete constitutive law for double-leaf brick masonry in compression is shown in Fig. 3.6.

The constitutive model for tension was defined as a stress-strain curve, following the approach of Stavridis and Shing [3]. As highlighted in previous sections, the stress-strain curve in tension had the most significant influence on the results and was adjusted to account for phenomena

not explicitly included in the original model. It should be noted that the high residual tensile strength ($r_t = 0.84 f_t$) was assumed with a large deformation of 1.13 % at final failure in tension with respect to spandrel's ductility. Tensile strength of the double-leaf brick masonry was set to 0.14 MPa. The stress-strain relationship under tension for the double-leaf brick masonry is shown in Fig. 3.7.

Fig. 3.6 Stress-strain curve for double-leaf brick masonry in compression.

Fig. 3.7 Stress-strain curve for double-leaf brick masonry in tension: (a) initial response and (b) complete response.

- Mortar coating

The stress-strain formulation for mortar coating in compression was the same as for stone and brick masonry. Elastic modulus was 9000 MPa, as specified in technical datasheet, and the compressive strength f_c was 30.1 MPa. Residual strength was set to 0 MPa. The graph of the material model for mortar coating is shown in Fig. 3.8.

The tensile portion of the constitutive model (Fig. 3.9) was determined in the same manner as for stone masonry, with the residual tensile strength set to 30 % of the tensile strength ($r_c = 0.3 f_c$). Both the peak tensile and residual strengths were calibrated based on experimental results. The final residual tensile strength was set to 0 MPa to reflect the brittle failure of the mortar after the rupture of the GFRP, which occurred at a strain of 2.3 %.

Fig. 3.8 Stress-strain curve for mortar coating in compression.

Fig. 3.9 Stress-strain curve for mortar coating in tension: (a) initial response and (b) complete response.

- GFRP mesh

The constitutive material model for the glass fibres was derived from the results of axial tensile tests. The values for elastic modulus are taken from the technical datasheet, and equal to 36400 MPa and 31443 MPa for weft and warped yarns, respectively. The mesh has different properties for weft and warped directions, as presented in Fig. 3.10.

Fig. 3.10 Tensile and compressive stress-strain curves for GFRP mesh.

- Concrete

The concrete material used for modelling the foundations and top beam was treated as an ideally elastic material in ABAQUS software, with an elastic modulus of 40000 MPa.

3.3. In-plane behaviour of piers

3.3.1. *Geometry, boundary conditions and loads*

The models consist of masonry wall (stone or brick) and two concrete beams, one at the top and one at the bottom, as seen in Fig. 3.11. GFRP mesh is embedded inside the mortar coating. Additionally, two steel beams are included as part of the testing apparatus, positioned above and below the concrete beams. In the numerical model, contact springs were placed between the steel and concrete elements to reproduce the displacements that were measured at those locations.

Fig. 3.11 ABAQUS models for piers: unstrengthened U (a), strengthened on one side R1 (b) and both sides R2 (c).

The boundary conditions are illustrated in Fig. 3.12. The bottom steel beam is fixed to the laboratory floor, restricting both horizontal and vertical movements as well as rotation, in accordance with the experimental setup. The top steel beam is free to move horizontally and vertically while its rotations remain constrained, ensuring realistic replication of experimental conditions.

Between the steel and concrete beams, springs were used as connectors to model the uplift observed at the heel during experiments. A connector stiffness of 1.875 N/mm/mm² was applied consistently across all tests to capture this behaviour. These connectors permitted movement only in the vertical direction, while translations in the other two directions were restricted using slot-type connectors available in ABAQUS [2].

At the start of the numerical simulation, a constant vertical pressure of 0.5 MPa was applied to the top steel beam surface, with the self-weight of the material contributing to the total vertical load (Fig. 3.12). This vertical load remained constant throughout the simulation, which is consistent with the experimental conditions. Following the application of the vertical load, a monotonic horizontal displacement was introduced at the top steel beam, pushing from left to right (Fig. 3.13).

As mentioned at the beginning, the analyses were of the explicit dynamic type. The duration of each analysis was specified individually for each experiment, ensuring a balance between computational efficiency and numerical accuracy by maintaining a reasonable simulation time.

Fig. 3.12 Boundary conditions and applied load in the numerical models.

Fig. 3.13 Load amplitudes.

Regarding the contact definition, the concrete beam was constrained to the masonry in the tangential direction, assuming infinite friction, while allowing separation in the normal direction to accommodate tensile opening. All other contacts were fully tied.

3.3.2. Numerical results and comparisons

- Pier P-R2-U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened stone masonry pier and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation on the FE model in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.14a. The deformed configuration of unstrengthened stone masonry pier P-R2U is shown in Fig. 3.14b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.15. Finally, the uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.16.

Fig. 3.14 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-R2-U (a) and deformed configuration of the model (b).

Fig. 3.15 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (plastic strain - PE) (a) and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.16 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-R2-R1

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of stone masonry pier P-R2-R1 and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.17a. The deformed configurations of the mortar coating, and the stone masonry under the mortar are shown in 3.19b-c. The comparison of the damage predicted by numerical simulation and damage pattern observed in the experiment are shown in Fig. 3.18. Fig. 3.19 shows the damage in the GFRP mesh in terms of rupture of fibres. The uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.20.

Fig. 3.17 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-R2-R1 (a) and deformed configuration, with view of the mortar coating (b) and of the stone masonry (b). Deformation scale is 10.

Fig. 3.18 Elastic strains – view of mortar (a) and stone masonry under the mortar (b) and experiment (c).

Fig. 3.19 Elastic strain in GFRP. Red zones indicate ruptured fibres.

Fig. 3.20 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-R2-R2

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of stone masonry pier P-R2-R2 and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.21. The deformed configurations of the mortar coating, and the stone masonry under the mortar are also shown in Fig. 3.21. The comparison of the damage predicted by numerical simulation and damage pattern observed in the experiment are shown in Fig. 3.22. The damage predicted in the GFRP mesh is shown in Fig. 3.23. Finally, the uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.24.

Fig. 3.21 (Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-R2-R2 (a) and deformed configuration of the model (b)).

Fig. 3.22 Elastic strains – view of mortar (a), masonry under the mortar (b) and experiment (c).

Fig. 3.23 Elastic strain in GFRP. Red zones indicate ruptured fibres.

Fig. 3.24 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-B1-U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened single-leaf brick masonry pier and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.25a. The deformed configuration of unstrengthened brick masonry pier P-B1U is shown in Fig. 3.25b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.26. Finally, the uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.27.

Fig. 3.25 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-B1-U (a) and deformed configuration of the model (b).

Fig. 3.26 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (plastic strain - PE), (a) and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.27 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-B1-R1

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of a single-leaf brick masonry pier strengthened on one side P-B1-R1 and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.28a. The deformed configurations of the mortar coating, and the brick masonry under the mortar are shown in Fig. 3.28b-c. The comparison of the damage predicted by numerical simulation and damage pattern observed in the experiment are shown in Fig. 3.29. Fig. 3.30 shows the damage in the GFRP mesh in terms of rupture of fibres. The uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.31.

Fig. 3.28 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-B1-R1 (a) and deformed configuration: view of the mortar coating (b) and of the masonry (c). Deformation scale is 10.

Fig. 3.29 Plastic strains - view of mortar (a), masonry under the mortar (b) and experiment (c).

Fig. 3.30 Elastic strain in GFRP. Red zones indicate ruptured fibres.

Fig. 3.31 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-B2-U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened double-leaf brick masonry pier and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.32a. The deformed configuration of unstrengthened brick masonry pier P-B2U is shown in Fig. 3.32b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.33. Finally, the uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.34.

Fig. 3.32 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-B2-U (a) and deformed configuration of the model (b).

Fig. 3.33 Damage (plastic strain) (a) and damage during experiment (b).

Fig. 3.34 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

- Pier P-B2-R1

The capacity curve (V_p-d_p) of single double leaf brick masonry pier strengthened on one side (P-B2-R1) is shown in Fig. 3.35a. Deformed configurations of the pier, and the masonry below the pier are shown in Fig. 3.35b-c. Damage in mortar and masonry, and comparison of the damage to the experiment are shown in Fig. 3.36. Fig. 3.37 shows the damage in the GFRP mesh. Finally, the uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.38.

Fig. 3.35 Push Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-B2-R1 (a) and deformed configuration: view of the mortar coating (b) and of the masonry (c). Deformation scale is 10.

Fig. 3.36 Plastic strains – view of mortar (a), masonry under the mortar (b) and experiment (c).

Fig. 3.37 GFRP elastic strain. Red zones show ruptured fibres.

Fig. 3.38 Uplift at the heel, compression at the toe and comparison with the experiment.

- Pier P-B2-R2

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of a double-leaf brick masonry pier strengthened on both sides P-B2-R2 and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.39a. The deformed configuration of brick masonry pier P-B2-R2 is shown in Fig. 3.39b. The comparison of the damage predicted by numerical simulation and damage pattern observed in the experiment are shown in Fig. 3.40. Fig. 3.41 shows the damage in the GFRP mesh in terms of rupture of fibres. The uplift at the heel and compression at the toe are shown in Fig. 3.42.

Fig. 3.39 (a) Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for P-B2-R2; (b) Deformed configuration of the model.

Fig. 3.40 Elastic strains - view of mortar (a), masonry under the mortar (b) and experiment (c).

Fig. 3.41 Elastic strain in GFRP. Red zones indicate ruptured fibres.

Fig. 3.42 Comparison between numerical and experimental results: uplift at the heel and compression at the toe.

3.4. In-plane behaviour of spandrels

3.4.1. *Geometry, boundary conditions and loads*

The models comprise of masonry wall (stone or brick) and four concrete beams, two at the top and two at the bottom, as seen in Fig. 3.43. GFRP mesh is embedded inside the mortar coating, and applied on one or both sides the masonry.

Fig. 3.43 The FEM mesh in ABAQUS models of spandrels.

The boundary conditions are illustrated in Fig. 3.44. Initially, the concrete beam on the bottom left could only rotate around its center, while the concrete beam on the bottom right could rotate around its center and slide horizontally.

Fig. 3.44 Boundary conditions and applied load in the models.

A constant vertical pressure of 0.4 MPa was applied to the top concrete beam surfaces. This pressure of 0.4 MPa is the sum of the 0.33 MPa vertical pressure during the experiment and the total gravity load force divided by the top beam surface area (Fig. 3.44). This vertical load remained constant throughout the simulation, which is consistent with the experimental conditions.

Following the application of the vertical load, shear and bending loads were applied through displacements at the inner edges of the bottom concrete beams, as seen in Fig. 3.44. The displacements on the left and right were equal but in opposite directions. The loading was applied monotonically, resulting in clockwise rotations of the piers. The imposed displacement was applied after the vertical load (Fig. 3.45).

As previously stated, the analyses were of the explicit dynamic type. The duration of analysis was specified individually for each experiment in order to have minimal but long enough time duration for optimal time efficiency – numerical accuracy of our model.

Fig. 3.45 Load amplitudes.

Concrete beam is tied to masonry (stone or brick) in tangential direction to achieve infinite friction but allows separation in normal direction (tensile opening).

Regarding the interaction between wooden lintel and stone masonry is defined as friction contact with friction coefficient 0.1 that allows separation (tension induced opening). ON the other hand, interaction between brick arch lintel and brick masonry is defined as friction contact with friction coefficient 0.5 that allows separation (tension induced opening).

All other contacts were tied.

3.4.2. Numerical results and comparisons

- Spandrel S-R2-U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened stone masonry spandrel and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.46a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of unstrengthened stone masonry spandrel S-R2U is shown in Fig. 3.46b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.47. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.48. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be reproduced by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.46 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-R2-U (a) and deformed configuration of unstrengthened stone masonry spandrel (b).

Fig. 3.47 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (logarithmic strain - LE), (a). Damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.48 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-R2-R1

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of stone masonry spandrel strengthened on one side and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.49a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of stone masonry spandrel S-R2-R1 is shown in Fig. 3.49b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.50. The strain and locations of fracture of GFRP fibres are shown in Fig. 3.51. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.52. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be reproduced by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.49 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-R2-R1 (a) and deformed configuration of stone masonry spandrel strengthened on one side (b)

(c)

Fig. 3.50 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (logarithmic strain - LE) in mortar coating (a) and in the masonry (b), and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.51 GFRP strains. Fibres in red zones have ruptured.

Fig. 3.52 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-R2-R2

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of stone masonry spandrel strengthened on both sides and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.53a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of the spandrel model is shown in Fig. 3.53b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.54. The strain and fracture locations of the GFRP fibres are shown in Fig. 3.55. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.56. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be replicated by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.53 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-R2-R2 (a) and deformed configuration of stone masonry spandrel strengthened on both sides (b).

(c)

Fig. 3.54 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (logarithmic strain - LE) in mortar coating (a) and in the masonry (b), and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.55 GFRP strains. Fibres in red zones have ruptured.

Fig. 3.56 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-B1-U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened single-leaf brick masonry spandrel and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.57a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of brick masonry spandrel S-B1U is shown in Fig. 3.57b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.58. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.59. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be reproduced by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.57 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-B1-U (a) and deformed configuration of unstrengthened single-leaf brick masonry spandrel (b)

Fig. 3.58 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (plastic strain - PE), (a) and damage pattern observed during the experiment, right (b).

Fig. 3.59 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-B1-R1

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of single-leaf brick masonry spandrel strengthened on one side and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.60a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of brick masonry spandrel S-B1-R1 is shown in Fig. 3.60b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.61. The strain and locations of fracture of GFRP fibres are shown in Fig. 3.62. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.63. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be replicated by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.60 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-B1-R1 (a) and deformed configuration of single-leaf brick masonry spandrel strengthened on one side (b).

Fig. 3.61 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation in mortar coating (plastic strain - PE), (a) and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.62 GFRP strains. Fibres in red zones have ruptured.

Fig. 3.63 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-B2U

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of unstrengthened double-leaf brick masonry spandrel and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation in the ABAQUS software are presented in Fig. 3.64a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of brick masonry spandrel S-B2U is shown in Fig. 3.64b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.65. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.66. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be replicated by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.64 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-B2U (a) and deformed configuration of unstrengthened double-leaf brick masonry spandrel (b).

Fig. 3.65 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (plastic strain - PE), (a) and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b)

Fig. 3.66 Horizontal movement of the right support.

- Spandrel S-B2-R1

The comparison between the experimentally obtained envelope curve of double-leaf brick masonry spandrel strengthened on one side and capacity curve (V_p-d_p) obtained from the numerical simulation are presented in Fig. 3.67a. Since the response in the positive and negative loading directions differed, both numerical curves are shown in the graph. The deformed configuration of brick masonry spandrel S-B2-R1 is shown in Fig. 3.67b. The damage predicted by the numerical model and damage pattern from the experiment are compared in Fig. 3.68. The strain and locations of fracture of GFRP fibres are shown in Fig. 3.69. Finally, the horizontal movement of the right support is shown in Fig. 3.70. The right support gradually creeps (curve gradually moves upwards) because the cracks do not fully close during the experiment. This cannot be replicated by the current model, and therefore the displacement of the support is plotted twice (once with solid and once with dashed line) to facilitate comparison.

Fig. 3.67 Comparison of the numerical force-displacement curve and the experimental envelope curve for S-B2-R1 (a) and deformed configuration of double-leaf masonry spandrel strengthened on one side (b)

(c)

Fig. 3.68 Damage predicted by the numerical simulation (logarithmic strain - LE) in mortar coating (a) and in the masonry (b), and damage pattern observed during the experiment (b).

Fig. 3.69 GFRP strains. Fibres in red zones have ruptured.

Fig. 3.70 Horizontal movement of the right support.

4. Numerical modelling with OOFEM (by DIA – UNITS)

OOFEM [5] is a free, open-source code for finite element modelling (FEM), featuring an object-oriented architecture for addressing mechanical, transport, and fluid mechanics problems [6]-[7]. It is released under the GNU Lesser General Public License (LGPL v2.1) and offers a modular and extensible environment. The current version is OOFEM 2.5 [8]. For detailed information on the types of elements and materials used in simulations, refer to the OOFEM manuals section available online.

4.1. Modelling approach

The models are composed by using 20-node brick elements (“*QSpace*” OOFEM element type) with dimensions of $167 \times 167 \times T$ mm³, where T represents the overall wall thickness. The mesh size is selected to maintain an aspect ratio (the ratio between the largest and smallest characteristic dimension) between 1.5 and 3 (for numeric reliability), considering typical thickness range in existing masonry walls and providing good balance between representation accuracy and numeric convergence facilitation.

The elements feature layered cross sections (“*LayeredCS*” OOFEM cross section type), consisting of different layers arranged along the sample thickness, so to represent the original masonry, the fiber-based reinforcement, and the mortar coating (Fig. 4.1). The simplified hypotheses of perfectly bonded layers and planar cross sections are assumed. Position of mid surface is determined by its distance from bottom of cross section (normal and momentum forces are then computed with regard to its position, by default it is located at average thickness position). The number of integration points per layer can be specified (it is possible to set up different number of integration points per individual layer). The Gauss integration rule is used for setting up integration points in each layer. Specifically, 6 integration points are set for the masonry layer, 3 for the mortar coating, and 1 for the GFRP layer.

Fig. 4.1 Schematization of 20-nodes multi-layer elements used in the OOFEM models.

Nonlinear static analyses under displacement control, accounting for material nonlinearities, are performed by using the Newton-Raphson solver (relative displacement and force convergence norms set to $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$). For simplified assumption, all the materials are considered as homogeneous and isotropic, with properties set on the basis of from experimental data.

4.2. Material models

For the masonry, a concrete-damage plasticity material model is used ("CdpM2" OOFEM material type) to account for both cracking in tension and crushing in compression. The mechanical parameters are resumed in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Main numerical parameters adopted for the masonry layer (for unspecified parameters, the OOFEM default values are used [5]).

Masonry layer	Type R2	Type B2	Type B1	
OOFEM material type	CdpM2	CdpM2	CdpM2	
Secant Young's modulus E	1.07 GPa	1.34 GPa	1.64 GPa	
Initial Young's modulus E_{init}	3.22 GPa	4.00 GPa	4.92 GPa	
Poisson modulus ν	0.45	0.45	0.45	
Self-weight γ	21.0 kN/m ³	18 kN/m ³	18 kN/m ³	
Comp. strength f_c	2.48 MPa	2.98 MPa	3.84 MPa	
Tensile strength f_t	0.085* MPa	0.102**MPa	0.162 MPa	
Dilation ψ	40°	40°	40°	
Softening law	Linear	Linear	Linear	
Hardening parameters	b_h	0.022	0.015	0.015
	h_p	0.0	0.0	0.0
	k_{init}	0.15	0.15	0.15
Softening parameters	w_f/h	0.004	0.004	0.004
	a_{soft}	5.0	8.0	8.0

Tensile behavior

Compressive behavior

* reduced value, to account for the relevant interlocking effect in rubble stone masonry

** or 0.102×1.3 for masonry provided with transversal connectors and diatons, coherently to [1]

It is observed that the strength and stiffness parameters (f_t , f_c , E) are generally those already considered in the analytic study performed in the PRO-SIS project (with $f_t = 1.5 \tau_0$) [1]. In exception, a reduced value of equivalent tensile strength was considered for masonry type R2 ($\sim 0.8 f_t$), coherently with the numerical study carried out by Brignola et al. [10]. In fact, in that study it was observed that in rubble stone masonry a relevant redistribution of the stresses due to the interlocking effect occurs in the specimen (which is almost negligible in regular, solid brick masonry), resulting in a further appreciable increase of the diagonal cracking load after the occurrence of the first cracking.

So that, since the values of f_t were calculated in [1] from the unstrengthened panel resistance, a reduction is deemed necessary for masonry R2, to correctly detect the first cracking.

For all masonry types, the stress-strain uniaxial tensile law is linear elastic till reaching f_t ; the resistance is initially maintained constant and, then, a linear decay occurs. For compression, the stress-strain uniaxial law is linear elastic till achieving k_{init} times the strength (k_{init} set to 0.15), then it prosecutes with a parabolic trend, accounting for a progressive stiffness degradation: the initial value of Young's modulus E_{init} is set equal to 3 times the mean, secant one E ; then an exponential law decay is considered.

The masonry constitutive laws under uniaxial compressive and tensile stresses are represented in Fig. 4.2. The softening parameters are calibrated so to fit the results of the CONSTRAIN in-plane cyclic tests on unstrengthened masonry piers.

It is important to note that, due to the assumption of a homogeneous isotropic material, the masonry behavior is considered uniform in all directions, irrespective of the orientation relative to the bed joints. While this simplified assumption may not precisely simulate the behavior of unreinforced masonry, it is deemed an acceptable approximation for the model purpose, focused on CRM-strengthened reinforced masonry.

Fig. 4.2 Masonry uniaxial constitutive laws in (a) compression and (b) tension.

To the uniform layer representing the Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (GFRP) mesh, a unitary thickness is assigned. The material parameters are based on experimental outcomes from tensile tests on GFRP yarns and are scaled over the uniform layer. For this simplification, the average resistance of the GFRP yarns in the two mesh directions is considered. The main parameters are resumed in Table 4.2; it is observed that the stiffness and peak strain parameters (E , ϵ_0) are coherent to those already considered in the analytic study performed in the PRO-SIS project [1].

The isotropic damage model for tensile failure is assigned to the layer ("*ldm1*" OOFEM material type), so the material to be linear elastic in tension up to peak tensile stress and then performing a linear stress decay, with slope set so to account for the progressive breakage of concurrently stressed yarns (the so called "group effect"). The compressive resistance is neglected. Moreover, the contribution of the layer to the shear stiffness of the wall is neglected by setting a low Poisson's ratio.

Table 4.2 Main numerical parameters adopted for the GFRP layer (for unspecified parameters, the OOFEM default values are used [5]).

GFRP layer	
OOFEM material type	<i>ldm1</i>
Young's modulus E	3.81 GPa
Poisson modulus ν	0.01
Comp. strength f_c	0
OOFEM Equiv. strain type	modified Mises
Peak strain ϵ_0	1.8%
Damage law	linear
Ultimate strain ϵ_u	6.0%

For the mortar of the coating layer (30 mm thick), a concrete-damage plasticity material model is used ("Cdpm2" OOFEM material type); the main parameters are resumed in Table 4.3. It is observed that, due to the smeared-crack approach of the multi-layer model, the fracture energy necessitates to be fictitiously increased so to account for the tension stiffening effect between cracks. This adjustment allows the combined effect of the plaster and GFRP layers to macroscopically reproduce the typical trilinear tensile behaviour of the Composite Reinforced Mortar (CRM) material.

To clarify, in Fig. 4.3, it is reported the comparison between the experimental behaviour of CRM coupons subjected to direct tensile tests [9] and the numeric results obtained from the simulation, according to the multi-layer modelling (GFRP and mortar layer only). Clearly, the numeric model, being smear-cracked, do not allow the detection of the single cracks, nor the respective jagged stress-strain curve characterizing the post-cracking stage, but catches with satisfying approximation the typical trilinear behaviour of CRM, as well as the spreading of plasticization over the whole coupon length. Note also that the mortar tensile strength in the model is properly reduced, to fit adequately the mean behaviour of the post-cracking stage. Also the peak strain of the GFRP layer is properly reduced in respect the values considered in [1] (from 2% to 1.8%), so that the composite material "mortar coating + GFRP" fails in tension at the attainment of the actual GFRP peak stress.

For the compressive strength of the mortar, a very low, fictitious value was considered in the numeric simulations. In fact, experimental compression test on CRM strengthened masonry provided resistance values just slightly higher than of plain masonry, due to the debonding of the mortar coating. Since in the simplified, multi-layer numeric model this debonding is not considered (perfect bond between layers is assumed), a negligible value of mortar compressive strength was set.

Table 4.3 Main numerical parameters adopted for the mortar coating layer (for unspecified parameters, the OOFEM default values are used [5]).

Mortar layer	
OOFEM material type	<i>Cdpm2</i>
Young modulus E	14.4 GPa
Poisson modulus ν	0.25
Self-weight γ	20 kN/m ³
Comp. strength f_c	0.85 MPa
Tensile strength f_t	0.85 MPa
Dilation ψ	40°
Softening law	Bilinear
Hardening parameters b_h	0.002
h_p	0.0
Softening parameters w_f/h	0.035
a_{soft}	4
f_{t1}	0.45
w_{f1}/h	0.0045

Tensile behavior

Compressive behavior

Fig. 4.3 Schematization of 20-nodes multi-layer elements used in the OOFEM models.

4.3. In-plane behaviour of piers

4.3.1. *Geometry, boundary conditions and loads*

The numerical model to reproduce the CONSTRAIN tests carried out on masonry piers samples, subjected to in-plane cyclic loading is schematized in Fig. 4.4: red colour represents the steel parts of the testing apparatus, blue colour the RC beams, grey the masonry sample.

The solid elements of the lower row are fixed at the base, while the steel and the RC beams (below and above the masonry sample) are linked by means of vertical elastic springs aimed at stimulating the slight but not negligible vertical displacements actually monitored experimentally in those areas (already discussed in [1]). Differently, a perfect bond was assumed between the masonry pier and the RC beams. It is observed that, when simulating the CRM strengthened masonry samples, the multi-layer approach is assumed also for the RC beams, since in the experimental sample the CRM application prosecuted also over such beams.

To avoid rotations of the upper steel beam (coherently with the experimental setup), a master node is selected at the location of the horizontal actuator, and all other nodes at that height are constrained to have the same translations. To simply model connectors and diatones, axial rigid links were used to connect nodes on opposite faces of the wall, where the anchors were located.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is distributed across the top of the upper steel beam and then kept constant. Subsequently, a horizontal, in-plane load is applied at the actuator's height and varied to increase step-by-step the horizontal displacement of the control point (at the top of the pier sample).

Fig. 4.4 The OOFEM numeric model for the CONSTRAIN in-plane tests on piers

4.3.2. Numerical results and comparisons

The main numerical results are summarized with thick lines in the V_p - d_p graphs of Fig. 4.5, in comparison with the thin lines of the experiments. The applied horizontal load V_p (shear force) is plotted as function of the horizontal displacement of the top RC beam d_p .

Fig. 4.5 Numeric analyses of the CONSTRAIN in-plane tests on masonry piers: capacity curves, in comparison with the experimental results.

More detailed numerical-experimental comparisons are plotted in Fig. 4.6-Fig. 4.13:

- the V_p - d_p graphs;
- the V_p - d_{Vtot} graphs, being d_{Vtot} the global vertical displacements between the upper steel beam and the laboratory floor (positive displacements conventionally refer to elongations);
- the principal tensile strains evidencing the damage patterns at 20% reduction of peak load (just the sample and RC beam are represented), in comparison with the crack pattern surveyed at the back side of the experimental samples by means of a Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system.

Considering the coarseness of the numerical model, all the numerical curves generally show good agreement with the envelope of the cyclic experimental ones.

Also, the damage patterns well correspond with the failure modes observed in the CONSTRAIN experiments. Specifically, the unstrengthened samples fail due to diagonal cracking (with high tensile strains along the diagonal), while the strengthened samples exhibit mixed damage patterns, consistently with experimental findings. In particular, high tensile strains at opposite top-bottom extremities (damage related to the in-plane bending mechanism) are also observed.

For samples S-R2R-1 and S-B2R-1, strengthened on one side only, diagonal cracking remains the dominant failure mode, whereas samples strengthened on both sides and sample S-B1R-1 exhibit a combination of diagonal cracking and bending failure modes.

- Pier P-R2U

Fig. 4.6 Pier sample P-R2U: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-R2R-1

Fig. 4.7 Pier sample P-R2R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-R2R-2

Fig. 4.8 Pier sample P-R2R-2: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-B2U

Fig. 4.9 Pier sample P-B2U: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-B2R-1

Fig. 4.10 Pier sample P-B2R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-B2R-2

Fig. 4.11 Pier sample P-B2R-2: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-B1U

Fig. 4.12 Pier sample P-B1U: numerical – experimental comparisons.

- Pier P-B1R-1

Fig. 4.13 Pier sample P-B1R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons.

4.4. In-plane behaviour of spandrels

4.4.1. *Geometry, boundary conditions and loads*

The numerical model to reproduce the CONSTRAIN tests carried out on masonry spandrel samples, subjected to in-plane cyclic loading is schematized in Fig. 4.14: red colour represents the steel parts of the testing apparatus, blue colour the RC beams, grey the masonry sample, green the lintel or jack arch. To simply reproduce connectors and diatones, axial rigid links are introduced to join the nodes at the opposite wall faces, in correspondance of the anchors. The nodes in correspondance of the left lever fulcrum are pinned, while in those at the right lever fulcrum the horizontal translation is free.

To represent, in a very simplified way, the extreme weakness emerged in the contact area between the lintel (or the jack arch) and the overlaying masonry, a negligible Young modulus was assigned to the masonry layer of the mesh elements just above the lintel/jack arch (detected with orange contour in Fig. 4.14).

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the self-weights are applied and the axial pre-compression on the piers is introduced by means of four vertical nodal forces at top; subsequently, the vertical displacement at the external ends of the two lever beams is incremented monotonically, with same magnitude but opposite directions.

Fig. 4.14 The OOFEM numeric model for the CONSTRAIN in-plane tests on spandrels.

4.4.2. Numerical results and comparisons

The numerical V_S - d_S capacity curves are reported with thick lines in Fig. 4.15 in comparison with the thin lines of the experiments.

The shear load V_S is obtained from the vertical translation equilibrium of the external vertical forces acting on the left half (as well as right half) of the sample. The spandrel distortion d_S is calculated by using Eq. (4.1):

$$d_S = (\delta_{V,r} - \delta_{V,l}) \cdot \left(\frac{b_S}{2} + \frac{b_P}{2} \right) / \left(\frac{b_P}{2} \right) \quad (4.1)$$

where b_S and b_P are the spandrel and the pier widths, respectively and δ_V the vertical displacements in correspondance on the inner corners of the two masonry columns (right - r , and left - l).

Fig. 4.15 Summary of the numerical analyses of the CONSTRAIN in-plane tests on masonry spandrels: capacity curves, in comparison with the experimental results.

Two different numerical curves are plotted for S-R2R-2: a first simulation (dashed line) was carried out accordingly to the default load pattern of the experimental tests (i.e. the same rotation of the the two piers). A further simulation (solid lines) was performed by applying on the left pier half the rotation compared to right pier, in order to fictitiously replicate the actual boundary conditions observed in this sample during the experimental test (see [1] for further experimental details). This latter configuration reproduced more accurately the experimental outcomes; however, the former should be considered for consistent comparisons e.g. with S-R1R-1.

Two different numerical curves are plotted also for S-B2R-1 and S-B1R-1: in addition to the standard simulation (solid lines), a further simulation (dashed lines) was carried out by considering reducing values of the masonry material parameters for the spandrel. In fact, since it was observed that the standard simulations tended to overestimate the strength of these samples, it was realistically hypothesized that the pre-existing damage of the masonry (related to the previous test on the unreinforced configuration [1]) might have compromised its characteristics. The crack sealing intervention carried out before the application of the reinforcement likely only partially restored the original parameters. In the simulations, the Young's modulus, the compressive and tensile strengths, and the softening parameter wf/h reported in Table 4.1 were divided by 3. It is observed that this modification was not applied to the retrofitted samples made of stone masonry and having a timber lintel, which are likely less affected by pre-existing damage (as emerged from the pseudo-ductile behavior of S-R2U-1/2, compared to the brittle behavior exhibited experimentally by S-B2U and S-B1U).

More detailed numerical-experimental comparisons are plotted in Fig. 4.16-Fig. 4.13:

- the V_S-d_S graphs;
- the V_P-d_{Ht} graphs, being d_H the horizontal sliding of the right support;
- the $V_P-\epsilon_{top}$ and $V_P-\epsilon_{bot}$ graphs, being ϵ_{top} and ϵ_{bot} the equivalent horizontal strains at the top and the bottom of the spandrels, respectively
- the $V_P-\epsilon_{d1}$ and $V_P-\epsilon_{d2}$ graphs, being ϵ_{d1} and ϵ_{d2} the equivalent strains across the spandrels diagonals.
- the principal tensile strains evidencing the damage patterns at 20% reduction of peak load (just the spandrel area is represented), in comparison with the crack pattern surveyed at the front side of the experimental samples by means of a Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system.

It is observed that two different analyses were performed for the unstrengthened configurations: one simulating the unbounded condition of the lintel/jack arch with the overlying masonry (dashed line curves), the other (solid line curves) assuming perfect bond (i.e. no modifications in masonry properties in the above lintel/jack arch area).

For sample S-R2U, the perfect bond assumption was found to be the most consistent with the experimental behavior; conversely, for samples S-B2U and S-B1U, the unbounded condition fits better.

Considering the coarseness of the model, the numerical curves show good agreement with the envelope of the cyclic experimental ones. Also, the damage patterns generally reflect the failure modes observed in the CONSTRAIN experiments.

The failure of S-R2U is dominated by the in-plane bending mechanism. In S-B2U and S-B1U, also the activation of the diagonal cracking mechanism emerged, but the failure is induced by bending. For S-B2U, this is in contrast with the experiment, where diagonal cracking failure occurred.

The bending mechanism prevailed in the one-side retrofitted samples, even though in combination with an advanced diagonal cracking mechanism. Unsymmetrical bending failure occurred in S-R2R-2, under “modified boundary” conditions.

The pre-damage of the masonry seems to have a not negligible influence on the reinforced brick samples, consistently with the brittle behavior exhibited by the unreinforced configurations. Differently, the impact appears to be less pronounced in the stone samples, accordingly with the more ductile behavior observed in the unreinforced configurations.

- Spandrel S-R2U-1

Fig. 4.16 Spandrel sample S-R2U-1: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-R2U-2

Fig. 4.17 Spandrel sample S-R2U-2: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-R2R-1

Fig. 4.18 Spandrel sample S-R2R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-R2R-1

Fig. 4.19 Spandrel sample S-R2R-2: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-B2U

Fig. 4.20 Spandrel sample S-B2U: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-B2R-1

Fig. 4.21 Spandrel sample S-B2R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-B1U

Fig. 4.22 Spandrel sample S-B1U: numerical – experimental comparisons

- Spandrel S-B1R-1

Fig. 4.23 Spandrel sample S-B1R-1: numerical – experimental comparisons

5. Direct comparisons and remarks

The results from the ABAQUS and OOFEM numerical simulations are compared and the differences analysed.

5.1. In-plane behaviour of piers

- Pier P-R2U

Fig. 5.1 Direct comparison for pier sample P-R2U.

Both models capture diagonal shear damage and failure adequately. ABAQUS model shows steeper drop of pushover curve immediately after maximum resistance due to steeper tension softening material definition compared to smoother OOFEM response where plateau after tensile strength was used. Nevertheless, both models accurately predict maximum resistance, and both can be considered good. Overall assessment is that the results of both models are reasonably aligned and that both give sufficiently good results. OOFEM model predicts vertical displacements slightly better, due to modified material law in compression, lack of contact elements at the top and bottom, and slightly different effect of springs between the RC beams and steel supports.

- Pier P-R2R-1

Fig. 5.2 Direct comparison for pier sample P-R2R-1.

Both models capture diagonal shear with some flexural damage in the corners adequately. ABAQUS damage prediction shows steeper diagonal crack angle due to top and bottom separation contact definition between masonry and RC beams. The effect of separation contacts is also a more gradual decrease of resistance after peak resistance. Both models predict maximum resistance accurately. The shrinkage of the sides of the piers was better captured by the OOFEM. Overall, both simulations give reasonable results.

- Pier P-R2R-2

Fig. 5.3 Direct comparison for pier sample P-R2R-2.

Both models simulate diagonal shear cracking with substantial flexural damage in the corners. This response is the same as was observed in the experiments. However, ABAQUS predicts steeper diagonal crack and a more gradual decrease of resistance due to top and bottom separation contact between masonry and RC beams.

Both models predict maximum resistance accurately. However, the vertical shrinkage at the sides of the wall of both simulations is slightly different, and both are slightly different from the experiment. Nevertheless, both simulations sufficiently reproduce experimental results.

- Pier P-B2U

Fig. 5.4 Direct comparison for pier sample P-B2U.

Both models capture diagonal shear damage adequately. ABAQUS model shows steeper drop of pushover curve after maximum resistance due to steeper tension softening material definition compared to smoother OOFEM. Both models predict maximum resistance with accuracy. OOFEM model also shows a good match of vertical displacements.

- Pier P-B2R-1

Fig. 5.5 Direct comparison for pier sample P-B2R-1.

Simulations of both models predict diagonal shear with flexural damage at the corners, which is consistent with the tests. More gradual decrease of resistance in ABAQUS pushover curve is due to lower stiffness because of separation between masonry and RC beams. Both models slightly underpredict maximum resistance. The difference in both models most likely occurs because of strengthening of masonry due to connection of both leaves due to connectors, which was not directly taken into account in the models. OOFEM model also shows good match of vertical displacements.

- Pier P-B2R-2

Fig. 5.6 Direct comparison for pier sample P-B2R-2.

The results of both simulations adequately reproduce diagonal shear with extensive flexural damage in the corners. In this case, both models predict steep diagonal crack, which is in alignment with the experimental test. More gradual decrease of resistance in ABAQUS's pushover curve, due to definition of separation contacts between masonry and RC beams. Both models predict maximum resistance accurately. OOFEM model also shows accurate match of vertical displacements.

- Pier P-B1U

Fig. 5.7 Direct comparison for pier sample P-B1U.

The diagonal shear damage is adequately predicted by both numerical simulations, and the damage is aligned with the experimentally observed one. The pushover curves of both models are reasonable. The OOFEM model better simulates initial stiffness, but both models struggle with post peak response. The maximum resistance is predicted accurately in both models. The OOFEM model also shows good alignment of vertical displacements with the tests.

- Pier P-B1R-1

Fig. 5.8 Direct comparison for Pier sample P-B1R-1.

Both models predict diagonal shear with concentrated flexural damage in the corners, which is aligned with the observations from the tests. The peak resistance is underestimated by both simulations, but not by much. The post peak response seems slightly better in the ABAQUS simulation, but the vertical displacements are better simulated by the OOFEM.

5.2. In-plane behaviour of spandrels

- Spandrel S-R2U

Fig. 5.9 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-R2U.

In case of spandrels, ABAQUS simulations consistently show higher maximum resistance due to assumed higher tensile strength. On the other hand, OOFEM model, which uses lower tensile strength with a plateau in tension, predicts maximum resistance more accordingly (bounded lintel condition). Both models are susceptible to bending damage. Note that both homogeneous models cannot account directly for the interlocking effect, which particularly affects the behavior of unreinforced spandrels without ties. Shear damage is therefore somewhat limited and both simulations struggle with diagonal strains and horizontal strains.

- Spandrel S-R2R-1

ABAQUS model (by UL FGG)

OOFEM (by DIA - UNITS)

Fig. 5.10 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-R2R-1.

Both models fail to simulate long hardening that was observed in the test. However, the maximum resistance is predicted with satisfactory precision. ABAQUS model shows steeper degradation after maximum resistance, whereas OOFEM model shows longer hardening phase with more gradual degradation. This is due to tensile stress-strain diagram of masonry, where ABAQUS models have higher uncracked strength with steeper softening law and OOFEM models have lower strength with plateau afterwards.

Diagonal strains in the spandrel are predicted better in OOFEM, but both simulations predict large compressive strains, that were not recorded at all. The prediction of horizontal strains is quite good for both models.

- Spandrel S-R2R-2

Fig. 5.11 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-R2R-2.

OOFEM model gives a good pushover curve prediction, whereas ABAQUS model shows slight overestimation of maximum resistance and too high resistance in post peak phase. Both models are able to simulate longer hardening phase due to boundary conditions in that particular case, where left pier was not connected properly to RC beam due to failing of apparatus when simulating vertical pressure. Both models correctly predict bending damage, but ABAQUS struggles with diagonal and horizontal strains, while OOFEM, on the other hand, simulates them relatively well. However, OOFEM predicts the horizontal sliding in the opposite direction, while ABAQUS matches the experimental direction, although it overestimates the magnitude of the displacements.

- Spandrel S-B2U

ABAQUS model (by UL FGG)

OOFEM (by DIA - UNITS)

Fig. 5.12 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-B2U.

OOFEM model (unbounded jack arch condition) shows quite precise response of spandrel specimen when comparing pushover curve, whereas ABAQUS model shows overestimation of ductility, due to high ultimate strain used for the material definition. Both models are able to simulate relatively brittle failure. Both models show predominantly bending damage, and OOFEM predicts also small levels of shear damage. The horizontal sliding of the right support and horizontal strains are modelled quite well by both programs, while diagonal strains show evident discrepancies with the test.

- Spandrel S-B2R-1

ABAQUS model (by UL FGG)

OOFEM (by DIA - UNITS)

Fig. 5.13 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-B2R-1.

OOFEM simulation (reduced masonry parameter condition) gives quite good prediction of spandrel specimen response in terms of the pushover curve, whereas the ABAQUS simulation overestimates the ductility due to high ultimate strain in the tensile material response. Both models give good maximum resistance approximations and show bending and shear damage. The horizontal sliding of the right support is better simulated in OOFEM, and the horizontal strains are approximately simulated by ABAQUS and OOFEM. OOFEM diagonal tensile strains are in agreement with the experiments, but both simulations predict large compressive strains, that did not emerge in the experimental test. The prediction of horizontal strains is quite good for both models.

- Spandrel S-B1U

ABAQUS model (by UL FGG)

OOFEM (by DIA - UNITS)

Fig. 5.14 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-B1U.

The pushover curve is predicted quite well by the ABAQUS model, however even this simulation fails to simulate ductility due to the high ultimate strain used in the material constitutive law. OOFEM model (unbounded jack arch condition) is capable to approximately reproduce the brittle failure mode. Both models show good maximum resistance approximation and both show predominantly bending damage, with OOFEM model predicting also light a shear damage. The simulation of the movement of the right support is poor for ABAQUS model, and also the diagonal stains are not aligned with experiments. The horizontal strains are quite good predicted by OOFEM.

- Spandrel S-B1R-1

ABAQUS model (by UL FGG)

OOFEM (by DIA - UNITS)

Fig. 5.15 Direct comparison for spandrel sample S-B1R-1.

Both models somewhat overestimate of resistance when taken into account the original masonry parameters. It was suspected that the repair of cracked masonry was not completely satisfactory, which reduced the strength of the masonry material. OOFEM simulation was performed also with reduced masonry material parameters, and gives good alignment with the tests. Also the horizontal sliding and horizontal strains are simulated with adequate alignment with tests, whereas diagonal strain predictions detect excessive compressive phenomena, not observed experimentally.

Both models show the same damage pattern – predominantly bending with light shear damage.

5.3. Final remarks

The numerical simulations generally succeeded in reproducing the capacity curves, the type and extent of damage, and other quantities measured in the experiments (such as the heel uplift of the piers and the horizontal movement of spandrel supports). The fairly good agreement between the simulations and the experiments serves to validate the developed numerical models.

The verification of the numerical simulations was performed by comparing the results from two different software programs using similar models. Here too, the similarity between the results of both programs was sufficient to confirm the modelling approach and reduce the likelihood of errors.

Following successful validation and verification, the models can now be used for their intended purpose: simulating structural components that have not been experimentally tested, thereby further enhancing the usefulness of CONSTRAIN strengthening.

Acknowledgments

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PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.3

Risultati di analisi di casi studio di elementi strutturali e di interi edifici

NOVEMBRE 2025

Poročilo 1.3

Rezultati analiz konstrukcijskih elementov in stavb

NOVEMBER 2025

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PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.3 Results of case studies analysis of structural elements and entire buildings

NOVEMBRE 2025

Authors: Gattesco N.⁽¹⁾, Boem I.⁽¹⁾, Rizzi E.⁽¹⁾, Gams M.⁽²⁾, Kirn D.⁽²⁾, Krtinić N.⁽²⁾

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Report 1.3

Results of case studies analysis of structural elements and entire buildings

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1. Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 1.3 of the PRO-SIS project, titled “Case study analysis of structural elements and entire buildings to be used for the calibration of analytical models and intermediate-level numerical models”.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extended experimental campaign. The developed strengthening method is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced by fiber-based composite materials. The main advantage of the developed system is that it can be applied only on one side of the wall, which makes it much more convenient for residents and businesses. Due to construction works only on the outside of the building, people and their belongings don't have to be relocated, and business activity doesn't have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the inside (or outside, when the inside side application is preferred). The developed strengthening method stands out because of its proven effectiveness by tests on structural components and on full scale pilot building.

The aim of the “PRO-SIS” project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for the design and application of these strategies. For this purpose, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated on the experimental results of “CONSTRAIN”. The results provide the designers with robust strategies for the design of the proposed systems, and instructions for design in commonly used commercial programs for design of structures.

In the previous report “REPORT 1.1: Analytic model for dimensioning” [1] the “CONSTRAIN” experimental results were gathered and critically reviewed and a first calibration of analytical-mechanical models capable to describe the experimental behaviour was presented.

Then, in “REPORT 1.2: Numerical models for simulating the behaviour of reinforced elements/buildings” [2], advanced numerical models were developed by using two different finite element software (ABAQUS and OOFEM) and were used to simulate the behaviour of the CONSTRAIN experimental samples (masonry piers and spandrels) strengthened with Composite Reinforced Mortar (CRM). The ABAQUS models were developed by the University of Ljubljana (UL FGG), while the OOFEM models by the University of Trieste (DIA – UNITS).

In this REPORT 1.3, the advanced numerical models, previously developed and validated, are used for the simulation of case studies of increasing complexity, ranging from single structural elements to entire buildings. Both unreinforced and CRM strengthened masonry configurations are analysed and compared. The results of the analyses provide a valuable reference for designers and researchers and allow for the calibration of more simplified numerical models in the next project steps.

Coherently with the approach applied in [2], once the characteristics of the various configurations to be analyzed were agreed upon, the two partners autonomously carried out the simulations and compared the results at the end.

The report starts describing the main characteristics of the defined case studies. Then, there are the two main sections of the report, one for each type modelling developed. For each section, the first part briefly summarizes the modelling approach, then the numeric results are presented and analyzed. At the end, a final section provides the overall final remarks on the obtained results.

2. Benchmark examples

The main geometrical and mechanical characteristics of the analysed configurations are described in the following. The modelling assumptions are listed, and the naming conventions adopted for the examples is explained.

2.1. Pier elements

The benchmark pier element is made of single leaf solid brick masonry (type B1, as calibrated in [2]), with main dimensions 1250x1250x250 mm³ (width x height x thickness). It is subjected to a constant axial stress of 0.5 MPa applied at the top (the masonry self-weight is neglected in all models). The rotation is constrained at both the base and the top and the horizontal displacement is gradually increased at the top (i.e., shear-type scheme).

Starting from this benchmark, different variations are considered and analysed:

- material: type R2, as calibrated in [2] (rubble stone masonry, 350 mm thick);
- geometry: width 850 mm, 2250 mm and 3350 mm.
- axial stress: 0.3 MPa;
- boundary conditions: the rotation is released at the top (i.e. cantilever scheme).

The models are distinguished by a label indicating the type of structural element (P for “pier”), the masonry (B1 for single leaf brick masonry or R2 for double leaf rubble stone masonry), the configuration (U, R1 and R2 for unstrengthened, strengthened with CRM at one or both sides, respectively). Then, there is the varying geometry parameter (the width: 1250, 2250, 3350 or 850 mm), the axial stress level (05 or 03, for 0.5 or 0.3 MPa) and the static scheme (either shear-type or cantilever).

2.2. Spandrel elements

The benchmark spandrel element is made of single leaf masonry (type B1), with main dimensions 1200x1200x250 mm³ (width x height x thickness) and having in addition a masonry jack arch of 250 mm height. The reference configuration consists in reproducing a shear-type scheme for the spandrel (i.e. left pier fixed at the base, right pier moving vertically, with rotations avoided at the base). Unstrengthened (U) and CRM strengthened configurations at one and both sides (R1 and R2) are analysed and compared.

Starting from this benchmark, different variations are considered:

- geometry: spandrel height 1500 mm and 800 mm;
- material: type R2, as calibrated in [2] (rubble stone masonry, 350 mm thick);
- lintel: presence of a 150 mm thick wooden lintel inserted for 150 mm at both ends;
- presence of a horizontal steel tie at the mid height of the spandrel (tensile resistance 100 kN);

- boundary conditions/loading scheme: cantilever beam scheme (i.e. release of the in-plane rotation at the base of the right pier);
- boundary conditions/loading scheme: identical rotations at the base of the piers are applied.

The models are distinguished by a label indicating the type of structural element (S for “spandrel”), the masonry (B1 or R2), the configuration (U, R1 and R2 for unstrengthened, strengthened with CRM at one or both sides, respectively). Then, there is the varying geometry parameter (the height: 1000, 1500 and 800 mm). Label “ltl” refers to wooden lintel; the absence/presence of the horizontal tie is indicated with label “t0” or “t1”, respectively. Label “ct” indicates the released rotation at the right pier, label “rot” identical rotations applied at the base. The capacity curves of the benchmark spandrel are reported in dashed lines in the other graphs, for comparison.

2.3. Single-story walls

The benchmark single-story wall is made of single leaf masonry (type B1), with main dimensions 5600x3850x250 mm³ (width x height x thickness). It has two symmetric windows 1200x1400 mm² at a distance of 1150 mm from lateral ends and 1000 mm from the floor (Fig. 2.1). The spandrels have a gross height of 1450 mm, including also a masonry jack arch of 250 mm height. A horizontal steel tie at the mid height of the spandrel (tensile resistance 100 kN) is introduced.

Fig. 2.1 Main geometric features of the single storey wall.

The masonry self-weight is considered; in addition, the wall is subjected to a constant vertical load at the top. The different levels of axial stress are analysed, considering different values of constant vertical load at the top:

- 14.3 kN/m (additional compressive stress on the piers ~0.1 MPa);
- 42.9 kN/m (additional compressive stress on the piers ~0.3 MPa);
- 71.5 kN/m (additional compressive stress on the piers ~0.5 MPa).

Unstrengthened (U) and CRM strengthened configurations at one and both sides (R1 and R2) are analysed and compared.

The models are distinguished by a label indicating the type of structure (SW for “Single storey Wall”), the masonry type (B1), the presence of the horizontal tie (t1), the configuration (U, R1

and R2 for unstrengthened, strengthened with CRM at one or both sides, respectively) and the axial stress level (01, 03 and 05).

2.4. Two-story walls

Two benchmark examples are considered for the two-story walls configurations. They are both made of single leaf masonry (type B1) and have main dimensions $5750 \times 6000 \times 250$ mm³ (width x height x thickness). One (configuration "a" - Fig. 2.2a) is symmetric and has two aligned identical windows at each story (dimensions 1200×1400 mm²). The other (configuration "b" -- Fig. 2.2b) has a window and a door (1200×2100 mm²) at the ground floor, and a single window at the first floor (aligned with that at the ground floor). All the openings include a masonry jack arch of 250 mm height. A horizontal steel tie at the mid height of the spandrels (tensile resistance 100 kN) is also introduced.

Fig. 2.2 Main geometric features of the two-storey walls: (a) TWA and (b) TWb.

The masonry self-weight is considered; in addition, the wall is subjected to a constant vertical load at the top, so that the additional compressive stress on the piers of the first floor corresponds approximately to 0.3 MPa. In particular, the additional vertical load applied is 42.9 kN/m for the configuration "a", and 59.4 kN/m for the configuration "b".

Unstrengthened (U) and CRM strengthened configurations at one and both sides (R1 and R2) are analysed and compared.

The models are distinguished by a label indicating the type of structure and configuration (TWA or TWb(+)/ TWb(-), for "Two-storey Wall" with configuration "a" or "b", with "b" loaded in both positive and negative direction), the masonry type (B1), the presence of the horizontal tie (t1), the configuration (U, R1 and R2 for unstrengthened, strengthened with CRM at one or both sides, respectively) and the mean axial at the first floor (03).

2.5. Pilot building

The benchmark building herein considered is a two storey building made of single leaf masonry (type B1), with main plan dimensions 5750x4350 mm² and a height of 6000 mm. It features four bearing walls (Fig. 2.3), an intermediate floor of 70 kN and a gabled timber roof of 50 kN (main direction E-W). All the openings include a masonry jack arch of 250 mm height. Horizontal steel ties (tensile resistance 100 kN), oriented in both the N-S and E-W directions are located just below the intermediate floor and roof level.

Unstrengthened (U) masonry and masonry strengthened with CRM applied at the outer surface (R1) are analysed and compared.

The models are distinguished by a label indicating the type of structure (GB is for “Global building”), the masonry type (B1) and the configuration (U and R1).

Fig. 2.3 Main geometric features of the building.

3. Modelling with ABAQUS (by UL-FGG)

3.1. Main features

The numerical models represent the actual geometry and boundary conditions of the samples. An example of a pier and a spandrel is shown in Fig. 3.1. In the model, there are separate meshes for finite elements representing masonry, mortar coating and glass fibre mesh, and each material has its own nonlinear material model.

Fig. 3.1 Finite element mesh for piers (a) and for spandrels (b) with boundary conditions and loads.

Both the masonry and the mortar coating were modelled as a continuum using 3D solid linear brick elements (C3D8R) with eight nodes and reduced integration, ensuring computational efficiency and stability in explicit dynamic simulations. The glass fibre mesh, on the other hand, was represented using T3D2 elements, 2-node linear 3D truss elements, which was incorporated into the models as a separate component with lengths and positions taken from the tested pier and spandrels.

The material model for masonry and mortar was the well-known Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model, which is reliable and proven for analysis of brittle materials such as masonry and concrete. The material parameters were painstakingly determined from tests on materials (compression tests) and by calibration with tests results of piers and spandrels (see PRO-SIS Report 1.2 [2]). The material model for GFRP was a perfectly brittle elastic model. The rupture stress was obtained from the measured rupture force of each type of fibre (weft or warped).

Explicit dynamic analyses were used for simulations. The advantages of such analysis for modelling brittle response are well known (stability, less convergence issues). The minimum and maximum time increment in the analyses were 0.000001 s and 0.001 s, respectively, depending on the type of simulation. The size of the time increments was determined by a dedicated parametric analysis to find the optimal balance between accuracy and computation time. To speed up the analyses, mass scaling was used. Mass was scaled by a factor that

produced the target time increment of 0.001 s for pilot building analyses and 0.0001-0.00008 s for other simulations, and dedicated analyses confirmed that the effect of mass scaling on accuracy was negligible.

A detailed description of the numerical models can be found in PRO-SIS Report 1.2 [2].

3.2. Parametric analysis on pier elements

The response of walls is herein represented by a pushover force-displacement response curve, and a plot of the logarithmic elastic strains. The concentrations of strains indicate locations of expected damage. The scale on all strain plots in Section 3 of this report is the same and is shown in Fig. 3.2.

Fig. 3.2 The scale of strain plots in the entire report.

The effects first analysed on 1250 mm long piers (Fig. 3.3). As the results show, adding layers of coating increases strength, displacement capacity and ductility of piers. Furthermore, the failure mechanism also changes. In the case of unstrengthened pier, the failure is in shear. Pier strengthened on one side exhibits shear failure, but with clear elements of bending response in the form of horizontal damage at the corners. Finally, the pier strengthened on both sides responds strongly in bending.

In the second stage, the effect of strengthening is analysed on slender piers with a length of 850 mm (Fig. 3.4) and squat piers with a length of 2250 mm (Fig. 3.5) and 3350 mm (Fig. 3.6). As before, the effect of strengthening on pushover force-displacement response curves is clear. Increasing the amount of coating increases strength, displacement capacity and ductility of piers. For slender walls the response mechanism changes from shear to bending due to coating, whereas for squat walls with length of 2250 mm and more, the response mechanism remains shear regardless of amount of coating.

The effect of increasing the length of the piers is that piers get substantially stronger. The effect on ductility and displacement capacity, on the other hand, is relatively small.

Fig. 3.3 The effect of strengthening on 1250 mm long piers. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right.

Fig. 3.4 The effect of strengthening on 850 mm long piers. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right. The grey pushover curves correspond to 1250 mm long walls.

Fig. 3.5 The effect of strengthening on 2250 mm long piers. Pushover curves force-displacement are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right. The grey pushover curves correspond to 1250 mm long walls.

Fig. 3.6 The effect of strengthening on 3350 mm long piers. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right. The grey pushover curves correspond to 1250 mm long walls.

The effect of vertical stress on the wall is analysed next by changing the vertical stress from the original 0.5 to 0.3 MPa. The responses of both walls are compared in Fig. 3.7, where grey curves denote response of highly stressed piers, and coloured curves denote response of lightly stressed piers. Reducing the vertical stress clearly reduces strength of the walls in case of both, unstrengthened and strengthened configurations, but the effect on the displacement capacity and ductility appears to be relatively small. Although the curves do not change much due to the reduced vertical load, the response mechanism becomes much more bending like, with a lot of strain concentrations in the corners (bottom left and top right corner in Fig. 3.7).

Fig. 3.7 Response of wall with smaller vertical stress. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right. The grey pushover curves correspond to the wall with 0.5 MPa vertical stress.

Fig. 3.8 shows the response of 1250 mm long walls if top rotation is freed (cantilever type of boundary conditions). Unstrengthened pier and pier strengthened on only one side fail in pure bending, and the resistance of such walls under cantilever boundary conditions is drastically lower.

Fig. 3.8 Response of brick piers under cantilever boundary conditions. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations on the right. The grey curves correspond to the wall with clamped boundary conditions.

The response of unstrengthened *stone* masonry under reduced vertical stress and under cantilever boundary conditions is shown Fig. 3.9. Simulations indicate that the principal effect of reduced vertical stress is the reduction of shear resistance. Changing the boundary conditions, on the other hand, drastically changes the response. The cantilever wall exhibits a large reduction of stiffness and strength compared to the clamped one. Additionally, the failure mechanism changes from shear to bending.

Fig. 3.9 Response of stone piers with smaller vertical stress and cantilever boundary conditions. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and damage on the right.

The effect of geometry on seismic response of stone masonry piers is analysed in Fig. 3.10. Increasing the length of the walls increases strength of the walls and displacement at peak strength. The response mechanism in all cases is shear.

Fig. 3.10 Effect of geometry on the response on unstrengthened stone masonry piers. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown at the top and strain concentrations at the bottom. The grey curves correspond to the (thinner) single wythe brick walls.

3.3. Parametric analysis on spandrel elements

The results shown in Fig. 3.11 compare the response of unstrengthened 1200 mm tall spandrel with that of spandrels with coating on one and both sides. The strength, displacement capacity and ductility strongly increase with coating. The type of damage also changes. The unstrengthened spandrel exhibits only bending damage, evident from two vertical cracks, whereas in the strengthened spandrels, there is diagonal damage, which indicates also shear response. The shear damage is smeared over a large surface, indicating a large area for potential energy dissipation, which is a desired property.

Fig. 3.11 Effect of coating on the response on brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right.

The effect of coating on spandrels with different geometries shows the same trend, as can be observed on Fig. 3.12 and Fig. 3.13. Increasing the height of the spandrel also increasing the strength of the spandrel.

The short spandrel with 800 mm height, shown in Fig. 3.12 exhibits lower properties than the benchmark 1200 mm tall spandrel. Furthermore, the response mechanism is much more heavily inclined towards bending, and the damage is much more concentrated in the vertical cracks. This reduces energy dissipation capacity, which is evident from the much more brittle response (faster strength degradation) in the force-displacement response in the graph in Fig. 3.12.

The tallest spandrel, with a height of 1500 mm is the strongest as expected. However, the response mechanism is very similar to the response of the benchmark spandrel. Therefore the response curves (Fig. 3.13), are qualitatively very similar with similar displacement capacity and energy dissipation characteristics.

Fig. 3.12 The response of 800 mm tall spandrels with different amount of strengthening. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey curves on the graph show the response of 1200 mm tall spandrels.

Fig. 3.13 Effect of coating on the response on brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey curves on the graph show the response of 1200 mm tall spandrels.

The effect of steel rod at the middle of the spandrel (Fig. 3.14), which is often installed during seismic strengthening, is analysed next. The effect is shown for 1200 mm, 800 mm and 1500 mm tall spandrels in Fig. 3.15, Fig. 3.16 and Fig. 3.17, respectively. The effect of the steel rod is that the response in terms of strength, displacement capacity, energy dissipation capacity and ductility increases. The increase is the biggest for 800 mm tall piers. The high strains appear to be smeared across a larger area in case steel rod is used, because the effect of the rod is similar to the effect of the compressive force in piers – compression generally improves the response, unless there is too much of it. In that case, the walls become brittle. However, in spandrels the effects of compression are only positive because axial stress in masonry is still quite low. The effect of more distributed strains is also positive, because it indicates damage over a larger surface area, which results in increased capacity of the wall to dissipate energy.

Fig. 3.14 Location of steel rod (red line).

Fig. 3.15 Effect of steel rod on the response on brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey curves on the graph show the response of a spandrel without the rod.

Fig. 3.16 Effect of steel rod on the response on 800 mm tall brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey curves on the graph show the response of a spandrel without the rod.

Fig. 3.17 Effect of steel rod on the response on 1500 mm tall brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey curves on the graph show the response of a spandrel without the rod.

The last analysis shows the effect of vertical compression in piers on the response of spandrels. The results are shown in Fig. 3.18. Reducing the stress from 0.5 MPa to 0.3 MPa only has a negligible effect on the response. It should be noted that the present continuum model is not the most suitable for such analysis, because the main effect of compression in piers is to increase friction in vertical bending cracks. In any case, the effect of the vertical stress in the piers is expected to be low, just perhaps not as low as the results in Fig. 3.18 indicate.

Fig. 3.18 Effect of compressive stress in piers on the response on brick masonry spandrels. Pushover force-displacement curve is shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right.

3.4. Parametric analysis on single-story walls

The geometry and boundary conditions of the numerical model to simulate single-story walls are shown in Fig. 4.10. All solid elements are of “masonry” type. Bottom plane is completely restrained (displacements u_x , u_y , u_z). Masonry jack arches are connected to masonry via friction contact with friction coefficient of 0.5.

The analysis is divided into two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement at the top is gradually increased. The horizontal displacement is imposed over the whole top plane.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.11, along with the wall damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the total horizontal load varying the horizontal displacement at the top.

Fig. 3.19 Numerical model for parametric analyses on single storey wall.

The results show clear correlation between vertical load and failure mechanism. Walls under low vertical load experience bending failure whereas walls under high vertical load tend to fail in shear failure. With increasing amount of strengthening the response becomes more inclined towards bending.

Fig. 3.20 Numerical parametric analyses on a single storey wall: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of axial stress level.

3.5. Parametric analysis of two-story walls

The main features of the numerical model to simulate two-story walls are summarized in Fig. 4.10. All solid elements are of “masonry” type. All displacement in the bottom plane are restrained (u_x , u_y , u_z). Masonry jack arches are connected to masonry via friction contact with friction coefficient of 0.5.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement at the top and at the intermediate floor (at a height of 3 m) is gradually increased. It is imposed via rigid body that rotates in accordance to wall's stiffness. Displacement is controlled in the middle of the rigid body.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.11, along with the wall damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the total horizontal load varying the horizontal displacement at the top.

Fig. 3.21 Numerical model for parametric analyses on two-storey wall.

In both configurations of unstrengthened samples, the response of two storey walls can be described as a combination of shear and bending mechanisms in both piers and spandrels. With higher amount of strengthening, the damage localizes more at the 1st floor and becomes more inclined towards bending failure. The direction of displacement in unsymmetric walls has an effect on damage formation (shear/bending) but not on maximum resistance.

Fig. 3.22 Numerical parametric analyses on the two storey walls: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the different wall configurations.

3.6. Parametric analysis on buildings

The benchmark building considered in this section is a two-storey building made of double leaf stone masonry (type R2), strengthened on one side (Fig. 3.23). Because the building was tested within the CONSTRAIN project, the actual response is known. The purpose of the parametric analysis is to investigate the effect of strengthening on both sides and the effect of strengthening on a building that is made of bricks (B1). These two scenarios were not tested within the CONSTRAIN project.

In the brick model, there are 250 mm high masonry jack arches above doors and windows. In the stone masonry building, the lintels are wooden.

Fig. 3.23 View of the ABAQUS model of the pilot building with loads and boundary conditions.

In the first step, the response of the numerical model is compared to the experiment. The comparison is shown in Fig. 3.24. The response of the structure during the experiment is shown by two green curves, which indicate displacements at the left and right of the structure at first floor. The numerical results are shown by a black line, which is averaged for both sides. The alignment between the experimental tests and numerical results serve as further validation of the numerical model.

Fig. 3.24 Comparison of pushover force-displacement curves of experiment and numerical model: unstrengthened sample U (a) and strengthened on one side R1 (b).

In the first parametric analysis, the stone masonry pilot building is numerically analysed for cases when it is unstrengthened (U) and when it is strengthened the outer surface (R1) and both surfaces (R2). The case when the coating is not anchored into the foundation is considered first. The results are shown in (Fig. 3.25). It should be noted that such application is not correct, and its purpose is to show how much worse it is compared to the correct application. Despite the lack of anchoring, the strengthening substantially improves the response, as one-sided coating substantially increases strength, displacement capacity and ductility. Two-sided coating increases these characteristics even further.

Fig. 3.25 Effect of strengthening on the response of stone masonry pilot building. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right.

In the previous model, the building was not anchored into the ground. If CONSTRAINT strengthening is applied properly, the fibres are anchored into the foundations and prevent uplift. Such a case is shown in Fig. 3.26, and exhibits a much-improved response. In case of single-sided strengthening, the resistance increases by about 20 % (from about 500 kN to about 600 kN). In case of two-sided strengthening, the effect is even larger. The increase in strength

is about 30 % (from about 650 kN to about 850 kN). The conclusion is that it is vital to anchor the coating into the foundation and provide continuity of the GFRP mesh everywhere.

Fig. 3.26 Effect of strengthening on the response of stone masonry pilot building. Pushover force-displacement curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey lines show the response of a model not anchored into the ground.

Finally, the material of the pilot building is changed to single leaf brick type (B1) of masonry (the thickness of the walls remains the same). Such a structure has better material properties and better seismic response with much higher strength and similar displacement capacity and ductility, as can be seen in Fig. 3.27.

Fig. 3.27 Effect of strengthening on the response of brick masonry pilot building. Pushover curves are shown on the left and strain concentrations at the right. Grey lines show the response of a stone masonry building.

4. Modelling with OOFEM (by DIA – UNITS)

4.1. Main features

The main features of the advanced numerical model developed by using OOFEM are herein briefly described. Detailed description of the model and material characteristics can be found in PRO-SIS Report 1.2 [2].

The OOFEM models are based on 20-node brick elements with dimensions of $167 \times 167 \times T$ mm³, where T represents the overall wall thickness. The elements feature layered cross sections, with layers arranged through the thickness, so to represent the original masonry, the fiber-based reinforcement, and the mortar coating. Nonlinear static analyses, accounting for material nonlinearities, are performed under displacement control. The materials (Table 4.1) are considered as homogeneous and isotropic (concrete-damage plasticity material model for both the masonry and the mortar coating, to account both cracking and crushing, and an isotropic damage model to the fiber-based reinforcement layer, to account for tensile failure).

Table 4.1 Main numerical parameters adopted for the OOFEM numerical simulations

	B1 masonry	Mortar	
Material type	<i>Cdpm2</i>	<i>Cdpm2</i>	
Secant Young's modulus E	1.64 GPa	14.4 GPa	
Initial Young's modulus E_{init}	4.92 GPa	14.4 GPa	
Poisson modulus n	0.45	0.25	
Self-weight γ	18 kN/m ³	20 kN/m ³	
Comp. strength f_c	3.84 MPa	0.85 MPa	
Tensile strength f_t	0.162 MPa	0.85 MPa	
Softening law	Linear	Bilinear	
Hardening parameters	b_h	0.015	0.002
	h_p	0.0	0.0
	k_{init}	0.15	0.10
Softening parameters	w_f/h	0.004	0.035
	a_{soft}	8.0	4
	f_{t1}	-	0.45
	w_{f1}/h	-	0.0045

	GFRP
Material type	<i>ldm1</i>
Young's modulus E	3.81 GPa
Poisson modulus n	0.01
Comp. strength f_c	0.0
Equiv. strain type	mod.Mises
Peak strain ε_0	1.8%
Damage law	linear
Ultimate strain ε_u	6.0%

4.2. Parametric analysis on pier elements

The main features of the numerical model to investigate on pier elements are summarized in Fig. 4.1. The model consists of a "I"-shaped wall portion, as if it is extracted from the windowed wall of a building, and it is composed of a central pier (1250x1250 mm²) and upper and bottom bands (2000x700 mm²). The perimetral solid elements of the bands are assumed rigid; the other solid elements are of "masonry" type.

The solid elements of the lower row are pinned at the base. To reproduce the shear-type scheme, both the vertical load and the increasing horizontal in-plane displacement are applied on the node at the top left corner of the model (Master node). Both the translations and rotations of the Master node, along the out-of-plane direction, are avoided and all other nodes at the top (Slave nodes) are constrained to have the same displacements of the Master node. Differently, to reproduce the cantilever beam scheme, the increasing horizontal displacement is applied on the node at the top left corner, while the vertical load was equally distributed among all the nodes at the top. The translations along the out-of-plane direction are avoided in all the top nodes.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement is gradually increased.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.2 and Fig. 4.3, along with the panel damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode.

The capacity curves represent the trend of the horizontal load varying the net pier displacement (difference between the horizontal displacements at top and bottom of the pier, excluding upper and lower bands.). The capacity curves of the benchmark pier are reported in dashed lines in the other graphs, for comparison

Fig. 4.1 Numerical model for parametric analyses on pier elements.

All the unstrengthened piers with shear-type scheme fail in diagonal shear; the cantilever beam scheme turns the failure in flexural mode.

In the benchmark pier (P-B1-Rx_1250_05_st), the failure of the CRM strengthened samples is still dominated by diagonal shear, although there is also the activation of the flexural mechanism (more pronounced in R2 than R1).

As the axial force decreases (P-B1-Rx_1250_03_st), the resistances reduce and the displacement capacities increase; the collapse mechanism is still dominated by diagonal shear, but the activation of the flexural mechanism becomes more pronounced.

The influence of the masonry type (P-R2-Rx_1250_05_st) is very modest and likely related to the post-elastic characteristics of the material, contrasting more effectively the activation of the flexural mechanism and thus resulting in reduced ultimate displacements.

The free rotation at the top (P-B1-Rx_1250_05_ct) localizes the damage at the base of the pier, which collapses due to bending, at significantly lower force values and higher ultimate displacements; the effectiveness of the reinforcement, in this case, is modest.

Increasing the pier width (P-B1-Rx_2250/3350_05_st), the shear mechanism dominates, while reducing it (P-B1-Rx_850_05_st), also the flexural mechanism activated, until prevailing on shear. It is also observed that the shear damage, which generally localizes along the diagonal of the pier, tends in particularly squat piers to take on an almost tri-linear pattern, with the two extremities more inclined than the panel diagonal and the central branch approximately horizontal.

Fig. 4.2 Numerical parametric analyses on pier elements: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of axial load, masonry type and boundary conditions.

Fig. 4.3 Numerical parametric analyses on pier elements: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of pier geometry.

4.3. Parametric analysis on spandrel elements

The main features of the numerical model to investigate on spandrel elements are summarized in Fig. 4.4. The model consists of a "H"-shaped wall portion, as if it is extracted from the windowed wall of a building, and it is composed of a central spandrel (1200x1450 mm²) and two lateral pier portions (1170x3000 mm²) subjected to a constant vertical compressive stress of 0.3 MPa (the masonry self-weight is neglected in all models). The base and top solid elements in the piers are assumed rigid; the other solid elements are of "masonry" type. Accordingly to the spandrel model developed in Report 1.2 [2], to represent, in a very simplified way, the extreme weakness of the contact area between the jack arch and the overlaying masonry, a negligible Young modulus was assigned to the masonry layer of the mesh elements just above the jack arch.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the vertical uplift at the base of the right pier is applied and gradually increased.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.5-Fig. 4.7, along with the spandrel damage state (principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the shear load acting on the spandrel, varying the spandrel shear distortion (evaluated as the relative vertical displacement measured at the spandrel ends).

Fig. 4.4 Numerical model for parametric analyses on spandrel elements.

All the plain masonry spandrels fail in flexural mode (localized at both ends, or only one in case of "ct" configuration), while the introduction of the horizontal steel tie (S-B1-U_1200_t1) leads to a combined shear-bending collapse.

The CRM strengthened benchmark spandrel (S-B1-Rx_1200_t0) is affected by combined diagonal shear and flexural mechanism.

Decreasing the spandrel height (S-B1-Rx_800_t0), the flexural mechanism dominates, while increasing it (S-B1-Rx_1500_t0) the shear mechanism tends to prevail on bending.

The influence of the masonry type (S-R2-Rx_1200_t0) is quite negligible, since rubble stone masonry R2 is thicker but weaker.

Slightly higher resistances emerge from the configurations with the timber lintel (S-B1-Rx_1200_t0_ltl), even though the shear mechanism is evidently mitigated.

The introduction of the horizontal steel tie (S-B1-Rx_1200_t1), leads to higher resistances and lower displacements capacity, counteracting effectively bending failure towards the diagonal shear collapse.

With the rotational freedom of the right pier (S-B1-Rx_1200_t0_ct), damage localizes mainly at the left end of the spandrel, which collapses due to bending, and the overall structural resistance is significantly reduced.

The base rotation (S-B1-Rx_1200_t0_rot) yields performance equivalent to the benchmark configuration.

Fig. 4.5 Numerical parametric analyses on spandrel elements: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of spandrel geometry.

Fig. 4.6 Numerical parametric analyses on spandrel elements: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of masonry type, lintel type and introduction of horizontal tie.

Fig. 4.7 Numerical parametric analyses on spandrel elements: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the boundary conditions/loading scheme.

4.4. Parametric analysis on single-story walls

The main features of the numerical model to investigate on single-story walls are summarized in Fig. 4.8 Fig. 4.4. The solid elements of the base row are assumed rigid; the other solid elements are of “masonry” type. In exception, accordingly to the spandrel model of §4.3, a negligible Young modulus was assigned to the mesh elements just above the jack arches.

The solid elements of the base row are pinned at the base. The out of plane displacement at the top were avoided, to represent the constrain provided by an effective connection with the floor.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement at the top is gradually increased.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.9, along with the wall damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the horizontal load varying the horizontal displacement at the top.

Fig. 4.8 Numerical model for parametric analyses on single storey wall.

The failure on the unstrengthened wall SW-B1-t1-U_01 is dominated by the bending failure of the three masonry piers; the bending damage affected also the right spandrel. As the axial load increases, also diagonal cracking failure is detected, which tends to prevail over the bending mechanism in the central pier, for SW-B1-t1-U_03, and in both central and right pier, for SW-B1-t1-U_05.

In the R1 configurations, the failure mode is very similar to the respective unstrengthened configuration; however, it is generally observed that the areas where the maximum strains are attained results wider. More extensive damaged areas emerged also in the R2 configurations, in respect to U; in this case, the bending failure of the piers tends to dominate the collapse of the wall also in case of high vertical forces. In general, the increase of the axial force leads to an increase of the resistance; differently, the displacement capacities tend very slightly to increase.

Fig. 4.9 Numerical parametric analyses on a single storey wall: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the influence of axial stress level.

4.5. Parametric analysis of two-story walls

The main features of the numerical model to investigate on two-story walls are summarized in Fig. 4.10. The solid elements of the base row are assumed rigid; the other solid elements are of “masonry” type. In exception, accordingly to the spandrel model of §4.3, a negligible Young modulus was assigned to the mesh elements just above the jack arches. The first row of solid elements are pinned at the base. The out of plane displacement at the top were avoided, to represent the constrain provided by an effective connection with the top floor.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical axial load is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement at the top and at the intermediate floor (at a height of 3 m) is gradually increased. A constant ratio between the intermediate and top floor displacement was considered (0.5 for TWa and 0.6 for TWb±), so to represent a distribution of lateral forces approximately proportional to the fundamental mode shape.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.11, along with the wall damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the total horizontal load varying the horizontal displacement at the top.

Fig. 4.10 Numerical model for parametric analyses on two-storey wall.

Even though the dominance of diagonal cracking or bending failure mechanism in single elements varies in the three walls, the performances are quite comparable in terms of global resistance and the damage is mainly localized at the ground floor; also the intermediate spandrels are generally affected by damage, while the damage at the first floor is very limited.

Looking at the R1 configurations, it emerges failure mode very similar to the respective unstrengthened configuration; however, it is the areas with maximum strains are wider (diffusive effect of the reinforcement). Even more extensive maximum strains areas emerged in the R2 configurations. The displacement capacity of all the strengthened walls is remarkable (drifts higher than 1%).

Fig. 4.11 Numerical parametric analyses on the two storey walls: capacity curves and failure modes, considering the different wall configurations.

4.6. Parametric analysis of buildings

The main features of the numerical model to investigate on single storey walls are summarized in Fig. 4.12. The solid elements of the base row are assumed rigid; the other solid elements are of “masonry” type. In exception, accordingly to the spandrel model of §4.3, a negligible Young modulus was assigned to the mesh elements just above the jack arches. The solid elements of the first row are pinned at the base.

The analysis is divided in two stages: in the first, the vertical load (masonry self-weight and floors load) is applied and then kept constant. Subsequently, the horizontal in-plane displacement in the S-N direction, at the top and at the intermediate floor (at a height of 3 m), is gradually increased. S-N loading direction (positive) is considered. Constant ratios between the intermediate and top floor displacements are considered (1 at the top of the east wall, 0.88 at the top of the west wall and 0.6 at the intermediate floor level of both walls), so to represent a distribution of lateral forces approximately proportional to the fundamental mode shape.

The capacity curves are reported in Fig. 4.13, along with the walls damage state (in terms of principal tensile strains), evidencing the dominant failure mode. The capacity curves represent the trend of the total horizontal load varying the mean horizontal displacement at the top.

In addition, to evaluate the contribution of the transversal walls (North and South) on the overall longitudinal performances of the structure, the same analyses are performed also after disconnecting the walls at the intersections. The failure modes are evidenced in Fig. 4.14; the capacity curves are compared in Fig. 4.13 with the original configuration.

Fig. 4.12 Numerical model for analyses on pilot building.

The resistance contribution provided by the transversal walls is significant in this small and squat building. This is already evident in the study of the unreinforced configuration, where the transversal walls, due to the masonry tensile strength, delay the activation of the bending mechanism in the lateral piers of the longitudinal walls. The contribution of the transverse walls becomes even greater in the strengthened configuration, due the CRM tensile strength (applied also on the transversal walls and effectively connected at the foundation).

GB-B1

Fig. 4.13 Numerical analyses on the building: capacity curves and failure modes..

Fig. 4.14 Numerical analyses on the building with walls disconnected at the intersections: failure modes.

The same numerical model is used to simulate the performances of the experimental pilot building tested within the “CONSTRAIN” project. To adapt the model to the actual features of the experimental case, the following modifications are made:

- the masonry thickness is increased from 250 to 350 mm;
- the masonry mechanical characteristics are modified, accordingly to the different masonry type (rubble stone masonry Q2) - Table 4.2;
- the masonry jack arches are replaced by timber lintels indented in the masonry ~15 cm (elastic behavior, $E = 8000$ MPa). Just for the unstrengthened configuration, coherently with the findings of Report 1.2 [2], perfect bond between the lintel and the above masonry was considered (i.e. the mesh elements just above the lintel were assumed of masonry type).
- the presence of the horizontal ties is considered only the intermediate floor level (not at the top) and exclusively for the strengthened configurations;
- the ratios between the horizontal displacements applied to the longitudinal walls, at top and intermediate floors, are set accordingly with those recorded during the experiments.

Table 4.2 Main mechanical parameters adopted for the masonry of the CONSTRAIN pilot building (masonry type Q2)

	Q2 masonry	
Material type	<i>Cdpm2</i>	
Secant Young's modulus E	1.23 GPa	
Initial Young's modulus E_{init}	3.71 GPa	
Poisson modulus n	0.45	
Self-weight γ	21 kN/m ³	
Comp. strength f_c	2.0 MPa	
Tensile strength f_t	0.069 MPa	
Softening law	Linear	
Hardening parameters	b_h	0.027
	h_p	0.0
	k_{init}	0.075
Softening parameters	w_f/h	0.004
	a_{soft}	5.0

The results of the numerical simulations are summarized in Fig. 4.15, also in comparison with the experimental cyclic curves. Both S-N (positive, +) and N-S (negative, -) loading directions are analyzed.

Considering the simplifications of the numerical model, the numerical results are very well aligned with the experiments, both in terms of global capacity curves and damage modes of the elements (Fig. 4.16). Slightly lower resistance performance emerges in the numerical curves of the strengthened configuration, in the central part of the curves. This is likely due to the actual values of mortar coating tensile strength and thickness, that in the experimental test resulted slightly higher than the nominal ones used into the numerical simulations. However, numerical prediction of the reinforcement contribution is on the safe side.

GB-Q2-U

GB-Q2-R1

U+

R1+

Fig. 4.15 Numerical analyses on the "CONSTRAIN" pilot building: capacity curves and failure modes.

Fig. 4.16 Crack pattern of the strengthened configuration detected by DIC system at the end of the test (East wall).

5. Final remarks

In this report the results of the parametric analyses on benchmark examples are presented. The analyses were performed independently by the two partners (UL FGG and DIA-UNITS) in two different software environments: ABAQUS and OOFEM. The modelling approach and the material parameters are assumed the same as in the PRO-SIS Report 1.2 [2].

The conclusions of the PRO-SIS Report 1.2 are that both modelling approaches give very similar results on specimens tested in CONSTRAIN project. However, as this report shows, there is a clear difference between the two modelling approaches in the parametric analyses, and consequently the results are much less aligned.

The key reason for the discrepancy is that ABAQUS and OOFEM models use different assumptions about the properties of the material in tension and compression. Both modelling approaches are purposefully based on homogenous model with tied connection between the masonry and the mortar coating. As such, the models cannot directly take into account the masonry anisotropy, as well as phenomena like brick (or stone) interlocking, coating delamination, friction and residual strength after cracking. In order to include these phenomena in the model, material constitutive laws were modified.

In the case of OOFEM, the tensile and compressive properties were modified. In particular, the post peak tensile law of masonry included a plateau before the failure, to account for friction and interlocking after cracking. Moreover, the tensile strength of the coating mortar was smoothed to better account for smear cracking. Additionally, the compressive strength of coating was drastically reduced to indirectly take into account the delamination of the plaster from the masonry support, which was observed experimentally and prevented exploitation of full compressive strength of mortar.

In the case of ABAQUS, the modifications were made only in the tensile part of the masonry material response: the post-peak behavior featured a partial strength drop followed by a constant residual capacity. Additionally, the ABAQUS models required the introduction of several contacts (local interactions) to obtain more realistic response matching the global behavior of the experiments.

The different approaches produced quite comparable results when simulating the individual benchmark elements, such as piers and spandrels, in terms on initial stiffness, peak resistance and damage mode. However, when the models were used on walls (or larger structural layouts in general), which include complex interaction between structural components, the difference in the global performance of the two models became relevant, although the damage pattern looked generally comparable.

Despite the difference between the modelling approaches, the analyses shown herein give a valuable insight into the response of the CRM strengthened masonry walls and buildings, and enable qualitative and quantitative comparisons. Importantly, they confirm the assumptions used in the design of CONSTRAIN strengthening, such as assumption of equivalent frame

approach, rigid sections between spandrels and piers, and the assumed response of each component.

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PRO-SIS

Sviluppo e disseminazione di algoritmi per il progetto delle innovative strategie di protezione sismica "CONSTRAIN" e applicazione pilota su edifici esistenti in muratura

Razvoj in diseminacija postopkov za projektiranje inovativnega načina potresnega utrjevanja obstoječih zidanih stavb "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.4
Definizione parametri per programmi di calcolo automatico semplificati

NOVEMBRE 2025

Poročilo 1.4
Materialni parametri za programe za projektiranje

NOVEMBER 2025

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PRO-SIS

Development and dissemination of procedures for designing an innovative way seismic strengthening of existing masonry buildings "CONSTRAIN"

Report 1.4 Definition of parameters for simplified automatic calculation programs

NOVEMBER 2025

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Report 1.4

Definition of parameters for simplified automatic calculation programs

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1. Introduction

The report collects the results of Activity 1.4 of the “PRO-SIS” project, concerning the “Definition of modelling details of masonry buildings for simplified software used by designers and calibration of parameters based on the studied analytical and numerical models”.

Within the CONSTRAIN project (INTERREG V-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2014-2020 - <https://2014-2020.ita-slo.eu/it/constrain>), strategies to reduce the seismic vulnerability of existing masonry were developed and tested in an extended experimental campaign. The developed strengthening method is based on the use of mortar coatings reinforced by fiber-based composite materials. The main advantage of the developed system is that it can be applied only on one side of the wall, which makes it much more convenient for residents and businesses. Due to construction works only on the outside of the building, people and their belongings don't have to be relocated, and business activity doesn't have to be interrupted. Furthermore, valuable artistic decorations can be preserved on the inside (or outside, when the inside side application is preferred). The developed strengthening method stands out because of its proven effectiveness by tests on structural components and on full scale pilot building.

The aim of the “PRO-SIS” project (INTERREG VI-A ITALIA-SLOVENIA 2021-2027 - <https://www.ita-slo.eu/it/pro-sis>) is to develop the necessary methods for the design and application of these strategies. For this purpose, the design procedures have been developed based on analytical and numerical analyses calibrated on the experimental results of “CONSTRAIN”. The results provide the designers with robust strategies for the design of the proposed systems, and instructions for design in commonly used commercial programs for design of structures.

This REPORT 1.4 outlines the procedures to be used in commercial software for analysing the seismic behaviour of masonry buildings, considering the effects of reinforcement interventions using the CONSTRAIN techniques. Commonly used calculation tools are analysed: Midas GEN, 3MURI, PRO_SAP and SREMB, with each tool examined in its own section. Preliminary, a brief summary is presented concerning the behaviour and analysis of masonry buildings, along with the main challenges to be addressed when analysing reinforcement interventions using the CONSTRAIN techniques.

2. Overview of the seismic behaviour of masonry buildings

Most of the historic buildings in European cities and worldwide are made of brick or stone unreinforced masonry; this architectural heritage is variegated and ranges from Ancient Roman until Twentieth-century structures. Traditionally, masonry buildings were provided by wooden floors, and the presence of masonry arches and vaults was also rather frequent; however, in the most recent examples, floors made of steel joist with brick, of reinforced concrete vaults ceilings, of reinforced concrete joist with hollow brick interposed and of reinforced concrete plates were also employed.

These structures were built according to common practices, primarily based on empirical rules of proportion derived from experience. Although they typically perform well under normal operating conditions, they often exhibit high vulnerability in the event of a seismic occurrence, suffering serious damage and, in some cases, even collapsing. Therefore, ensuring adequate seismic behaviour for these buildings is a crucial to prevent loss of human lives, economic resources, and cultural and architectural heritage.

Ground motions caused by an earthquake induce three-dimensional vibrations in masonry buildings, resulting in vertical and horizontal inertial forces. Forces are transmitted from the intermediate floors and roof to the vertical masonry walls, and then to the foundation system. Typically, the seismic action is represented in a simplified way as a superposition of three load components: two acting horizontally in the main building's directions, and one vertically. In ordinary existing masonry buildings, the effects of the vertical component are usually negligible. The distribution of horizontal seismic loads among vertical resisting elements generally depends on their arrangement within the structure, their connections to each other, and the in-plane stiffness of the floors. Research ([1]-[2]) has shown that by ensuring structural regularity and effective connections between orthogonal walls and adequately rigid floor diaphragms (the so called "box behaviour" - Fig. 3.1.1), the distribution of seismic action among the resisting elements is primarily influenced by their stiffness. This allows for the effective use of the in-plane resistance of masonry walls oriented in the seismic direction, thus limiting out-of-plane forces on other walls. Conversely, if structural integrity is inadequate, walls may behave independently, both in-plane and out-of-plane, leading to partial collapses from local mechanisms such as wall overturning, vertical or horizontal bending, corner overturning, or gable collapse. Additionally, dangerous torsional vibrations can occur when there is an unbalanced distribution of masonry resisting elements in plan or height.

Fig. 3.1.1 Structural behaviour of masonry buildings: (a) schematization of "box behaviour", which promotes the desirable activation of (b) the in-plane response of masonry walls, while avoiding the activation of (c) weaker out-of-plane response

Besides structural integrity and distribution of resisting elements, the seismic behaviour of masonry buildings is strictly related to the mechanical characteristics of masonry itself. In fact, despite of its appreciable resistance when subjected to compression, masonry has a very low tensile resistance [3]. This mechanical characteristic, usually related to the scarce consistency of mortar joints and of the mortar-units interface, governs the main failure mechanisms in masonry resisting elements, both in-plane and out-of-plane. Moreover, the presence of multiple-leaf masonry walls without effective connections among leaves is also rather frequent; this aspect further weakens the resistance and stiffness characteristics of masonry walls.

A proper knowledge of the building structural characteristics and of the masonry consistency is thus necessary. Moreover, to ensure the seismic safety of existing masonry buildings, it is essential to apply reliable procedures for assessing their actual structural performances and, if needed, for designing effective intervention strategies.

Based on evidence from past-earthquakes, distinct macro-elements are typically identified in perforated walls, when studying the global behaviour of masonry buildings: piers and spandrels (Fig. 3.1.2). A pier is defined as the masonry portion between two horizontally adjacent openings or between an opening and a building corner, while a spandrel is the masonry portion between two vertically adjacent openings or between an opening and the roof. Referring to in-plane loads, masonry piers are subjected to axial compressive stress, shear forces and bending moments; the spandrels, coupling vertical resistant elements, are subject to shear forces and bending moments but, typically, only to very limited compressive forces.

Fig. 3.1.2 Identification of pier and spandrels in a perforated masonry wall

Experience has evidenced that the in-plane failure of a pier or a spandrel may be due to diagonal cracking, bending (rocking and/or toe crushing) or sliding, depending on the wall slenderness, axial stress level and boundary conditions, as well as masonry characteristics [4]. Shear-dominated response exhibited diagonal cracking (Fig. 3.1.3a,c) and a load-drift response characterized by high energy dissipation, but by rather rapid strength degradation. In the flexure-dominated response, the damage is typically concentrated at the extremities (Fig. 3.1.3b,d); it is characterized by a very moderate dissipation of hysteretic energy but a rather smooth strength degradation. Sliding may occur in piers combined with rocking, in case of low axial loads and regular, smooth bed joints; sliding failure at spandrel extremities is unlikely in periodic masonry, as the mortar joints are not continuous along the vertical direction. Due to

the negligible axial stress, spandrels typically exhibit a very limited bending resistance; the presence of effective horizontal tie beams at floor levels (e.g. steel rods, r.c. beams) counteracts this mechanism, leading to a shear-dominated failure.

Analytical correlations to evaluate the resistance of masonry piers and spandrels, based on the different, possible failure mechanisms, along with the respective ultimate drift limits, are available in the literature and have also been adopted in different national and international building codes and guidelines. Further details and examples of application can be found in the "PRO-SIS" Report 1.1 [5].

Fig. 3.1.3 Typical failure mechanisms of masonry piers and spandrels: (a, c) diagonal cracking, (b, d) bending with rocking and/or toe crushing

For the global analysis of masonry buildings, simplified modelling methods that subdivide masonry walls into macro-elements have been developed. Nonlinear static analyses (pushover) based on macro-element modelling have proven to be a useful, reliable tool for obtaining a realistic prediction of the resistance and displacement capacities with relatively low computational effort, provided that there is proper calibration of the mechanical parameters and a thoughtful schematization of the resisting elements.

The simplified macro-elements models represent an evolution of the well-known POR approach [6]. In simplified macro-elements models [7]-[9], the resisting elements (i.e. the piers and the spandrels), are usually schematised by means mono-dimensional, elastic beam elements, connected by rigid beams, defining the "Equivalent Frame" model of the structure (Appendix A). The nonlinear response is lumped into localized hinges, whose resistance and displacement capacities are determined by applying the simplified analytical correlations. However, different macro-element schematizations (e.g. based on bi-dimensional elements [10]) are also available.

3. Analysis of CRM strengthened masonry structures

The strengthening technique for masonry structures primarily addressed in the “CONSTRAIN” project is the Composite Reinforced Mortar - CRM technique. It consists in the application, on the masonry surface (one or both sides), of a 30 mm thick mortar coating with preformed Glass Fiber-Reinforced Polymer composite meshes embedded, in combination with the introduction of transversal connectors.

CRM was proved beneficial for the performances of masonry elements, improving resistance, displacement capacities and energy dissipation. As broadly discussed in the “PRO-SIS” Report 1.1 [5], the CRM application can modify the failure mechanism of the masonry element and its effectiveness may vary, depending on the governing failure mechanism, as well as the characteristics of the masonry. The analytical-mechanical models capable of describing the behaviour of CRM strengthened masonry piers and spandrels, based on experimental evidence, are outlined in [5].

However, conventional strategies/procedures necessitate to be developed to account for these improvements when performing the global numerical analysis of masonry buildings by using common commercial software. The application of the macro-element modelling approach described for unreinforced masonry in §2 is likely suitable also for CRM strengthened masonry, but some adjustments are deemed.

Some commonly used calculation tools are analysed: Midas GEN, 3MURI, PRO_SAP and SREMB.

3.1. Analyses with Midas GEN

The software Midas GEN, v1.3 (CSP FEA Engineering Solutions) [11] as used for the numerical simulation.

3.1.1. Modelling overview

The software Midas GEN allows to carry out nonlinear static “pushover” analysis for masonry buildings. The modelling of the structure is based on the “Equivalent frame” model with lumped plasticity (Appendix A). The user is asked to preliminary define:

- the geometry of the equivalent frame;
- the vertical loads;
- the masonry mechanical properties;
- the behaviour of the lumped plasticity hinges.

- Geometry

The user models the masonry structure according to the “Equivalent Frame” method (Fig. 3.1.1), by using beam elements, and provides the effective lengths of the piers and spandrels and of the “rigid nodes” (Appendix A). The rigid beams forming the “rigid nodes” of the structure can be modelled separately from pier/spandrel elements or by defining beam-end-offset constraints applied on piers/spandrel elements. Anyway, the user must be careful in assigning the self-weights of such rigid portions, to avoid double counting. An effective strategy is, for example, to apply the beam-end offset constraints option to vertical elements (therefore, having the masonry self-weight) in combination with a separate modelling of the horizontal rigid elements (assigning them zero self-weight).

The user also defines the beams cross sections (bending deformation is always considered, the shear one is optional but is activated by default). For the proper assignment of the plastic capacities, the Y-local axis of the beam has to be arranged along the wall thickness (i.e. perpendicular to the wall plane).

The piers of the ground floor are typically fixed at the base. To properly apply floor diaphragm constraints, the user shall keep attention in constraining only the nodes at the top of the piers, keeping free all the other nodes at that level.

- Vertical loads

The vertical loads transmitted by the floors can be assigned manually as nodal or distributed loads. The “assign floor load” option allows also automatic assignment, once floor typology (i.e. one/two way) and the nodes of the loading area are selected.

The masonry self-weights (defined in the material properties) shall also be activated.

- Material properties

Masonry is assumed as an equivalent isotropic material. The user provides the basic masonry mechanical characteristics in terms of self-weight, Young’s modulus, and shear modulus (or Poisson’s ratio).

- Lumped plasticity features

The user selects the type of masonry element (pier or spandrel) and defines the non-linear masonry characteristics:

- for the piers: the shear strength (τ_0), the vertical compressive strength (f_m), and the vertical stress distribution coefficient (0.85 by default);
- for the spandrels: the shear strength (τ_0), the horizontal compressive strength ($f_{m,h}$) and the horizontal tie resistance (H_p).

The hinges to be activated for the pushover analysis of masonry buildings are, typically, in-plane shear, at the beam centre (Fz), and in-plane bending (My), at both beam ends. Axial compression can also be activated (Fx).

The user is asked also to select the strength formulations: for the purposes of this study, "existing masonry" and "irregular masonry type" options are suggested. Thus:

- for pier elements, the shear resistance ($V_{P,d(URM)}$) and the bending resistance ($M_{P(URM)}$) are determined through Eqs. 3.1 and 3.2, respectively:

$$V_{P,d(URM)} = \frac{1.5\tau_0}{\beta} b_p \cdot t_p \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_0}{1.5\tau_0}} \quad (3.1)$$

$$M_{P(URM)} = \frac{\sigma_0 b_p^2 t_p}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_0}{0.85 \cdot f_m} \right) \quad (3.2)$$

- for spandrel elements, the shear resistance ($V_{S,d(URM)}$) and the bending resistance ($M_{S(URM)}$) are determined through Eqs. 3.3 and 3.4, respectively.

$$V_{S,d(URM)} = \frac{1.5\tau_0}{\beta} b_s \cdot t_s \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_0}{1.5\tau_0}} \quad (3.3)$$

$$M_{S(URM)} = \frac{H_p b_s}{2} \left(1 - \frac{H_p}{0.85 f_{m,h} \cdot h_s \cdot t_s} \right) \quad (3.4)$$

Where:

- t_p masonry pier thickness
- b_p masonry pier width
- l_p masonry pier height (i.e. "effective length")
- t_s masonry spandrel thickness
- b_s masonry spandrel height
- l_s masonry spandrel length (i.e. "effective length")
- σ_0 mean compressive stress on the pier/spandrel
- f_m masonry vertical compressive strength
- $f_{m,h}$ masonry horizontal compressive strength
- τ_0 equivalent masonry shear strength for $\sigma_0 = 0$
- β pier/spandrel slenderness factor ($1.0 \leq \beta = l/b \leq 1.5$)
- H_p tensile resistance of the horizontal tie (however, limited to $0.4 \cdot f_{m,h} \cdot b_s \cdot t_s$)

Basically, for the in-plane shear mechanism the software considers the Turnšek-Čačovič formulation [12]. For in-plane bending mechanism of piers, it accounts only for the masonry compressive resistance and the stabilizing effect of the vertical loads. For the strength in-plane bending mechanism of spandrels, it assumes the presence of an effective horizontal tie, otherwise the resistance is null.

Although, spandrels without a horizontal tie have some bending resistance, even though small, due to the interaction between adjacent blocks at the spandrel ends, as evidenced also from the experimental "CONSTRAIN" tests on the unstrengthened spandrel samples [5]. Thus, in this case, the user shall "force" the software for a proper evaluation of the bending resistance. For example, a fictitious horizontal tie resistance ($H_{p,fit}$) can be set, based on the actual resistance expected for the spandrel (as detailed in [5]).

For each hinge type, the user defines the post-elastic behaviour (FEMA type - Fig. 3.1.2). Point "B" is automatically determined (based on the elastic stiffness of the element and the resistance). The user defines "C", "D" and "E" (in terms of both strength ratio, in respect to point "B", and deformation capacities) and can opt/opt out for the total strength loss at the reaching of point "E" (kept constant by default).

Based on the provided hinges properties, the software automatically calculates the lateral strength and displacement capacities of masonry piers and spandrels; the axial stress level is automatically updated at each analysis step. The software considers the mean axial stress in the element to determine the resistance of hinges.

Fig. 3.1.1 "Equivalent frame" model schematization

Fig. 3.1.2 Plastic hinge behaviour according to FEMA 356 [13]

3.1.2. Analysis features

The user sets up the pushover analysis under displacement control (of a master node, i.e. the mass centre at the roof level), specifying the lateral load pattern, the target displacement, and the number of steps. The vertical loads shall be preliminary applied.

Different lateral load patterns can be applied: proportional to a static load case defined by the user, uniform acceleration (proportional to the mass at each story level), proportional to a mode shape, normalized mode shape times mass (the load pattern for the pushover analysis is derived by multiplying the normalized mode shape by the mass). The last three types require eigenvalue analysis to be previously performed; to that, it is essential to define the masses of the structure (e.g. the self-weights and added loads can be converted into masses). After the analysis, the user can check the calculated strength of each inelastic hinge at each step.

3.1.3. How to account for CRM

As previously specified, the software performs the pushover analysis by automatically evaluating the in-plane resistance and displacement characteristics of the piers and spandrels, by automatically applying the analytical correlations presented in §3.1.1, that are suitable for URM. Currently, the software does not include an automatic procedure to account for the CRM contribution. Thus, for CRM strengthened masonry, the user shall “force” the software by providing “fictitious” equivalent masonry properties, to account also for the CRM reinforcement contribution. In fact, the software does not allow to modify the correlations for the resistance estimation, but just the masonry material parameters and plastic hinges drift limits.

For CRM strengthened elements (both piers and spandrels), the “spandrel element type” shall be selected in the software and equivalent material parameters values $\tau_{0,eq}$ (masonry shear strength) and $H_{P,eq}$ must be set, according to Eqs. 3.5 and 3.6:

$$\tau_{0,eq} = \frac{\sigma_0}{3} + \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_0^2}{9} + \left(\frac{\beta \cdot V_{d(CRM)}}{1.5 \cdot b \cdot t}\right)^2} \quad (3.5)$$

$$H_{P,eq} = \frac{2 \cdot M_{(CRM)}}{b} \quad (3.6)$$

where:

$V_{d(CRM)}$ Resistance of the CRM strengthened masonry element in shear (related to the in-plane diagonal cracking mechanism)

M_{CRM} Resistance of the CRM strengthened masonry element in bending (related to the in-plane bending mechanism)

The values of $V_{d(CRM)}$ and M_{CRM} shall be calculated analytically by the user, applying the correlations provided in the “PRO-SIS” Report 1.1 [5] for CRM. Note also that the masonry compressive strength shall be set fictitiously to a high value (e.g. 1000 MPa). For spandrel elements, it is assumed $\sigma_0 = 0$ in Eq. (3.5). Also increased ultimate drift values must be assigned to CRM strengthened masonry elements [5].

3.1.4. Validation

For the validation of the procedure, two benchmark examples (a pier and a spandrel element) are considered, and the comparison between numerical simulations and analytical calculations are made. The reference to the analytical calculations is provided in the Appendix B.

For piers, the vertical axial compression is simulated by applying a vertical force to the upper node and the pushover analysis is performed by gradually increasing lateral displacement of the upper node. The plotted graphs represent the base shear, F_p , varying the net horizontal displacement d_h between the top and the bottom of the effective pier length l_{eff} .

For spandrels, the pushover analysis is performed by gradually increasing the nodal rotation at the two base supports while controlling the horizontal displacement of the node at the top-right node. The plotted graphs represent the shear acting on the spandrel, F_s , against the distortion (i.e. net displacement d_v between the spandrel ends, determined orthogonally in respect to the direction of the adjacent rigid parts).

In both cases, the self-weight is not considered.

Fig. 3.1.3 Schematization of the validation numerical models for the pier, according to (a) a shear-type or (b) a cantilever beam scheme, and for the spandrel

It is observed that for both piers and spandrels, the analytical and numerical predictions coincide, in terms both of capacity curves and failure mode. It is thus concluded that the adopted procedure allows the software to correctly reproduce in a simplified way the behaviour of both unstrengthened and CRM strengthened masonry.

ID:	URM_Pier_st_0.3	R1_Pier_st_0.3 ($H_{p,eq}=135.6\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.232\text{MPa}$)	R2_Pier_st_0.3 ($H_{p,eq}=180.2\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.382\text{MPa}$)
State:	Unstrengthened	Strengthened on one side	Strengthened on two sides
Axial stress:	0.3 MPa	0.3 MPa	0.3 MPa
Capacity curve:			
Yield point:	1.31 mm 50.5 kN	1.20 mm 90.3 kN	1.10 mm 120.0 kN
Collapse:	9.38 mm 50.5 kN	37.5 mm 90.4 kN	37.5 mm 120.1 kN
Failure mode:	Diagonal cracking	Bending	Bending

ID:	URM_Pier_ct_0.3	R1_Pier_ct_0.3 ($H_{p,eq}=135.6\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.232\text{MPa}$)	R2_Pier_ct_0.3 ($H_{p,eq}=180.2\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.382\text{MPa}$)
State:	Unstrengthened	Strengthened on one side	Strengthened on two sides
Axial stress:	0.3 MPa	0.3 MPa	0.3 MPa
Capacity curve:			
Yield point:	1.53 mm 22.2 kN	1.35 mm 35.8 kN	1.20 mm 47.5 kN
Collapse:	18.7 mm 22.2 kN	37.5 mm 35.8 kN	37.5 mm 47.6 kN
Failure mode:	Bending	Bending	Bending

ID:	URM_Spandrel	R1_Spandrel ($H_{p,eq}=72.6\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.209\text{MPa}$)	R2_Spandrel ($H_{p,eq}=73.8\text{kN}$, $\tau_{0,eq}=0.364\text{MPa}$)
State:	Unstrengthened	Strengthened on one side	Strengthened on two sides
H_p	100 kN	100 kN	100 kN
Capacity curve:			
Yield point:	0.55 mm 18.0 kN	0.72 mm 41.8 kN	0.76 mm 49.2 kN
Collapse:	17.8 mm 10.8 kN	36.0 mm 41.8 kN	36.1 mm 49.2 kN
Failure mode:	Diagonal cracking	Diagonal cracking	Bending

3.2. Analyses with 3MURI

The numerical simulation was conducted using 3Muri software (version 12.6.2.4) [14], developed by S.T.A. DATA. 3Muri provides an integrated and modular solution for analysing masonry and mixed structures. It employs a macro-element-based approach, schematizing the structure as an assembly of macro-elements to replicate the mechanical behavior of the walls. This approach allows for both rapid and detailed analysis.

3.2.1. *Modelling overview*

The software 3Muri allows to conduct nonlinear static “pushover” analysis for masonry buildings. The modelling of the structure is based on the “Equivalent frame” model with lumped plasticity (Appendix A). The user is asked to preliminary define:

- the geometry of the structure, from which the equivalent frame model is automatically generated. The geometry can also be imported from various file formats (e.g., DXF, IFC, and other supported formats);
- the vertical loads;
- the masonry mechanical properties;
- the behaviour of the lumped plasticity hinges.

- Geometry

The automatically generated frame model schematizes the structure into piers and spandrels (Fig. 3.2.1). The user can later modify these elements to consider a different schematization, if needed.

Fig. 3.2.1 “Equivalent frame” model schematization: (a) 3D representation of the input geometry; (b) extruded view of the macro elements

- Material properties and lumped plasticity features

Masonry is assumed as an equivalent isotropic material. The user provides the following masonry mechanical characteristics, according to the example in Fig. 3.2.2:

- self-weight (w);
- Young's modulus (E);
- shear modulus (G).
- vertical compressive strength (f_m);
- equivalent masonry shear strength for $\sigma_0 = 0$ (τ_0);
- confidence factor (FC);
- material strength partial safety factor (γ_m);
- shear and bending limit drifts;
- type of formulation considered (existing masonry is herein considered).

These properties can be assigned to the walls or to each element individually.

Name	PRO-SIS Pilot01
E [N/mm ²]	1.500,00
G [N/mm ²]	500,00
w [kN/m ³]	18
f _m [N/cm ²]	345,00
f _k [N/cm ²]	345,00
τ [N/cm ²]	9,00
f _{vlim} [N/mm ²]	0,0
FC	1,00
γ _m	1,00
Shear drift	0,0050
Bending drift	0,0100
φ _∞	0,0
Damage condition	Existing
Description	for parametric study
Library	

Fig. 3.2.2 Input form for unreinforced masonry material data

The user considers the strength formulation for “existing” masonry and selects the Turnšek-Čačovič formulation [12] for the shear resistance (Eq. 3.1 for piers and Eq. 3.3 for spandrels), while the bending resistance of piers is determined using Eq. 3.2. For spandrels with a horizontal tie, the tie material properties and diameter, and its position are inputted in the wall segment attributes (Fig. 3.2.3). The software then uses Eq. 3.4 to calculate the spandrel's strength.

Based on the provided macro-elements properties, the software automatically calculates the lateral strength and displacement capacities of masonry piers and spandrels; the axial stress level is automatically updated at each analysis step.

Fig. 3.2.3 Input form for masonry section properties data

Since spandrels without a horizontal tie have some bending resistance, although reduced, it can be accounted e.g. by inserting a fictitious horizontal tie resistance corresponding to the expected resistance.

3.2.2. Analysis features

The user sets up the pushover analysis under displacement control (of a master node, i.e. the mass centre at the roof level), specifying the lateral load pattern, the target displacement, and the number of steps. The vertical loads shall be preliminary applied. There are different lateral load distribution options, including uniform acceleration and proportional to static forces.

The pushover procedure consists of an incremental static analysis with displacement control at only one degree of freedom, maintaining constant ratios between the applied forces. The capacity curve, which plots the total base shear against the horizontal displacement, represents the structure's behavior under horizontal loads (Fig. 3.2.4); the damage state of the elements is also given.

Fig. 3.2.4 Pushover analysis results: (a) capacity curve and (b) element damage state

3.2.3. How to account for CRM

The 3Muri software includes the possibility of automatic calculation of the FRCM reinforcement contribution, by applying the formulations given in the CNR-DT 215/2018 technical document [15].

This option can also be useful to consider the contribution of the CRM, with the necessary precautions. In particular, “user defined” parameters shall be set for the reinforcement properties, specifying the equivalent thickness/area, Young’s modulus and ultimate drift for the fibres in the two main directions (Fig. 3.2.5).

It is important to clarify that the equivalent thickness/area of fibres is that at one side of the wall. Then the user can specify whether the reinforcement is applied to one or both sides.

However, it is observed that when the one-side application option is selected, a reduction in the shear contribution of the reinforcement will automatically be applied by the software, complying with CNR-DT 215/2018 [15]. A way to avoid this reduction is selecting the double side application option and set halved values for the thickness/area (Fig. 3.2.6).

In the interface, also the new shear and bending ultimate drifts of the strengthened elements must be specified; although also the drift limits for plain masonry must be updated with the increased values (Fig. 3.2.7). It is observed that the specified drifts apply equally to both piers and spandrels; thus, if different drift values are to be assigned, it is necessary to define different masonry and reinforcement types.

Two sides CRM

Material properties

Type	Name
Name	MuraturaB1 con CRM_R2
Material colour	
Texture	
E [N/mm ²]	3900
Eh [N/mm ²]	3900
G [N/mm ²]	1430

Define characteristics

Masonry panel Masonry panel + R.C. tie beam

R.C. wall R.C. beam Steel/w

Masonry panel

Material

MuraturaB1 con CRM_R2

Reinforced masonry/Reinforcement

ConstrainCRM (MasonryB1)

Piers

Reinforcement properties

Name: ConstrainCRM Reinforcement type: **FRCM** User defined Use conventional values

Masonry		Calculation coefficients	
Masonry type		y f,d	
ηa definition		α	
Exposure class		y m	
f _{bm} [N/mm ²]		Shear drift	0.0100
f _{btm} [N/mm ²]		Bending drift	0.0200
Dist. application [mm]		β	0.79

Pier		Spandrel beam	
Layout	Continue	Layout	Continue
bf [mm]		bf [mm]	
Step[mm]		Step[mm]	
tf [mm]	0.058	tf [mm]	0.058
Layers number	1	Layers number	1
Effect typology	Shear+Bending	Effect typology	Shear+Bending
Application	Double side	Application	Double side
Bending anchor	Efficacious	Bending anchor	Efficacious
ηa		ηa	
Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00	Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00
ε _{fk} [%]		ε _{fk} [%]	
ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000	ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000
f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00	f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00
		Summit edging	
		Number of layers	0
		Width bf [mm]	0.000
		tf [mm]	0.000

Spandrels

Reinforcement properties

Name: ConstrainCRM Reinforcement type: **FRCM** User defined Use conventional values

Masonry		Calculation coefficients	
Masonry type		y f,d	
ηa definition		α	
Exposure class		y m	
f _{bm} [N/mm ²]		Shear drift	0.0300
f _{btm} [N/mm ²]		Bending drift	0.0300
Dist. application [mm]		β	0.79

Pier		Spandrel beam	
Layout	Continue	Layout	Continue
bf [mm]		bf [mm]	
Step[mm]		Step[mm]	
tf [mm]	0.058	tf [mm]	0.058
Layers number	1	Layers number	1
Effect typology	Shear+Bending	Effect typology	Shear+Bending
Application	Double side	Application	Double side
Bending anchor	Efficacious	Bending anchor	Efficacious
ηa		ηa	
Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00	Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00
ε _{fk} [%]		ε _{fk} [%]	
ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000	ε _{fd} [%]	1.85000
f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00	f _{fd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00
		Summit edging	
		Number of layers	0
		Width bf [mm]	0.000
		tf [mm]	0.000

Fig. 3.2.5 Input form for the definition of CRM parameters (application at both sides)

One side CRM

Material properties

Type **Name**

Name **MasonryB1 with CRM_R1**

Material colour

Texture

E [N/mm ²]	2700
Eh [N/mm ²]	2700
G [N/mm ²]	980

Define characteristics

Masonry panel Masonry panel + R.C. tie beam

R.C. wall R.C. beam Steel/h

Masonry panel

Material

MuraturaB1 con CRM_R1

Reinforced masonry/Reinforcement

ConstrainCRM (MasonryB1)

Piers

Reinforcement properties

Name **ConstrainCRM** Reinforcement type **FRCM** User defined

Masonry		Calculation coefficients	
Masonry type		$\gamma_{f,d}$	
η_a definition		α	
Exposure class		γ_m	
f _{bm} [N/mm ²]		Shear drift	0.0100
f _{btm} [N/mm ²]		Bending drift	0.0200
Dist. application [mm]		β	0.79

Pier		Spandrel beam	
Layout	Continue	Layout	Continue
bf [mm]		bf [mm]	
Step[mm]		Step[mm]	
tf [mm]	0.029	tf [mm]	0.029
Layers number	1	Layers number	1
Effect typology	Shear +Bending	Effect typology	Shear +Bending
Application	Double side	Application	Double side
Bending anchor	Efficacious	Bending anchor	Efficacious
η_a		η_a	
Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00	Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00
ϵ_{fk} [%]		ϵ_{fk} [%]	
ϵ_{fd} [%]	1.85000	ϵ_{fd} [%]	1.85000
f _{fdd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00	f _{fdd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00

Spandrels

Reinforcement properties

Name **ConstrainCRM** Reinforcement type **FRCM** User defined

Masonry		Calculation coefficients	
Masonry type		$\gamma_{f,d}$	
η_a definition		α	
Exposure class		γ_m	
f _{bm} [N/mm ²]		Shear drift	0.0300
f _{btm} [N/mm ²]		Bending drift	0.0300
Dist. application [mm]		β	0.79

Pier		Spandrel beam	
Layout	Continue	Layout	Continue
bf [mm]		bf [mm]	
Step[mm]		Step[mm]	
tf [mm]	0.029	tf [mm]	0.029
Layers number	1	Layers number	1
Effect typology	Shear +Bending	Effect typology	Shear +Bending
Application	Double side	Application	Double side
Bending anchor	Efficacious	Bending anchor	Efficacious
η_a		η_a	
Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00	Ef [N/mm ²]	72702.00
ϵ_{fk} [%]		ϵ_{fk} [%]	
ϵ_{fd} [%]	1.85000	ϵ_{fd} [%]	1.85000
f _{fdd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00	f _{fdd} [N/mm ²]	1345.00

Fig. 3.2.6 Input form for the definition of CRM parameters (application at one side)

Shear drift	0,0100	Shear drift	0,0100	Shear drift	0,0300
Bending drift	0,0200	Bending drift	0,0200	Bending drift	0,0300

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 3.2.7 Input drift values in the material data form for strengthened masonry piers: (a) strengthened on one side; (b) strengthened on two sides and (c) drift values for CRM strengthened spandrels on one- and two-sides

3.3. Analyses with PRO_SAP

The software PRO_SAP v. 24.10.0 (2S.l. Software e Servizi per l'Ingegneria S.r.l.) [16] was used for the numerical simulation, combined with the PRO_SAM [17] application to generate the equivalent frame model (Appendix A).

3.3.1. *Modelling overview*

The software PRO SAP allows to carry out nonlinear static analysis (pushover) for masonry buildings, by adopting the equivalent frame model. The structure modelling starts from the definition of the masonry properties, analysis criteria, and geometry. The user can use a wizard where it is possible to define the 2D dimensions of walls with openings, from which the equivalent frame is created by the algorithm. The behavior of lumped plasticity hinges is defined automatically by the software, based on Italian code indications.

The user is asked to preliminary define:

- the masonry mechanical properties (material);
- the masonry design criteria;
- the geometry of the equivalent frame;
- the vertical loads.

- Material properties

Masonry is assumed as an equivalent isotropic material. The user can assign Young's modulus, shear modulus (or Poisson's ratio), vertical compressive strength, horizontal compressive strength, shear strength (for diagonal failure), self-weight.

In Fig. 3.1.1 an example of the interface for defining the masonry characteristics is illustrated: by selecting an existing material, the software automatically defines an orthotropic material with equal mechanical characteristics in the three main directions.

Definizione proprietà materiale tipo muratura	
Stringa identificativa	PRO SIS
Generalità	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Materiale esistente	
Fattore di confidenza FC m	0.0
Resistenze	
Resistenza fm	3.45 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fhm	1.725 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fv0m	9.0000e-02 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fv0hm	9.0000e-02 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza tau0m	9.0000e-02 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fvlimm	0.0 [N/mm ²]
Coefficiente mu tilda	0.4
Coefficiente fi	0.5
Resistenza fbN	4.16 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fbm	0.0 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fbhm	0.0 [N/mm ²]
Resistenza fbtm	0.0 [N/mm ²]
Setta i valori non introdotti (...)	setta i valori = 0
<input type="checkbox"/> Elasto-plastico per aste ...	
<input type="checkbox"/> Muratura consolidata	
Proprietà	
Peso specifico	0.0 [N/mm ³]
Dilatazione termica	1.0000e-05 [1/C]
Dilatazione termica 2	1.0000e-05 [1/C]
Dilatazione termica 3	1.0000e-05 [1/C]
Smorzamento	5.0
Costanti elastiche	
Modulo E	1500.0 [N/mm ²]
Poisson	0.0
Modulo G	500.0 [N/mm ²]
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ortotropo	
Costanti elastiche ortotropo	
Modulo E2	1500.0 [N/mm ²]
Modulo E3	1500.0 [N/mm ²]
Poisson 1-3	0.0
Poisson 2-3	0.0
Modulo G1-3	500.0 [N/mm ²]
Modulo G2-3	500.0 [N/mm ²]
Avanzate	
Stringa identificativa	

Fig. 3.3.1 Example of the screen for defining the masonry characteristics

- Design criteria

Resistance and displacement capacities for the masonry elements (piers and spandrels) are determined by the software. Design criteria are selected by the user within those included in the software database (Fig. 3.3.2). For this study, according with the common assumptions made for the other software, the "NTC criteria" was selected (complying with the Italian building code and its commentary, [18]-[19]).

For the diagonal cracking failure mechanism, the Turnšek-Čačovič model [12] is considered for both piers and spandrels. The standard in-plane bending failure mechanism is also accounted by default, depending on the masonry compressive strength and on the axial stress level (for piers) or on the horizontal tie resistance (for spandrels). Default ultimate drift values for piers and spandrels are those given by the code; however, the user can modify them.

Design criteria table			
R.C. Walls	R.C. slabs	Reinforced concrete beams	Reinforced concrete columns
Floors and panels	Steel truss	Steel columns	Steel beams
<input type="checkbox"/> Apply par. C4.5.6.2			
<input type="checkbox"/> Apply EC6 app. C			
Tie strength		0.0 [kN]	
Shear failure M		list...	<input type="checkbox"/> Sliding [7.8.3] - (MC)
Shear failure F		list...	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Diagonal crack [C8.7.1.16] (TC)
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reinforcement and other advanced parameters...			<input type="checkbox"/> Diagonal crack [C8.7.1.17] (MM)
Masonry wall			
<input type="checkbox"/> Elastic only			
Drift DLS		2.0000e-03	
Drift M		1.0000e-02	
Drift V		5.0000e-03	
Masonry Spandrel			
<input type="checkbox"/> Elastic only M			
<input type="checkbox"/> Elastic only V			
Plasticity factor		1.0	
Drift M		2.0000e-02	
Drift ini V		5.0000e-03	
Drift fin V		5.0000e-03	

Fig. 3.3.2 Example of definition of design criteria

- Geometry

When using the PRO_SAM application, the user must define the plane geometry of each wall (perimeter). The start and end points of the wall in the horizontal direction can be defined either by coordinates or by a click on the specific points; the wall's height is defined last (Fig. 3.3.3a). Similarly, for defining the openings, it is necessary to indicate the start and end points in the horizontal direction, and the height of the spandrels below and above the openings. Then, the automatic process creates the equivalent frame, as a combination of piers, spandrels and rigid elements (Fig. 3.3.3b). However, the user can adjust the length of the rigid elements.

Fig. 3.3.3 Example of wall geometry definition (a) and equivalent frame generation (b)

- Vertical loads

The vertical loads, due to floors, can be assigned by giving the floor load, area, and orientation or by a nodal force acting at the top of each pier.

- Lumped plasticity features

The assignment of lumped plasticity hinges is done by the software, which automatically identifies piers and spandrels, and assigns the plasticity law accordingly to the selected design criteria. Typically, a rigid-plastic behavior is assigned to the lumped plastic hinges. Coherently with the selected "NTC design criteria" described above, the resistance value, for each element, is defined as indicated in the following:

- for piers, Eq. 3.1 and Eq. 3.2 applies for the shear and bending resistance, respectively;
- for the spandrels, the bending resistance follows Eq. 3.4, while the shear is according to Eq. 3.7:

$$V_{S,d(URM)} = \tau_0 \cdot b_S \cdot t_S \quad (3.7)$$

Where:

- t_S masonry spandrel thickness
- b_S masonry spandrel height
- τ_0 equivalent masonry shear strength for $\sigma_0 = 0$

It is observed that, differently from the piers, the formulation for the shear resistance of the spandrels does not consider the slenderness factor β . If the user wishes to consider it, it will be necessary to insert, for the spandrel masonry material properties, an actual shear resistance value scaled by $1.5/\beta$.

Moreover, for the in-plane bending resistance of spandrels, the software assumes the presence of an effective horizontal tie, otherwise the resistance is null. But spandrels without a horizontal tie have some bending resistance, although reduced, thanks to the block-to-block interaction at the spandrel ends. Thus, in this case, if the user wishes to account it, the software can be "forced" by inserting a fictitious horizontal tie resistance.

3.3.2. Analysis features

The software selects the control point (master node) in the mass centre of the top floor.

The vertical loads are preliminary applied; then the horizontal displacement of the control point is applied incrementally, according to the assigned lateral load pattern. Different lateral load patterns can be applied. For the scope of this study, a triangular distribution proportional to the static forces is considered (Fig. 3.3.4). The user can set the number of steps in which the software applies the incremental displacement.

After the analysis, the global capacity curve (lateral force vs. displacement of the control point) is provided (Fig. 3.3.5). The user is also able to check the failure mode of each element and the calculated strength of each inelastic hinge at each step.

Fig. 3.3.4 Example of setting analysis parameters

Fig. 3.3.5 Example of output (capacity curve and failure mode of elements)

3.3.3. How to account for CRM

The PRO SAP software (combined with the PRO_SAM application) includes the possibility of automatic calculation of an FRCM reinforcement contribution by applying the formulations given in the CNR-DT 215/2018 technical document [15]. This option is easy to adapt to the purposes of this project.

Where the strengthening intervention is applied, a new material must be defined (Fig. 3.3.6). After that, the FRCM application must be selected; however, the “simplified method” option (based on amplifications coefficients) must not be selected.

Fig. 3.3.6 Example of the interface for defining the CRM strengthened masonry characteristics

The user must define the properties of the CRM strengthening systems, specifying the equivalent thickness, Young's modulus, limit strength and strain of fibres (Fig. 3.3.7).

Two different CRM applications are considered in this project: single- and double-sided. It is observed that, according to CNR DT 215/2018, in case of one-side application the shear contribution of the reinforcement is reduced by 30%. To avoid that, according to experimental evidence, a fictitious property for the one-side application was adopted, where a two-side application was considered in the software, but assuming a halved thickness (Fig. 3.3.7).

ID	ID	Thickness	single side	E	sig u (composite)	eps u, f %	eps lim, c %	Direction	Exposition	Fiber	eta o	alfa internal	alfa terminal	H bands width	H bands pitch	V bands wid.	V bands pitch	uncovered area	Use ONLY for c
n. 1	R1	0.06	NO	72702.00	1345.00	1.85	1.85	biaxial	internal	glass	0.90	1.00	1.00	66.00	66.00	66.00	66.00	0.00	NO
n. 3	R2	0.12	NO	72702.00	1345.00	1.85	1.85	biaxial	internal	glass	0.90	1.00	1.00	66.00	66.00	66.00	66.00	0.00	NO

Fig. 3.3.7 CRM reinforcement properties

To consider the stiffness increase due to the CRM application (related to the mortar coating), higher values of Young's and shear moduli must be assigned to the reinforced masonry

material (based on the masonry and plaster moduli, weighted on their respective thickness). Similarly, also the self-weight can be adjusted; however, the increase is very limited. To consider the benefits of the CRM system in terms of ultimate drifts on piers and spandrels, the “design criteria” also needs to be modified (Fig. 3.3.8).

Fig. 3.3.8 Update design criteria for CRM strengthened masonry

3.4. Analyses with SREMB

3.4.1. Modelling overview

The software SREMB (internal prototype software of ZRMK; similar to the POR method [6]) allows to carry out nonlinear static “pushover” analysis for the critical story of a masonry building. Usually that is the ground floor, but the procedure can be repeated for all the stories, to determine the weakest. The modelling of the story is based on the subdivision in pier macro elements.

The user is asked to define:

- the geometry of the macro elements (walls, piers);
- the vertical loads (stresses due to vertical loads on macro elements);
- the masonry mechanical properties;
- parameters for calculation.

The following assumptions are considered in the seismic analysis:

- masonry piers are considered connected at story levels with the floor structures, which are stiff in their plane. This assumption ensures the participation of all walls in resisting the horizontal load;

- the walls are clamped at the upper and lower edges into the ceiling structure, into the lintel / parapet part of the wall;
- cantilever type boundary condition is generally assumed for the piers in single storey structures and in the top story of multi-story buildings. The presence of reinforced concrete beams, strong (tall) spandrels or stiff masonry in the above storey can be considered by assuming symmetrical boundary condition (shear-type);
- the walls of composite cross-sections (L, T, H) are considered as the sum of the walls separated from each other by vertical joints;
- the contribution of the resistance of the walls to the resistance of the floor depends on their stiffness and load-bearing capacity, as well as on their deformation, which depends mainly on their location in the building plan (accounting for eccentric effects);
- walls transmit their share of the horizontal load even in the nonlinear range, but only until their deformations exceed the deformations at the failure limit (defined by the masonry's ductility for the considered failure mechanism).

- Geometry

The user models the masonry structure as macro elements (walls, piers) for each storey separately. The rigid horizontal ties (reinforced concrete beams or steel ties) are assumed to guarantee a box like behaviour where all walls contribute to the storey load bearing capacity. The distribution of seismic action among the resisting elements (walls) is according to their stiffness and is limited by their load bearing capacity (considering both strength and deformation). The out of plane behaviour is not considered in the analysis. Also, spandrels are assumed to be perfectly rigid.

Macro elements are usually symmetrically fixed into the structure except at the top floor, where a cantilever boundary condition is considered to determine the stiffness and strength of the piers.

- Vertical loads

The vertical loads transmitted by the floors (including masonry self-weight) must be assigned manually as vertical loads on macro elements.

- Material properties

Masonry is assumed as an equivalent isotropic material. The user provides the basic masonry mechanical characteristics in terms of Young's modulus and shear modulus, compressive strength, and referential diagonal tensile strength (approx., 1.5 times the shear strength) .

The designer prepares the geometry and the material data (Fig. 3.4.1) in an Excel file.

n	dx [m]	dy [m]	x [m]	y [m]	sig.o [MPa]	h_x [m]	h_y [m]	boudary
Pilot PRO-SIS_01								
9								
1	1,050	0,250	0,525	0,175	0,130	2,22	3	1
2	1,250	0,250	2,875	0,175	0,220	1,4	3	1
3	1,050	0,250	5,225	0,175	0,130	2,22	3	1
4	1,050	0,250	0,525	4,175	0,140	2,22	3	1
5	1,250	0,250	2,875	4,175	0,220	1,4	3	1
6	1,050	0,250	5,225	4,175	0,140	2,22	3	1
7	0,250	4,350	0,175	2,175	0,100	3	3	1
8	0,250	1,400	5,575	0,875	0,130	3	1,4	1
9	0,250	1,750	5,575	3,300	0,130	3	1,4	1

n	tip zidu (izberi s seznama)	način	E [MPa]	G [MPa]	fc [MPa]	ft [MPa]	du.s [-]	du.f [-]
Pilot_01								
9								
1	parametric	1. klasika - TČ	1	1500	500	3,450	0,135	0,005
2	parametric	1. klasika - TČ	1	1500	500	3,450	0,135	0,005
3	parametric	1. klasika - TČ	1	1500	500	3,450	0,135	0,005
4	parametric	1. klasika - TČ	1	1500	500	3,450	0,135	0,005

Fig. 3.4.1 Input for definition of geometry and material data

3.4.2. Analysis features

The storey hysteresis envelope is the sum of the hysteresis envelopes of the walls that constitute the storey. The behaviour of individual walls under horizontal loads is an idealized elastoplastic hysteresis envelope, which is determined by the initial effective stiffness of the wall, its load-bearing capacity, and the ductility factor that limits the deformation of the wall in the inelastic range. The total storey horizontal force is distributed to the walls in proportion to their stiffnesses. The lower between the bending and shear load-bearing capacity is considered for determining the deformation at the elastic limit. The elastic stiffness of an individual wall is calculated using Eq. 3.8.

$$K_e = \frac{G \cdot A_w}{1.2 \cdot h \cdot \left[1 + \frac{G}{c \cdot E} \left(\frac{h}{l} \right)^2 \right]} \quad (3.8)$$

where:

- l masonry pier width
- h masonry pier height (i.e. "effective length")
- A_w wall horizontal cross section ($l \cdot t$)
- E elastic modulus of masonry (initial)
- G shear modulus of masonry
- c wall stress coefficient (1.2 in the case of symmetric and 0.3 in the case of cantilever boundary conditions)

For unstrengthened wall (pier) elements, the resistance to horizontal loads ($V_{P,URM}$) is the lowest value between bending ($V_{P,f,URM}$) and shear resistance ($V_{P,d,URM}$), which are determined through Eqs. 3.10 and 3.11, respectively:

$$V_{P,d(URM)} = \min(V_{P,f(URM)}; V_{P,d(URM)}) \quad (3.9)$$

$$V_{P,f(URM)} = \frac{\sigma_0 \cdot t \cdot l_p^2}{2 \cdot \alpha \cdot h} \left(1 - \frac{\sigma_0}{f_m} \right) \quad (3.10)$$

$$V_{P,d(URM)} = A_w \frac{f_t}{\beta} \sqrt{1 + \frac{\sigma_0}{f_t}} \quad (3.11)$$

Where:

- t masonry wall/pier thickness
- σ_0 mean compressive stress on the wall
- α stress coefficient for the bending moment (0.5 for symmetric and 1.0 for the cantilever boundary conditions)
- f_m masonry vertical compressive strength
- f_t masonry referential diagonal tensile strength
- β shear stress distribution factor in the wall (h/l but between 1,5 and 1,0)

From the idealized load capacity of the wall and its initial stiffness, the displacement at the elastic limit is obtained. The ultimate displacement (rotation) of the wall for shear and bending failure mechanisms is defined in the input data.

For the in-plane shear mechanism, the software considers the Turnšek-Čačovič formulation [12]. For the in-plane bending mechanism of piers, the software accounts only for the masonry compressive resistance and the stabilizing effect of the vertical loads.

According to the EC8 standard, the total ultimate transverse force due to an earthquake (ultimate base shear coefficient) is determined as follows:

$$BSC_u = \gamma_I \cdot a_{gR} \cdot S \cdot \frac{2.5}{q} \quad (3.12)$$

where:

- γ_I Importance factor
- a_{gR} reference peak ground acceleration
- S soil factor
- q structural behaviour factor

The storey resistance (SRC) is defined as the ultimate load capacity of the storey divided by the weight of the building above it. This coefficient (SRC) must be greater than the seismic load coefficient (BSC) calculated according to the EC8-1 standard:

$$BSC \leq SRC \quad \text{or} \quad E_d \leq R_d \quad (3.13)$$

In addition to the load capacity, the critical storey must also have sufficient ductility, which is determined from the structural behaviour factor (q). This factor reduces the force based on the ability of the structure to inelastically absorb the seismic load by means of hysteretic damping.

The calculated idealized ductility of the critical floor (μ) must be greater than the ultimate ductility (μ_u).

$$\mu_u = \frac{q^2 + 1}{2} \tag{3.14}$$

with:

$$\mu_u \leq \mu$$

Once the input data are provided, the user runs the program (written in Matlab/Octave), and the results are presented graphically (Fig. 3.4.2) and stored in output files.

Fig. 3.4.2 Results of SREMB :storey envelopes for push-over in one direction and 3D representation of elements near failure – coloured by utilization

3.4.3. How to account for CRM

SREMB implements equations for calculating strength of masonry elements strengthened with FRM, accordingly to CNR-DT 215/2018 [15]. The user defines appropriate material data to account for the CRM in the input Excel file (Fig. 3.4.3) and also increases ultimate drift limits.

n	tip zidu (izberi s seznama)	način	E [MPa]	G [MPa]	fc [MPa]	ft [MPa]	du.s [-]	du.f [-]
Pilot_01								
5	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM	5	2700	980	3,450	0,135	0,01	0,02
6	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM	5	2700	980	3,450	0,135	0,01	0,02
7	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM	5	2700	980	3,450	0,135	0,01	0,02
8	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM	5	2700	980	3,450	0,135	0,01	0,02

		način računa	vnos karakteristik za FRCM - CRN-DT 215:2018												
n	tip zidu (izberi s seznama)		splošni koef.	tau.0 [MPa]	gama.Rd	n.f	t.vf [mm]	l.f [m]	d.t [m]	alfa.t	E.fd [MPa]	eps.fd [mm/m]	eps.mu [mm/m]		
5	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM		1	0,09	1	1	0,029	1,65	2,25	1	72700	18,5	35		
6	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM		1	0,09	1	1	0,029	2,5	2,50	1	72700	18,5	35		
7	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM		1	0,09	1	1	0,029	0,25	0,25	1	72700	18,5	35		
8	parametric+FRCM 5. FRCM/TRM		1	0,09	1	1	0,029	0,25	0,25	1	72700	18,5	35		

Fig. 3.4.3 Input data for CRM

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Appendix A.

The “Equivalent frame” model for masonry buildings

The “Equivalent frame” method [17] for the modelling of masonry walls and structures basically consists in schematizing the structure into an equivalent frame system composed of vertical and horizontal resisting structural macro-elements (i.e. the piers and the spandrels) connected by means of rigid nodes (Fig. A 1a). Each macro-element is represented as a beam element along its principal centroid axis, with nodes positioned at the intersections with the centroid axes of the orthogonal connected elements. Infinitely rigid segments at the ends of the masonry macro-elements allow to model the reduced deformability of the structural nodes.

The length of the deformable part of a pier, i.e. the effective length l_{eff} , can be calculated by applying Eq. (A.1):

$$l_{eff} = l' + \frac{b(H - l')}{3l'} \leq H \quad (A.1)$$

being l' the conventional length determined accordingly to Fig. A 1b, b the pier width, H the net interstory height. The effective deformable portion is located proportionally to the length of the lower and upper rigid parts, as specified by Eq. A.2.

$$l_{inf,eff} = l_{inf} \left(1 - \frac{l_{eff} - l'}{l_{inf} + l_{sup}} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad l_{sup,eff} = l_{sup} \left(1 - \frac{l_{eff} - l'}{l_{inf} + l_{sup}} \right) \quad (A.2)$$

being, l_{inf} and l_{sup} the conventional length of the lower and upper rigid parts of the vertical element ($l_{inf} + l' + l_{sup} = H$).

The elastic deformation of the structural elements depends on the elasticity of the beam elements, while the inelastic response is lumped in rotational and shear plastic hinges. The rotational plastic hinges at the ends of the beam elements simulate the inelastic in-plane bending response, while the shear plastic hinge at mid-length represents the inelastic in-plane shear response.

Fig. A 1 Modelling of a masonry wall according to the Equivalent frame method (a), definition of the effective pier length (b), and location of the lumped plasticity hinges (c)

Appendix B.

Analytical calculations for validation

The numerical models are validated with reference to a pier and a spandrel element, represented in Fig. 3.4.1. The masonry and CRM characteristics adopted are reported in Table B.1. The pier is subjected to a vertical stress of 0.3 MPa and both the shear-type (*st*) and the cantilever (*ct*) beam static schemes are considered. The spandrel is assumed to have an effective horizontal steel tie. The main parameters assumed in the calculations are those collected in Table B.1.

Fig. 3.4.1 Benchmark examples: (a) pier and (b) spandrel elements (measures in mm)

Table B.1: Main characteristics for the benchmark examples.

ID	Value	Unit	Description
t_m	250	mm	masonry thickness
b'	800	mm	net masonry spandrel height (typically, lintel is not considered)
E_m	1500	MPa	secant Young's modulus of masonry
G_m	500	MPa	shear modulus of masonry ($E_m/3$)
f_m	3.45	MPa	vertical compressive strength
$f_{m,h}$	1.725	MPa	horizontal compressive strength ($f_m/2$)
τ_0	0.09	MPa	equivalent masonry shear strength under zero vertical stress
H_p	100	kN	resistance of the horizontal tie of the spandrel
T_G	5.11	kN	tensile resistance of a GFRP wire.
s	66	mm	GFRP mesh grid pitch
t_c	30	mm	mortar coating thickness
E_c	10000	MPa	secant Young's modulus of the coating mortar
H_p	100	kN	tensile resistance of the horizontal steel tie

To schematize analytically, in a simplified way, the in-plane lateral performances of masonry piers and spandrels, an elastic-plastic behaviour is considered. To estimate the stiffness, resistance and ultimate displacement capacities, the analytical correlations presented in [5] are adopted. Note that, in case of spandrels provided with both effective horizontal tie and CRM, in the correlation for the bending resistance it is assumed $\sigma_0 = H_p/(b't)$, considering both tensile failure of the mesh and crushing of the masonry as potential failure modes.

Table B.2: Analytical calculations concerning the benchmark pier (shear-type scheme).

Pier_st_0.3		URM	R1	R2
i	[-]	-	1	2
χ	[-]	-	1.0	1.0
f_m	[MPa]	3.45	3.45	3.45
E	[MPa]	1500	2700	3900
G	[MPa]	500	980	1460
K_e	[kN/mm]	42.7	80.9	119.0
x	[mm]	-	195.1	248.3
M_p	[kNm]	52.6	84.8	112.6
$V_{p,f}$	[kN]	56.1	90.4	120.1
$V_{p,d}$	[kN]	50.5	98.9	147.3
V_p	[kN]	50.5	90.4	120.1
Mode	[-]	Diag. cracking	Bending	Bending
$d_{p,e}$	[mm]	1.18	1.18	1.08
$d_{p,u}$	[mm]	9.4	37.5	37.5

Table B.3: Analytical calculations concerning the benchmark pier (cantilever beam scheme)

Pier_ct_0.3		URM	R1	R2
i	[-]	-	1	2
χ	[-]	-	1.0	1.0
f_m	[MPa]	3.45	3.45	3.45
E	[MPa]	1500	2700	3900
G	[MPa]	500	980	1460
K_e	[kN/mm]	19.8	36.5	53.2
x	[mm]	-	195.1	248.3
M_p	[kNm]	52.6	84.8	112.6
$V_{p,f}$	[kN]	22.2	35.8	47.6
$V_{p,d}$	[kN]	50.5	98.9	147.3
V_p	[kN]	22.2	35.8	47.6
Mode	[-]	Bending	Bending	Bending
$d_{p,e}$	[mm]	1.12	1.00	0.92
$d_{p,u}$	[mm]	18.8	37.5	37.5

Table B.4: Analytical calculations concerning the benchmark spandrel.

Spandrel		URM	R1	R2
i	[-]	-	1	2
χ	[-]	-	1.0	1.0
f_{hd}	[MPa]	1.73	1.73	1.73
E	[MPa]	1500	2700	3900
G	[MPa]	500	980	1460
K_e	[kN/mm]	66.9	128.1	189.1
x	[mm]	-	301.0	309.7
M_s	[kNm]	26.4	29.0*	29.5*
$V_{s,f}$	[kN]	43.9	48.4	49.2
$V_{s,d}$	[kN]	18.0	41.8	72.7
$V'_{s,d}$	[kN]	10.8	-	-
V_s	[kN]	18.0	41.8	49.2
Mode	[-]	Diag. cracking	Diag. cracking	Bending
$d_{s,e}$	[mm]	0.27	0.21	0.26
$d_{s,u}$	[mm]	6.0	36.0	36.0

* In both reinforced configurations, bending failure occurs due to masonry crushing, so the R2 configuration results in only a slight increase in the bending resistance in respect to the R1 configuration.

Legend:

- i number of CRM-strengthened sides (1-2)
- χ effectiveness reduction factor (=1 for CRM at both-sides, ≤ 1 at one side)
- K_e elastic stiffness
- x depth of the neutral axis of the cracked cross-section
- M resisting bending moment
- V_f in-plane lateral resistance related to bending mechanism
- V_d in-plane lateral resistance related to diagonal cracking mechanism
- V in-plane lateral resistance
- d_e yield displacement
- d_u ultimate displacement